

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D1.4

Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in marketing and data

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Glossary

Association pour le Maintien d'une Agriculture Paysanne (AMAP, Association for Maintaining Small Scale Family Farming, sometimes also literally translated as Peasant Agriculture).

It is generally agreed in France that CSA (Community-Supported Agriculture, see below) coincides with AMAP. AMAP is a local, solidarity-based partnership between a producer and a group of consumers. AMAP is indeed an association (and not a business) that supports the relationship between a consumer group and a local producer. These two parts, the producer and each consumer, are linked through a written contract-based direct-sales system. The idea is to make sure the farmer can rely on a guaranteed income that will continue to provide a decent living for that farmer for the next year at the very least. The original idea was to make it possible for smallholders to keep their business alive through strong support from consumers' groups. Risk sharing is the key to the AMAP model. In the AMAP model the producer signs a written contract with each consumer for several months or one year. <https://urgenci.net/france/>

Community Supported Agriculture (CSA)

“CSA is a direct partnership based on the human relationship between people and one or several producer(s), whereby the risks, responsibilities, and rewards of farming are shared, through a long-term, binding agreement.” <https://urgenci.net/our-european-declaration/> Outside of France, many CSAs have formalised into independent associations whereby the association organises the aggregation of products from more than one producer for consumer groups. It is for this reason that in this study CSAs are considered intermediaries as they are increasing emerging as a separate legal entity from producers.

Consumer

In the context of this study, consumers refer to the people who eat food. They can be purchasing this food that they each directly from farmers, shops, restaurants or other food service providers or they can be consuming what they produce themselves. Therefore, while there is often a commercial transaction that occurs that defines this category of food system actors, we are referring to the group as having interests and characteristics that are not limited only to their commercial transactions.

Consumption Influencers

This term refers to those actors in the value chain that shape food consumption patterns. They can influence consumption by controlling what products are available for purchase in retail outlets and food service, by purchasing and cooking food for others within the home, or by shaping the meaning of food consumption by promoting specific products or brands through different communication channels including social media, training courses, seminars or written materials (Shah and Asghar 2023)

Food environments

“Food environments are the physical, economic, political and socio-cultural contexts in which people engage with the food system to make their decisions about acquiring, preparing and

consuming food.” (www.eph.org). A short video on the concept: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5cUaro1gUcI>

Food value chain

“A food value chain consists of all the stakeholders who participate in the coordinated production and value adding activities that are needed to make food products” (FAO 2014) <https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en?details=I3953E>

Intermediary

Intermediaries are food system actors positioned between producers and consumers and who facilitate the creation of value for food as it moves from the sites of production to the sites of consumption (Loconto et al., 2018). In the context of this study, intermediaries include associations, non-governmental organisations, CSAs, online platforms, processors, traders, aggregators, wholesalers, food service providers, transporters, restaurants and shops.

Local Solidarity-based Partnerships for Agroecology (LSPA)

“LSPA initiatives typically involve multiple stakeholders from the local food systems: producers, consumers, researchers, local officials, etc. They are based upon partnership, local exchange, or direct relationships where producers can earn decent livelihoods, and consumers share the risks and rewards of sustainable agriculture in return for their share of healthy, nutritious, locally-grown food. There is no fixed way of organizing these partnerships: it is a framework to inspire communities to work together with their local farmers, provide mutual benefits and social cohesion, and reconnect people with one another and to the land where their food is grown. These partnerships are experiments of social innovation defined by their values rather than fixed operational mechanisms or schemes.” <https://urgenci.net/about-us/>

Long supply chains

A “long supply chain” typically involves multiple intermediaries, but the exact number can vary depending on the industry and the specific supply chain. Generally, a long supply chain has five or more intermediaries. These intermediaries can include suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, distributors, retailers, and sometimes even additional third-party logistics providers (Christopher, 2023).

Mid-tier value chains

Mid-tier value chains try to capture this middle space where medium-scale farmers, who are too big for direct sales but too small to reach industrial economies of scale, are able to access quality-based markets (Lev and Stevenson 2011). They typically have more than 1 intermediary between farmers and end consumers.

Neglected and under-utilised crop (NUC)

“NUCs are domesticated plant species that have been cultivated or consumed as food throughout human history but have been reduced in importance over time... with many of them actually disappearing.” (da Silva, FAO, 2012).

In the DIVINFOOD Project, the cereal and legume varieties that are considered NUCs for the purposes of our study are the following:

1. Chickpea – Hungarian local landraces – (*Cicer arietinum*)
2. Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*)
3. Lingot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*)
4. Meat bean (Chartreuse and Oisans beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*))
5. Lima bean (*Phaseolus lunatus*)
6. Lentils (*Lens culinaris*)
7. Blue lupine (*Lupinus angustifolius*)
8. White lupine (*Lupinus albus*)
9. Fava bean (*Vicia faba*)
10. Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*)
11. Pea (*Pisum sativum*)
12. Grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*)
13. Grey pea (*Pisum sativum* subsp. *arvense*)
14. Einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*)
15. Emmer (*Triticum dicoccum*)
16. Rivet wheat (*Triticum turgidum*)

NUC environment

We define “NUC environment” in this paper as the specific food environment (the physical, economic, political and socio-cultural contexts) in which citizen-consumers and institutions engage with neglected and under-utilised crops (NUCs).

Producer

We use this term to refer to food system actors who are engaged in production activities, which according to FAO is “the production of raw agricultural, livestock, fisheries and forestry products”. Therefore, this term refers to farmers, fisherfolk, pastoralists, apiculturists, wild food collectors, livestock raisers, etc. <https://www.fao.org/sustainable-food-value-chains/what-is-it/sfvc-vocabulary/en/>

Short food supply chain (SFSC)

“The foods involved are identified by, and traceable to a farmer. The number of intermediaries between farmer and consumer should be ‘minimal’ or ideally nil.” (Kneafsey et al. 2013, p. 42).

Article 2 of Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 “A short supply chain means 'a supply chain involving a limited number of economic operators, committed to cooperation, local economic development, and close geographical and social relations between producers, processors and consumers'". <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1465486207958&uri=CELEX:32013R1305>

This definition is complemented by Article 11 of European Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 807/2014 supplementing the Rural Development Regulation, which stipulates that 'Support for the establishment and development of short supply chains... shall cover only supply

chains involving no more than one intermediary between farmer and consumer'. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1465486255450&uri=CELEX:32014R0807>

Third place

“Third places are usually physical spaces where activities that are normally separate can be combined, allowing unlikely encounters between people who would not meet elsewhere, with a hybrid economic model in which for-profit activities support activities that are not for profit. They create all the conditions needed to allow everyone to suggest activities. They are places where individuals can realise their potential through the collective (...). Initially, the term referred to an intermediary place that was neither home, nor work. The term has been adopted throughout Europe but it is in France that the movement is the most structured and receives the most public support”. <https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/blog/third-places-and-learning>

Value Chain

This deliverable introduces a new understanding of value chain in order to capture a meaning of the value that is created through the sale of NUCs in the food environment. Based on the characteristics of “values-based food supply chains” (Ostrom et al. 2018), we use the term ‘value chain’ as those “supply chains that value” a specific product that is grown in a specified way and manifests consistent qualities. In this sense the word value has two meanings: the first is related to the “worth” of the product for those who are dealing with it, while the second refers to the economic, environmental, cultural, social, and political values that are created, maintained and transmitted through its trade. To build our typology, we differentiate between those value chain captains who organise the relationships between producers and consumers according to different degrees of transparency in the communication of values up and down the chains that they manage (Feenstra and Hardesty, 2016).

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Executive summary

DIVINFOOD Task 1.2 focuses on analysing the value of products based on neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) in food environments. The core activity of this task is to collect primary data from actors working with NUCs in the food environments of the seven countries involved in the DIVINFOOD project (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden and Switzerland).

Objective

The objective of this deliverable is to propose a typology of short and mid-tier chains successfully valuing NUCs, including SMART indexes to assess the benefits of NUCs use in marketing, as well as empirical data, based on data collection through questionnaires addressed to value chain actors and participatory modelling with experts including ‘consumption influencers’.

Results

The report presents four distinct, but interrelated, results. These results are: 1) the contextualisation of the NUC environment at national level; 2) empirical data resulting from a survey of 78 market initiatives that value the DIVINFOOD NUCs; 3) a typology of short and mid-tier chains that value agrobiodiversity; and 4) SMART indexes to assess the benefits of NUCs use in marketing. We summarise here each of our key findings.

NUC environments: To contextualise the NUC environment in which the presented value chains operate, we collected and analysed the primarily production data of NUC legumes and minor cereals grains involved in the project, in the participating countries. Overall, we find that there is a declining trend in the production of legumes and cereals in the six countries where we could access data.

Empirical survey data: We built a database of more than 1,200 initiatives that deal with NUCs and are visible on Internet, and conducted an online survey that collected 78 responses from organisations that value NUCs in the seven countries. Our core finding, that the majority of the initiatives that we identified are short value chains (many with direct sales to consumers), confirms the literature that has claimed that short food chains are mainly producer-driven and these actors are increasingly adopting intermediation activities.

The majority of initiatives were founded after 2011 and NUCs sales represent less than 25% of the commercial activity for more than half of the initiatives. The initiatives are specialised in few NUCs, dealing mostly with 1-2 types. Wheat ancient/local is the most common minor cereal, while lentils, peas, common beans, and chickpeas are the most traded legumes. The NUCs’ origin suggests that these short supply chains rely upon regional or even national chains rather than on their own municipality or local territory. Furthermore, we observed a wide variety of modalities of sourcing and selling NUCs suggesting that diversity in marketing channels is a core strategy.

The proportion of ‘binding’ contracts with suppliers is low and the results suggest that NUCs related activities are not significant enough in terms of sales to warrant entering into long term agreements among supply chain actors. Instead, one’s own production is often sufficient and purchasing on demand is feasible based on non-contractual relationships between the retailers

and the producers. Additionally, this is also a sector that is characterised by experimentation and seed exchanges, which means that the social engagement goes beyond pure market exchanges.

The sampled initiatives position themselves primarily around environmental concerns, which the majority actively promote through social media and by word of mouth. The social missions are more concerned with the model of agriculture that is unfair to both the agroecosystems and farmers, than with the nutritional benefits of NUCs. The sector relies heavily on organic certification and the perceived benefits from selling NUCs is mainly environmental. The NUCs sellers have a rather loyal customer base. Regarding the challenges of producing, processing or selling NUCs, the challenges of insufficient demand and lack of consumer awareness emerged as the most critical.

Value chain typology: Based on our survey analysis, a participatory modelling workshop with experts from the 7 DIVINFOOD partner countries, and a final validation with the DIVINFOOD partners at the project's annual meeting, we identified four main clusters of initiative-types, which we have denominated: 1) Active promoters, 2) Silent sellers, 3) Quality communicators and 4) Mission first initiatives. These types are distinguished based on the ways in which they rely upon certification to guarantee quality, the communication strategies used to communicate, value and promote NUCs, the number of missions driving their initiatives and the perceived benefits from selling NUCs.

SMART Indexes: Following from our survey findings and the characterisation of the value chain typology, we suggest some SMART Indexes that can assess the benefits of NUCs use in marketing: Differentiation from competitors, attraction/retention of consumers, higher profit margins, opportunities for value chain upgrading for farmers.

Together these results lead us to conclude that NUCs are currently being valued in food environments that are not very well suited for their promotion, with the lack of demand for these products remaining the main problem.

The first, tentative list of SMART indexes will be experimented with over the next few years as the DIVINFOOD partners develop new marketing strategies and channels. Specific work with digital tools dedicated to valuing (agro)biodiversity-use will be carried out in Tasks 1.3 and 1.4 of the project. The data already collected and those to come are or will be recorded in the database developed in Work Package 5, and the results from this report will also help partners of this Work Package to develop new business models.

Teams involved:

The work conducted for this deliverable was led by Agri Kulti and carried out in close collaboration with INRAE and the University of Pisa.

The deliverable was reviewed by Carlota Vaz Patto (UNL), Yuna Chiffolleau (INRAE) and Vincent Troillard (IT) NOVA.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background on DIVINFOOD

The context for the development and implementation of the DIVINFOOD project (Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food) is one of rapid decline of biodiversity, both globally and in Europe. The current heavy reliance on a small number of varieties is a threat to food security and deprives consumers of the nutritional quality of other species. Currently, small-scale producers and processors offer local food products valuing neglected and under-utilised species (NUCs) in short chains, thus helping to both reverse the decline in biodiversity and meeting this demand. However, they face many challenges, from insufficient availability of suitable varieties to difficulty in developing viable business models.

Given this, the overall objective of the project is to contribute to reversing the agrobiodiversity decline by producing knowledge and tools to support farmers and small-scale processors to develop short and mid-tier supply chains valuing NUCs and meeting consumer expectations of local, healthy, plant-based food. DIVINFOOD focuses on legumes and minor cereals, whose use in short and mid-tier chains is increasing, and whose potential for health and agroecology is high. The production of knowledge and tools, from breeding to marketing, involves citizen-consumers and relies on nine living labs (LLs) gathering all concerned stakeholders from seven partner countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland).

1.2 Background on DIVINFOOD Work Package 1

Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

DIVINFOOD uses an approach that considers all the activities that occur along the value chain of the NUC – from seed to plate - with a view to valorising NUCs and ultimately increasing their purchase and consumption. The first Work Package (WP) of the project begins with a focus on consumers and food environments so to better “guide” or inspire the valorisation process along the whole NUC value chain. Its work is founded on the assumption that there is a knowledge (and practice) gap with respect to the mechanisms, networks and physical infrastructures (i.e., food environments) that link the production and consumption ends of the value chain. It is for this reason that one of the objectives of WP 1 is that of better understanding how to influence both “engaged” and “regular” consumers in the valuing of agrobiodiversity, and in this respect, the role of the food retail environment is key.

Task 1.2, in particular, focuses on analysing NUCs-based products value in food environments by drawing on an extensive collection of primary data in the seven countries involved in the DIVINFOOD project. The current deliverable presents the results of that investigation.

1.3 Aims and scope of the study

This report constitutes Deliverable 1.4 of the DIVINFOOD project. It concludes Task 1.2, which aims at analysing the value of products based on NUCs in short- and mid-tier value chains. It follows up on Deliverable 1.3 – *Report on enabling food environments (existing shops, infrastructures, labels) valuing NUCs-based products* – where we presented a previous literature review on food environments, digital food environments, and consumer retail environments.

There, we concluded that based on the information available, retail spaces in Europe currently generally do not valorise NUCs - meaning that the food environment does not make it easy for consumers to choose and consume NUCs.

In this report (D1.4), we continue our research to find short- and mid-tier chains that – even in this non-enabling context – do valorise some NUCs. Deliverable 1.3 also presented a conceptual framework that established 4Ps of enabling consumer food environments for NUCs: P1, the availability of **products** (range of products in retail outlets); P2, the **placement** of products in retail spaces and in the broader food retail environment; P3, their **promotion** through a variety of communication means; and P4, the **price** and competitive nature of their markets. By constructing a survey inspired by this framework, we aimed to create a typology of the chains that successfully value NUCs by creating benefits from their sale. We additionally used the results of this analysis and typology to present a first attempt at a set of SMART indexes that enable food system actors to be able to identify the benefits of NUCs in the consumption space of food environments. Exploring the ways in which value chains and initiatives are successful in valorising NUCs will also help us later on in the project to set up such value chains and develop marketing strategies and digital tools to nudge citizen-consumers in the direction of consciously choosing NUCs and incorporating them into their diets.

In order to identify food environments in the seven DIVINFOOD countries that are conducive to the development of NUCs/NUCs-based products, an extensive search on the internet was made during the first trimester of 2023 to gather initiatives corresponding to short and mid-tier chains involved in the selling or valorisation of cereals and legumes NUCs. Although the focus was on finding initiatives dealing with NUCs, and in particular with the NUCs of the DIVINFOOD project, we expanded the search to initiatives that sold other cereals and/or legumes. This resulted in a database of 1,268 initiatives. Besides carrying out a lexical analysis of the self-description of these initiatives, a survey was sent out to their representatives and we gained 122 answers, 78 of which said they were concerned by NUCs.¹

Drawing on our results, we highlight that NUCs are currently being valued in food environments that are not very well suited for their promotion. The majority of chains studied are initiatives where the farmer has assumed a number of additional processing and institutional roles, which in some cases is a limit for their promotion. We have also found rather surprising similarities across the seven countries studied with the majority of differences being found between different actor types. For a more nuanced understanding of how value is created, further analysis was conducted to establish a typology of short- and mid-tier chains that successfully value NUCs. We grouped the initiatives into four ideal type clusters, based on the frequency of responses to key indicators, which we designated: 1) Active promoters, 2) Silent sellers, 3) Quality communicators and 4) Mission first initiatives.

1.4 Limitations of the study

This study has a number of limitations. First, there is a selection bias related to the way that the initiatives were identified that means that we have not included all of the initiatives that exist in all seven countries of study. We conducted an exhaustive search on the internet – including

¹ We used the definition of NUCs that is explained in the glossary.

Facebook and Instagram – however, this means that we captured only those initiatives that have a web presence. Second, while we did ask all DIVINFOOD partners in WP1 to check the lists of initiatives that we collected in order to delete or add initiatives to the list, not all partners are necessarily aware of all initiatives operating in the areas surrounding the Living Labs. Therefore, our list of initiatives is most likely also limited in terms of exhaustive coverage of the value chains that are linked to our living labs.

Third, our online survey was focused on activities relative to NUCS. However, several data from the questionnaire showed that the interpretation of what a NUCS is varies according to the initiatives, with some of them considering NUCs in a very broad sense (for example, "lentils"), while others were focalised on very specific and precise varieties. This may have had an impact on the way in which the initiatives responded to the questionnaire and also constitutes a limit to the proposed typology.

Fourth, while a 10% response rate is generally what is obtained for internet surveys, the low number of completed surveys created difficulties for the creation of a typology that fully captured the diversity of the value chains that exist for NUCs in the 7 countries of our study. Therefore, the value chain typology that we present in this report is a first attempt to classify the initiatives and will be improved upon as more data may be collected within the Living Labs and from the database. Finally, this same limitation of a low response rate for the study also means that there may be additional or alternative indicators that might be better suited for capturing the value of NUCs in the consumption sphere of food environments. We will continue to refine these indexes in T1.3/1.4 over the coming years.

Fifth, the data we collected from the 7 countries involved in the project to cultivation data of the NUCs involved in the project. Whilst the cultivation data itself is also rather limited, we did not extend the database we built here to include consumption data. The main reason for this has been that detailed NUC consumption data is generally not available, or not available to the partners involved in the preparation of this paper. Where such data is available, it has been deemed rather unreliable precisely because of the low levels of cultivation and consumption of these varieties.

1.5 Structure of the report

The structure of this report is as follows. In Section 2 after this introduction, we present a review of the current literature on food value chains and NUC value chains in particular. In Section 3, we briefly present the NUC environment of DIVINFOOD partner countries primarily based on NUC production data available in official databases. The aim of these two chapters is to contextualise the environment in which value chains operate to valorise NUCs and in which citizen-consumers must navigate if they wish to obtain them.

Section 4 presents our survey methodology. We explain in detail the purposive sampling strategy employed to identify those initiatives that deal with NUCs across Europe. We detail how the online survey was structured and carried out, and how we conducted an expert, participatory modelling workshop to validate the first version of the NUC value chain typology derived from the survey results.

Section 5 discusses the results of the online survey in detail, focusing on those initiatives that self-reported dealing with NUCs. Drawing on the theories of value chains discussed in Section 2 and the survey results presented in Section 5, Section 6 maps out the typology of short- and mid-tier

chains valuing (agro)biodiversity. Here, the four key clusters are described, with case studies in Appendix 7 from each partner country that illustrate both the typical elements and the diversity found across the surveyed initiatives. A first tentative attempt to present SMART indicators is included in this section. In Section 7, we summarise our results and map out further directions for research. We conclude with reflections about how Deliverable 1.4 and its results will aid the DIVINFOOD project in its future work.

As will be explained in this document, given the lack of literature and data available on food chains that value NUCs, we decided to develop a database of initiatives in order to document as many situations as possible with empirical data. Setting up this database, which was not planned as such in the task, took time, but the final result (more than 1,200 initiatives identified and recorded) is significant, and the data base has been published in open access in the space dedicated to the DIVINFOOD project on the Zenodo directory: <https://zenodo.org/records/12775303>. In addition, following the participatory modelling workshop in which we submitted a first typology of chains based on the initial data collected, we extended the data collection to take better account of the experts' comments and built a second typology, which we validated with the project partners at the annual meeting in June 2024. This iterative process explains the delay of a few months in submitting the deliverable, but this delay has enabled us to produce results that better reflect the diversity of food chains that value NUCs in the 7 DIVINFOOD countries and will therefore be more useful for developing the rest of the project.

2. Literature review

In Deliverable 1.3, we presented the concepts of food environments, digital food environments, food retail environments and consumer retail environments. That literature review presented a broad conceptual framework for understanding this unique zone of interaction among producers, intermediaries and consumers as they transform seeds, plants and animals into food.

In the present literature review, we focus now on food value chains (FVC), which “consist of all the stakeholders who participate in the coordinated production and value-adding activities that are needed to make food products” (FAO 2014). The term “value chain” was coined by Michael Porter (1985) as a management tool that could help firms first to identify and then exploit their competitive advantage within an industry, to “create shared value” among supply chain actors (Porter and Kramer 2011)

About 20 years ago, the concept of *circuit court* (Chiffolleau 2008) or **short food supply chain** (SFSC) emerged (Renting et al. 2003; Marsden et al. 2000), where short supply chains are defined as those with few (maximum one) intermediaries, between farmers and consumers (Santini et al. 2013). In common understanding, SFSCs are considered to be short based on criteria of social and geographic proximity. Given that there was a wide variety of SFSCs across Europe at the time, Kneafsey et al. (2013), put forward the following definition – based on French ministerial and the European Commission (EC) definitions – in order to separate these initiatives from conventional food chains.

“The foods involved are identified by, and traceable to a farmer. The number of intermediaries between farmer and consumer should be ‘minimal’ or ideally nil.” (p. 42).

Subsequent EU regulations in 2013 and 2014 determined that the number of intermediaries would be thus used as the official means to determine the length of a supply chain. Short supply chains thus were referred to as those with no more than one intermediary.²

While the European Union (EU) average for farms selling more than half of their production direct to consumers is near 15%, this is distributed unevenly among member nations and is largely restricted to small farms (Augère-Granier 2016). Direct sales had minor importance in Malta, Austria and Spain, where supermarkets dominate food retail with more than 90% market share. However, direct sales, traditional specialty shops and food markets are very important in other countries. Direct sales account for 25% in Greece, 21% in France, 19% in Slovakia and around 18% in Hungary, Romania and Estonia (Augère-Granier 2016). In addition, a nationally representative survey in France found that 42% of consumers regularly purchase food through a SFSC (Loisel et al. 2016).

Mid-tier value chains try to capture this middle space where medium-scale farmers, who are too big for direct sales but too small to reach industrial economies of scale, are able to access quality-based markets (Lev and Stevenson 2011). A lot of the work in this area has tried to elaborate how Porter's (1985) five primary activities of value chains – Inbound Logistics, Operations, Outbound Logistics, Marketing & Sales and Services – can be organised differently based on different combinations of intermediaries. The contribution of the research presented here is our attempt to bridge the notion of value chains as a means of coordinating upstream and downstream commercial transactions and the idea that these chains of relations are also creating myriad values as they link farmers to consumers of food (Loconto 2012).

2.1 Evolutions in value chain typologies

In the 1990s, increased attention was focused on the very long value chains that spanned the globe – global value chains (GVC) (Gereffi 1994). Questions of concern emerged in this literature about how such long, diverse chains were coordinated and more precisely governed by powerful actors who requested very specific quality compliance through the use of certification (Ponte, Gereffi and Raj-Reichert 2019). These types of governance are differentiated according to: (1) complexity of inter-firm transactions; (2) the degree to which this complexity can be mitigated through codification; and (3) the extent to which suppliers have the necessary capabilities to meet the buyers' requirements (Gereffi et al. 2005). There are three main trends in GVC governance:

- Producer-driven – where low-profit activities are out-sourced upstream to networks of suppliers, bound by contract to produce according to rigorously specified product and process standards) (Gereffi and Korzeniewicz 1994). In these cases, the producers are the raw ingredient producers who are farming on a large scale and also are typically carrying out aggregating functions by sourcing from smaller farmers to create large economies of scale that feed into long value chains.
- Buyer-driven – with high barriers to entry and high profits located at the retail end with the protection and promotion of brands (Conroy 2007; Gereffi et al. 2005; Gereffi and Korzeniewicz 1994); or where large retail establishments use their market power to

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1465486255450&uri=CELEX:32014R0807>

effectively govern the production of commodities with the desired attributes (Fold and Larsen 2008; Law 1991);

- Twin-driven – where lead firms govern the supply network, while environmental groups/movements and third-party certifiers/standards developers govern the regulatory aspects of the network (Islam 2008).

While these typologies focus on economic power within the organisation of value chains, cultural power is also vital to their governance (cf. Dixon 1999; Friedberg 2004), particularly with respect to notions about quality (Gibbon and Ponte 2005; Ponte and Gibbon 2005) and stakeholder preference (cf. Ochieng 2008; Pirsch et al. 2007). Indeed, in the 2010s, a body of literature emerged that tried to examine how value chains moved beyond actor and product coordination towards governing the production of alternative values like fairness or sustainability (Loconto 2012). A range of values was found to be produced through attempts to govern qualities that were tied to a notion of place (origin, local, territory, proximity) (Fleury et al. 2016).

In the 2000s, “green” value chains were introduced as a concept where environmental and social indicators are taken into consideration in determining the sustainability of the supply chain (Carter and Rogers 2008). However, an interesting concept emerged in the 2010s around “values-based food supply chains” that explained how mid-tier chains were beginning to form directly through producers and their supply chain partners to ensure high-quality, diversified products that were fully traceable (Ostrom et al. 2018). Feenstra and Hardesty (2016) clarified three characteristics of these values-based chains that were able to support regional economies: (1) transparency in communicating values throughout the supply chain; (2) the ease with which they can coordinate purchases from small and mid-scale producers; and (3) the extent to which they provide fair prices to farmers versus remaining competitive in the marketplace. Building upon van der Ploeg et al.’s (2012) notion of nested markets, a typology has been introduced that qualifies how values define the producer-consumer relations through information-rich, socio-cultural, diversified or interactive intermediation (Loconto et al. 2018).

Recent consumer research demonstrates that trust-worthiness of food chain actors and the openness of food manufacturers are strongly related to consumer confidence in food (Macready et al. 2020). Thus, the assumption of SFSC promoters is that this greater transparency translates into greater consumer confidence in farmers and as a result, more social, equitable and fairer trading practices between farmers and consumers. However, these values require infrastructures that enable farmers, intermediaries and consumers to assess and ensure the quality of food that is traded through SFSCs as the industrial food system infrastructures are usually ill adapted to dealing with small and medium volumes and distances.

2.2 Communicating values and qualities in SFSCs

In preparation for the launch of the DIVINFOOD project, we conducted a literature review about short food supply chains where we tried to identify the questions of transparency in communicating values throughout the supply chain that are of concern for values-based value chains (Loconto and Garrido-Garza 2021). In this section, we present that first project preparatory literature review so that the state of the art that was used to construct our present survey instrument and our value chain typology are clear.

In that preparatory review, which was conducted via a Scopus search resulting in 2,397 articles studying quality assessment and short food value chains, the first study dated from 1975, but the number of publications only began to increase continuously around 2000.

The first study highlighted in the preparatory review presented, quite possibly for the first time, an analysis of the role played by consumer-facing labels and certifications symbols in the decision-making process (Parkinson, 1975). The focus on consumer recognition of labels has become quite important since that time, with a significant amount of research conducted upon consumer behaviour and consumer preferences – particularly related to ethical and other green or sustainability labels (425 articles). This trend emerges from studies in marketing that have assessed the ability of consumers to be able to recognise specific labels and to ignore those that do not add significant information (Drugova et al. 2020). The use of purchasing practices by individual consumers as a means to make a political statement, complemented by the increase in celebrity chefs who take a political stance (Phillipov and Gale 2020), has only grown since it was first theorised in 2005 (DuPuis and Goodman 2005).

According to Schenk et al. (2016), consumer purchasing power does not influence the national sales of ethical products, but moral convictions and the range of products available for sale (in supermarkets) are consequential. Market growth for ethical or green products therefore depends crucially on whether or not supermarkets include these products in their range. A report from the International Trade Centre (2019) found that European retailers give high priority to sustainable product sourcing, as they assume strong consumer support and expect sustainable businesses to increase significantly in the coming years. According to this report, 96 percent of retailers interviewed have sustainable sourcing strategies, but it remains unclear in the literature why companies choose one label over another, and many develop their own quality assurance schemes (Chkanikova and Lehner 2015; Chkanikova 2016). What seems clear, however, is that supermarkets can choose between competing sustainability alternatives (Arnold & Hasse 2015; Reinecke et al. 2012).

Recent EuroBarometer special reports (2020)³ asked citizens about their priorities in purchasing food. Overall, Europeans prioritise taste (45%), food safety (42%) and cost (40%) over sustainability concerns when purchasing food. The remaining characteristics follow in terms of order of importance: origin of the food (34%), nutrient content (33%), product shelf-life (20%), “minimally processed” (16%), personal “ethics and beliefs” (e.g., animal welfare concerns) (16%), and “environmental and climate impact” (15%). Surprisingly, “convenience” (9%) is the least influencing factor – which indicates a shift from the supermarket mentality among consumers.

Food is considerable “sustainable” when it is nutritious and healthy (41%), has been produced with little or no use of pesticides (32%) and when it is affordable for all (29%). “Local or short supply chains” (24%) and “low environmental and climate impact” of food (22%) remain

³ EU citizens, agriculture and the CAP

<https://ec.europa.eu/comfrontoffice/publicopinion/index.cfm/Survey/getSurveyDetail/instruments/PECIAL/surveyKy/2229>

Making our food fit for the future – Citizens' expectations

<https://ec.europa.eu/comfrontoffice/publicopinion/index.cfm/survey/getsurveydetail/instruments/spacial/surveyky/2241>

important characteristics of sustainable food systems but are not as important as the notion of a healthy diet for them as consumers (74%). The latter is described as eating a “variety of different foods, having a balanced diet” (58%) and “eating more fruit and vegetables” (58%). A healthy diet is seasonal (50%), local (47%), and consist of “eating more home-cooked meals” (43%), with “little or no pesticides” (43%), “avoiding wasting food” (42%) and “avoiding or not eating too much food high in fat sugars and/or salt” (40%).

The 2020 State of Food Insecurity Report from FAO introduced a global metric for healthy diets and claimed that 3 billion people around the world could not afford a healthy diet and 18 million of them lived in North America and Europe (FAO et al. 2020). According to the Eurobarometer survey in 2020, two thirds of Europeans say that they eat a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time (56%) or always (10%). However, there are significant differences across Member States, ranging from the top range in the Netherlands (83%) and Finland (81%), to the low range in Bulgaria (32%) and Lithuania (46%). Affordability and availability of healthy, sustainable choices and clear information on food labelling are the recommendations from this report.

The historical literature suggests that information and labelling can only go so far in terms of communicating qualities or values (Bullock and van der Ven 2020); and recent studies argue that closer interactions that produce trust, shared visions and mutual responsibilities among food system actors, are promising avenues for increasing the impact of labels (Nakandala et al. 2020; Hebinck et al. 2018). These topics are reflected in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Key topics of research 1975-2020 (source: Loconto and Garrido-Garza 2021)

NB: This map presents a lexicometric analysis of the relationships among the key terms that characterise the literature collected in the Scopus database of 2,397 articles from the keyword search string: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("alternative agri-food networks" OR "short food supply chain" OR "circuit court" OR "local food system" OR "quality turn" OR "certification" OR "participatory guarantee systems" OR "participatory certification" OR "farm to fork") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ARTS")). The size of the triangles indicates the frequency of the use of the term and the concentration of terms in clusters demonstrate that there are a number of subgroups of literature within the large database and that they are not all using the same terminology. The physical proximity of the clusters (particularly overlapping circles) signifies that the articles have other elements in common, such as the journal, the affiliation or the author. The top five countries that are publishing on these topics are identified for each cluster.

The two elements - consumer purchasing behaviour and the ways in which intermediary actors influence the use of transparency in the communication of values within their supply chains - are particularly important when we think about the emergence of alternative agri-food networks (AFNs). These AFNs networks saw a rebirth in the United States in the 1990s (Ostrom 2008) and in the 2000s in Southern Europe (Dubuisson-Quellier and Lamine 2004). More generally, AFNs focus on the relationship between farmers and consumers because of direct or mediated

interaction between the two subjects (Marsden et al. 2000). It is important to understand what the term short chain means. First, the term short can be understood as reducing the number of product passages between the farmers and consumers; in this sense, geographically distant chains can also be considered as short. Secondly, the term short can be understood as the physical distance between the two subjects, and hence the closeness or distance between production and consumption, irrespective of the number of intermediaries. Finally, a third sense may relate to the temporal dimension; that is, when the time between production and consumption decreases – which leads towards greater attention and consumption of fresh products. These assumptions are not necessarily exclusive and may exist in parallel within even the same initiatives. The linkage between AFNs and the quality management literature (blue cluster) is found through food products and particularly through food safety, food quality and organic standards (red cluster). However, there seems to be separate bodies of literature between those studies that focus on environmental and sustainability certification (red and dark green clusters), particularly in global value chains, and those who are focused on assessing and assuring quality in alternative and local food systems (yellow cluster).

An element of AFNs that has been studied intensively is how quality is created and defined in the relationships between production and consumption. In fact, there is a *socially constructed quality* (Watts et al. 2005), in which the concepts of trust and the embeddedness of the chains in particular places is fundamental (Goodman 2003). The *socially constructed quality* of AFNs is, in some respects, analogous to the *institutionally defined quality* (Salis 2013), which is linked to state agencies, the agri-food industry and based on the certification of products against quality standards (Arfini et al. 2016; Cavazzani et al. 2006; Loconto and Busch 2010). However, according to Goodman (2003), despite the fact that brands and certifications relate quality to places, they do not succeed as AFNs because interpersonal trust remains fundamental to movement adherence, which we have witnessed with the rapid explosion and retraction of box-schemes during the COVID-19 pandemic in France in 2020 (Chiffolleau et al. 2020).

From this point of view, AFNs typically develop certifications that are *alternative* to *institutional* ones: this is a bottom-up certification process that involves the producers and the creation of mutual trust. For example, *Participatory Guarantee Systems* operate locally and require the active participation of producers and consumers in quality assurance systems (Loconto and Hatanaka 2018). These systems are generally initiated by small farmers in collaboration with collectives of consumers precisely because it is possible to establish symmetrical and solidarity-based relationships based on knowledge and trust (Hebinck et al. 2014). Carrera (2009) claims that AFNs use a *difference bet* because the people involved are willing to accept different types of additional costs (higher prices, time dedicated to the organisation) to ensure individual and social well-being as a greater good. The complex relationship between consumers and farmers opens up space for the creation of bottom-up social innovation (Chiffolleau and Loconto 2018; Kropp et al. 2020).⁴

⁴ This whole section is reproduced with the permission of the authors from the report: Loconto, A., & Garrido-Garza, F. (2021). Formal and informal European quality assurance initiatives offering a connection between local gastronomy and small-scale farmers. Paris: LISIS for AgriKulti and Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture. Retrieved from <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-03173144>

These insights from our project preparatory review are important for the present Deliverable as they highlighted the importance of gathering more information about the types of value chains that are current valuing NUCs and of trying to understand if there are specific value chain characteristics that might be able to create more value and benefits for NUCs in the consumption sphere, which in turn might be able to better conserve (agro)biodiversity.

2.3 NUCs value chains

In order to understand what the current state of knowledge is on food chains that value NUCs, we conducted a preliminary systematic literature review published as Deliverable 1.3.⁵ D1.3 presented the broader framework of food environments and what is known about NUCs in these environments. In the search on Scopus that was completed as part of the work summarised in D1.3, we found 306 results for “food environment” AND “food system”, with a broad range of variations. Examples are (to name only a handful among the most cited): “food deserts literature” (Walker et al. 2010), the “local food environment and diet” (Caspi et al. 2012), the “built environment and obesity” (Feng et al. 2010), “measures of the consumer food store environment” (Gustafson et al. 2012), “influence of the retail food environment around schools” (Williams et al. 2014). However, as was highlighted in D1.3, we did not find much information specifically about NUCs or agrobiodiversity and their value in this consumption space.

Therefore, in the present Deliverable we decided to conduct a second review of the literature, entering the topic from a different perspective. We searched the literature focused on *agrobiodiversity* (“AB”) and *neglected and underutilised crops/species* (“NUC/NUS”), in order to see what we can find about value chains within this broader literature. A search conducted in Scopus in November 2022 yielded the following results, of which 78 articles were selected to be included in the review due to their relevance for food environments and value chains:

- “neglected and underutilised crop” (“NUC” in table below) = 74 of which 10 were selected from their abstracts
- “neglected and underutilised species” (“NUS” in table below) = 128 of which 35 were selected from their abstracts
- “neglected” AND “underutilised” AND “crop” (“N+U+C” in table below) = 283 of which 29 were selected from their abstracts
- “neglected” AND “underutilised” AND “species” (“N+U+S” in table below) = 307 of which 44 were selected from their abstracts
- “agrobiodiversity” (“AB” in table below) = 1324 of which 140 were selected based on their title and from these 41 were selected from their abstracts

Due to redundancy, the 78 articles amount to less than the sum of sub-totals from the combined searches. The selection threshold seems particularly low given the total number of articles which came up in the search (especially for “agrobiodiversity”): this is due to the fact that many results relate to agricultural production practices or genetics, which often do not relate closely enough to the concept of food environment. However, the combined number of results across both searches

⁵ Mattioni D, Loconto A, Veér Z, Králl A., & Stephens R., 2024. Deliverable 1.3 - Report on enabling food environments (existing shops, infrastructures, labels) valuing NUCs-based products. DIVINFOOD H2020 project, report, 22 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12679480>

appears more than sufficient to conduct a review, which is a first attempt at bridging these literatures. The full list of articles and their thematic coding is found in Appendix 1.

For the purpose of this review, the concept of “agrobiodiversity” (and its products) is subsumed into that of NUS/NUC (NUS and NUC are considered here as interchangeable). The review is structured around (i) Value chains, which may have been studied comprehensively or with a focus on only some parts of the chain (e.g., processing); (ii) Institutions and their programs, policies and regulations.

2.3.1 Value chains

2.3.1.1 Comprehensive value chain analyses

Market development and value chain analysis of agrobiodiverse products has been conducted for nearly two decades (Giuliani et al. 2004; Giuliani 2012). As a result, certain leveraging actions have been identified across the value chain for NUC/NUS, from the resources and production side (preservation of local knowledge, conservation of genetic resources, nutritional assessments to shed light on their nutritional qualities), to storage and processing (setting up low-cost storage facilities, establishing processing procedures tailored to the crop/specie’s characteristics, creating processing quality standards), trade and retail (highlighting intrinsic nutritional or sensory qualities, promoting extrinsic properties through marketing, teaming up with fair trade and organic initiatives) and finally to consumption (raising awareness of, and fostering attitudes to, NUC/NUS as “innovative” or “newly rediscovered” through advertisement and storytelling) (Baldermann et al. 2016). Different investigations into NUC/NUS markets and value chains have helped gain better understanding of bottlenecks hindering their use, and better ascertain on how to fix broken linkages along the value chain, enhance local businesses and improve farmers’ livelihoods (Borelli et al. 2020). They may hold certain commonalities (e.g., same country, same crop/specie, same methodology, etc.) but their results may be quite specific and thus collectively and complementarily build an evidence-base on how NUC/NUS value chains are constrained and may be strengthened. For instance, two case study articles mobilise the same methodology, Rapid Market Appraisal (RMA), to develop a comprehensive understanding of barriers and opportunities to NUC/NUS value chain development, in different crop/specie or geographic contexts. In studying Chaya (Mayan Spinach) in Guatemala, Amaya et al. (2020) conducted surveys among vendors, consumers, restaurants, processing industry actors, farmers and research/institutional actors, while Mbosso et al. (2020) used the same RMA method to study fonio and bambara value chains in West Africa. Such value chain assessments can highlight different problems (and opportunities for action). For instance, the first study emphasises the role of consumers (low awareness, skewed perceptions or stigma whereby they consider Chaya a medicinal crop, not a food crop, or as poor people’s food), and the constraints of farmers (geographically remote, producers face high transaction costs to access urban markets). The second study, rather, sheds light on difficulties in the processing part of the value chain that are due to poor access to equipment, machinery and generally poor processing facilities, or lack of training to use them; but also, specific issues such as fonio or bambara’s seasonal clashes with other important harvests (e.g., cotton). Another case study by Vandebroek et al. (2021) analysed barriers to, and designed a roadmap for, the development of a cottage industry for artisanal producers of Jamaican root drinks, emphasizing the importance of root drinks in cultural heritage.

Besides detailed case studies, there are also broader reviews articles, which are angled on a particular family or type of NUC/NUS in a particular region or country. For example, a review of research linked to Neglected and Underutilised Medicinal Crop Species (NUFMs) in South Africa, suggests that their value chains can be strengthened by developing agro-processing capacity, enhancing logistics, or setting up cooperatives. But of particular interest in this review is the emphasis put on so-called “Agribusiness Accelerators” – multi-stakeholder initiatives whose role is to co-develop and co-implement Research, Development and Innovation roadmaps in support of NUFMs, provide technical support and capacity development to farmers, and support the establishment of NUFM-using production enterprises (Mudau et al. 2022).

It has also been shown that NUC/NUS value chains can evolve very quickly when they are “pulled” by rapid demand growth in European or North American markets (e.g., if a new NUC/NUS superfood becomes “trendy” to increasingly health-conscious consumers, e.g., goji berries, while gourmet urban food scenes play the roles of catalysts and accelerators). The unravelling effects of such “boom-and-bust” cycles in long value chains can be destabilizing for local communities, as has been shown by Andreotti et al. (2022) with Andean quinoa, Indian millet and Ethiopian teff, but they also show that the nature of the boom-and-bust cycle depends on who led the initial rapid growth cycle, whether it was bottom-up, grassroots-based communities or, instead, was driven by top-down national policies (Andreotti et al. 2022). The recent COVID-19 pandemic showed that many short food chains for healthy food were boosted in the beginning of the pandemic, which may have been favorable to NUCs (Chiffolleau et al. 2020). However, the pandemic may also have had adverse effects on NUC/NUS food chains, in particular for informal food chain actors who may have suffered more than formally registered value chain actors from stringent regional/national policy responses to the pandemic (think of how pandemic-related compensation mechanisms were formalised). This was suggested by Zimmerer and De Haan (2020), who in their study mobilise an *ad hoc* “Agrobiodiversity Knowledge Framework” which links agrobiodiversity to food system governance including markets, distribution/logistics and seed systems.

2.3.1.2 Transformation: preparation, processing, packaging and marketing

Besides research looking at entire value chains, there are studies, which focus on particular segments of value chains. One such core segment identified in the literature relates to the transformation of NUC/NUS into food products, through different means, which can all add significant value. “Transformation”, here, means the stage between harvest and distribution/consumption, and therefore subsumes the different sub-stages of processing and/or preparation, storage, packaging and marketing.

For instance, value addition for NUC/NUS can be enhanced through the promotion of traditional preparation techniques, like tsukemono pickling in Japan, which can enhance the unique organoleptic qualities of heirloom varieties (Kimura 2021). Other food preparation and processing methods (e.g., mechanical processing, soaking, microbial fermentation, germination and malting, etc.) can significantly increase nutrient bioavailability – but it is not clear whether this nutritional complexity – the differentiation of nutritional quality depending on the type of preparation/processing – is emphasised enough in nutritional guidelines. In which case, more evidence-based information is needed on the characteristics of different preparation or processing methods (Mensi and Udenigwe 2021).

In order for NUS/NUC transformation (and value addition) to be successful, these stages may also need to be better embedded at the community level, to benefit from local knowledge and local

interactions between local stakeholders. This type of local embedding enabled the successful development in Kenya of a prototype for a pressure-popping machine, which was made using locally available materials and involving community-led interventions and experimentations: these in turn led to the elaboration of new processed products based on NUS/NUC, with additional value-added through packaging and marketing (Morimoto et al. 2021). The importance of adding extrinsic value through packaging/marketing is also emphasised in a case on baobab-derived food products in Malawi. Here, health claims associated to baobab, packaging quality and labelling, provided guidance for food processing companies to improve the composition of their recipes, as well as their marketing techniques (Darr et al. 2020): this shows how the extrinsic potential determined at the packaging/marketing stages influences the intrinsic qualities that are to be developed at the prior preparation/processing stages. Another case of local embedding took place in a coastal area of South Africa, with a focus on developing markets for coastal wild foods. In this case context, local communities were organised around Transformation Labs (T-Labs) involving multi-stakeholder interactions between chefs, farmers, retailers, government officers, NGO coastal actors and researchers. The T-Lab was not only propitious to knowledge co-production and agri-food innovation: it also helped surface deeply embedded issues around land, race, history and culture (Pereira et al. 2022).

2.3.1.3 Consumer awareness

At the end of supply and value chains, but key to determining how much the NUS/NUC value chain is worth, some research seeks to better understand consumers' perceptions, attitudes and willingness to pay a premium price for an NUC/NUC or NUC/NUC-derived food product. For instance, Meier and Oehen (2019) study consumers' valuations of farmers' varieties of tomatoes and their (limited) awareness of the general loss of cultivated diversity, its causes and its consequences, in France, Spain, Italy and Switzerland (for EU project DIVERSIFOOD). Pallante et al. (2016) find that urban consumers' willingness to pay a premium price for Nepalese finger millet is sufficient to support smallholder farmers in facing the high transaction costs associated with maintaining this niche crop in their production. Posadinu et al. (2021) also drew similar conclusions with regard to ancient tomato landraces. However, the interplay of awareness and willingness is complex (does raised awareness mechanically increase willingness to pay?), depending on what type of consumer is exposed to such a question, but also depending on the nature of the arguments that are presented before her/him. There is often a normative assumption within science and policy circles that consumers will necessarily pay more for NUC/NUC simply because agrobiodiversity provides functional, instrumental benefits (e.g., "ecosystem services", "natural capital"). However, Runhaar et al (2019) demonstrate that if not enough emphasis is placed on the more intrinsic (less "capitalistic") contributions of agrobiodiversity (such as beautiful landscapes), interventions to shape consumer demand for NUS/NUC will fall short. In addition, as shown by Lysak et al. (2019) on a consumer study for Hawaiian breadfruit, acceptance of novel food products may be largely determined by how similar the food product is to a food product that is already consumed in the consumer's regular diet. This highlights the importance of accounting for "appropriateness" in consumption studies, by considering the situational context, be it the cultural context (local geography/culture), or shopping setting context in which the consumer respondents were found (e.g., supermarket shoppers may have different outlooks than farmer's markets shoppers).

Furthermore, somewhat contrary to "willingness to pay" a premium price, some consumers – and possibly most consumers in certain cultural contexts – tend to associate NUC/NUC with food

consumed mainly in times of deprivation and unfairly label it “food for the poor”, or “food for the sick” (not food to be enjoyed but to be consumed only because of its healthy properties). As a result, as Borelli et al. (2020) indicate, developing consumer markets for (sometimes) stigmatised NUC/NUS may require continuous efforts in awareness-raising and education: through nutrition education (e.g., school gardens), dietary guidelines, seasonal calendars, gastronomy and food innovations, for example through events such as food fairs. The importance of events or tourism on consumers’ and food citizens’ awareness, interest and knowledge about NUC/NUS, is emphasised in some studies. For instance, municipal and agroecological food fairs (Zamar and Trillo 2022) or agri-tourism/culinary tourism (Taranto et al. 2020) and sustainable gastronomy initiatives that can help rebuild food and biocultural heritage, tradition and identity (Hunter et al 2019). In addition, specific innovative technologies can improve traceability, trust and a sense of identity across the value chain, such as DNA barcoding (Campanaro et al. 2019). Finally, the role of gourmet restaurants in finding new uses for underused foods has been illustrated by Luziatelli et al. (2020), with a renew in the use of Andean roots and tuber crops in Latin America, although there seems to be very few studies on the role of gastronomy and restaurants in supporting NUC/NUS.

2.3.1.4 Governance of value chains

The promotion of NUS/NUC may be difficult in conventional market governance arrangements. Indeed, the complex nature of the sustainable commercialisation of agrobiodiverse products requires governance rearrangements around innovation platforms that can coordinate innovations of different kinds, from technical to socio-organisational and relational (Jordan et al. 2016). Similarly, in reviewing systematically the extent to which Geographical Indications have been shown to generate environmental and biodiversity benefits, Milano and Cazella (2021), emphasise the importance of strong governance systems that guarantee participation of a wide range of local actors of productive systems. The importance of enhancing market linkages through participatory, multidisciplinary, community-centred and multi-stakeholder value chain development interventions, has been emphasised by King et al. (2021). In the same vein, Meinhold and Darr (2021), advocate Community Based Enterprise and New Product Development multi-stakeholder community pathways which foster behavioural changes in the stakeholders involved.

2.3.1.5 Alternative and local food networks

There is some research, which links the continued development of Alternative Food Networks (“AFN”) and other similar local, de-intermediated food initiatives and systems with support for NUC/NUS. For instance, a comprehensive study was conducted across Europe (for EU project CERERE) to study how “Alternative and Sustainable Food Systems” can promote cereal biodiversity (Sacchi et al. 2018). Galt et al. (2016) show that Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) initiatives thriving in California provide agrobiodiverse products as a strategy of distinction. In a study of the impact of retailing strategies on the agrobiodiversity of organic farms, Rover et al. (2020) show that direct sale and spatial proximity to large consumption centres are key to fostering agrobiodiversity. Torres-Salcido (2022) studies the ways in which Localised Agri-Food Systems (Sial) and Participatory Certifications are an expression of consumer recognition of the quality and origin of agrobiodiversity products from traditional agri-food systems in Mexico City. In addition, urban gardens can host significant agrobiodiversity (Da Cunha et al. 2020). Yet considering the extent of AFN-related literature and their explicit contributions to supporting NUC/NUS seems under-documented.

2.3.2 Institutions: programs, policies and regulation

2.3.2.1 International and continental level programs and policies

There is a wide range of literature on institutions, programs and policies set up and implemented in support of agrobiodiversity and NUC/NUS, at different institutional levels (international, national, regional). This literature helps trace the genealogy of interest in promoting NUC/NUS, at least in the policy realm. At the international policy level, fairly early on, Johns and Eyzaguirre (2006) already emphasised the importance of linking agrobiodiversity, biodiversity conservation and nutrition to relevant policy platforms such as the Millennium Development Goals, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, Convention on Biological Diversity, Global Strategy on Diet, Physical Activity and Health, Food-Based Dietary Guidelines, Right to Adequate Food and UN Human Rights and Commission's Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues. In 2011, the IFAD-NUS project started as the first UN-supported global effort on NUC/NUS and has developed a holistic, innovative framework to address value-chain issues and bridge the gap between conservation and use. This project made use of multi-stakeholder, participatory, inter-disciplinary, pro-poor, gender- and nutrition-sensitive approaches, linking stages usually separated such as cultivation, value-addition and marketing and building networking skills and marketing capacities in regions as diverse as Latin America, South Asia and North Africa (Padulosi et al. 2014).

The FAO also recognises the contributions of NUC/NUS in addressing SDG2: Zero Hunger via its Regional Initiative on Zero Hunger through the Future Smart Food (FSF) initiative to support countries in the identification of NUS with high potential to be integrated into agricultural and food systems (Li and Siddique 2020). The FSF initiative covers all stages for the creation of an enabling environment for FSF, from prioritisation to production, post-harvest and processing, marketing and consumption (Li et al. 2020). More recently, Bogliotti et al. (2021) documented the voices of international and regional Research for Development (R4D) agencies which promote NUC/NUS, such as the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), Self Help Africa (SHA), the Italian Agency for Development Cooperation (AICS), the International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM), the UN System Standing Committee on Nutrition (UNSCN) and the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. However, one of the main, early, global institutional efforts to promote NUC/NUS was the launch in 2002 of the (ongoing) Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAHS) program by the FAO. This program has since then identified and helped maintain 72 agro-silvo-pastoral systems, which stem from traditional techniques, ancestral knowledge and strong cultural and social values, and thus play a key role in preserving traditional agricultural systems, agrobiodiversity and related ecosystem services both in developed and developing countries (Agnoletti and Santoro 2022). Parallel to international agencies, Slow Food, via an approach that considers NUC/NUS through the lens of “endangered foods”, has set up grassroots-based projects such as Ark of Taste, Slow Food Presidia and Gardens in Africa, which provide local communities with technical support, networking capacities, scientific knowledge and markets (Barstow et al. 2021). Finally, the Biodiversity for Food (BFN) project led by CGIAR (Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research) between 2012-2019 developed a “mainstreaming toolkit” which analyses barriers which prevent greater use of NUS. In addition, it also informs on how to create enabling policy environments based on the provision of evidence, the influencing of policy and raising of awareness, through the mobilisation of diverse strategies such as national biodiversity strategies, school food procurement, green employment, cultural festivals and the analysis of specific business cases (Borelli et al. 2021).

2.3.2.2 National level programs and policies

Countries differ in their commitments to supporting NUC/NUS. Tools exist to compare these, such as the Agrobiodiversity Index, which helps quantify countries' commitments and actions towards agrobiodiversity for healthy diets, sustainable agriculture and genetic resource management (Juventia et al. 2020). Some research focuses on the commitments of one country, such as Torres et al. (2022) for Mexico, or on specific policies for several countries, such as public procurement policies (e.g., school meals) in Kenya, Brazil and India (Hunter et al. 2019). Certain countries, like Brazil, are also more heavily documented than others, due to their relative advancement in agrobiodiversity policy/program support. For instance, the Brazilian Socio biodiversity Native Food Species of Nutritional Value policy defines, recognises and formalises NUC/NUS as holding particularly high nutritional value, and this policy is seconded by dietary guideline policies through initiatives such as the launch of a Brazilian Regional Foods book by the Ministry of Health (Hunter et al. 2019). Brazil's National Policy for Agroecology and Organic Production (PNAPO), set up in 2012, was also one of the first to promote agroecological transition at the state level. It incorporates public procurement programs (National School Meal Program and Food Procurement Program) through which products are purchased from local smallholders for consumption in social and educational institutions. This policy reflects how "public mediated markets", with specific rules and conventions, can provide ways to ensure the sale of agrobiodiversity products, especially if the roles of intermediary cooperatives is strengthened (Resque et al. 2019). Public Food Procurement Programs (PFPP) are important in helping foster agrobiodiverse food systems due to their ability to determine for whom (e.g., schoolchildren), from whom (e.g., smallholder producers) and what type of food (e.g., NUC/NUS) is procured (Swensson and Tartanac 2020). More general analysis of policy environments has also been conducted to determine barriers and enablers to NUC/NUS development, for instance in India regarding the impact of the National Food Security Act in 2013 for the incorporation of small millets considered important for the survival or marginalised communities (Notaro et al. 2017).

2.3.2.3 Policies to encourage broader participation

Policies need to take a multi-actor perspective, which may include engaging researchers in more participatory and interdisciplinary approaches, supporting different supply chain actors in the challenging reorganisation of their activities, or properly rewarding facilitators for their role in bridging knowledge gaps (Chable et al. 2020); and participatory breeding programs (Caetano et al. 2015) or decentralised collaborative plant breeding (Camacho-Henriquez et al. 2016); or developing participatory assessments of seasonality with a view to creating seasonality calendars (Lochetti 2021). Some studies show the complex articulation between international and EU-level institutional frameworks (e.g., EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, CAP, Rural Development Policy, etc.) with the specificities of national or regional policies and institutions. This is for example the case with the Tuscany Regional legislation in Italy, which recognises territorial commons and engages public control and responsibility over the use of agrobiodiversity assets like the Valtiberina Red Onion (Scaramuzzi et al. 2021). In addition, studies by Van Amstel and Van Saane (2007) and Van Amstel et al. (2007) of international eco-labels and product-specific labels designed to provide consumers with reliable performance standards, shows generalised transparency issues, which warrant the need for the inclusion of third parties in the planning and implementation stages of self-regulation giving them supervisory, regulatory and/or enforcement powers.

2.3.2.4 Regulation

The path-dependency of agricultural and food production systems on strong intellectual property laws and regulations related to the registration, performance testing and certification of marketable seeds has been considered by some to be a political and legal impasse. This thinking questions neoliberalism and certain concepts of property and ownership and propose new notions such as “global seed commons” or “open seed licenses”. Such collective governance propositions, geared to supporting local and indigenous communities, are backed against international frameworks laid down by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol on access and benefit-sharing (Girard and Frison 2018).

Research has also shown that critical consumers (ethically- and environmentally-minded) support open-source seed licenses, for reasons such as preventing the privatisation of plant genetic resources, the support small-scale farmers and the prevention of market concentration (Kliem and Wolter 2022). There are indeed shortcomings in seed system regulations: in EU legislation, for instance, there may too much focus on agrobiodiversity conservation, as opposed to agrobiodiversity innovation by farmers, who, as a result, find themselves having to navigate a complex web of incomplete pathways into the market simpler regimes may exist for niche varieties outside the EU, for example in Switzerland (Batur et al. 2021). One problem, though, with seeing agrobiodiversity products under the angle of genetic, seed or food “commons” is that such products are also prone to market failure as impure public goods with both public and private economic attributes, due to farmers generating less (bio- and agrobio-) diversity than is desirable in contemporary and future societies (Jaeger et al. 2017).

More generally, there has been a rich innovation process in law-making applied to agrobiodiversity over the past two decades, which consider farmers’ rights, agricultural systems as part of cultural heritage and the role of protected areas in promoting agrobiodiversity (Santili et al. 2013). Timmermann et al. (2016) argue in favour of a “mixed property regime” for the ownership of genetic resources, which encompasses open access, commons, private property, state property and common heritage, and would hold different and complementary advantages in the incentivizing of variety conservation, development, sharing and waste-avoiding. However, due to differences in legal systems, traditions and consumer expectations, such systems are difficult to harmonise, and trade barriers remain. These could, however, be overcome by the provision of certification standards based on an internal control system harmonised internationally – addressing in particular the issues of traceability and the problem that if NUS/NUC are considered “endangered”, they cannot be sold through markets (Baldermann et al. 2016).

2.4 Research gaps

The present literature review shows that there remain a number of gaps in the literature about how short and mid-tier food chains are organised in their diversity, what is known about **transparency in communicating values** along different types and **lengths of chain**, and how the **social relations** are created that are effective in embedding these chains in communities that support their sustained value creation.

The role of **intermediaries** is clear in the literature, but we need more information about how they are working and particularly how they interact within value chains, in order to understand how value for NUCs is created and what **benefits** are created through the sale of NUCs.

The focus of the review of the literature specifically on NUCs opened up two entry points to better understand how value can be created: through regional, national and European level institutions that create an enabling environment for NUCs and through the value chains.

In the next section, we present our first efforts to collect data about these enabling environments, seeking to both add an extra layer of analysis to our value chain analysis and to present the current available data at the national level for the NUCs studied in DIVINFOOD.

In the sections 4 and 5, we present the empirical study that we conducted on the NUC value chains, followed by our proposed typology. We revisit some of the literature presented in this section, as the creation of the typology was an iterative approach of comparing our empirics to the current literature.

3. The “NUC environments” in DIVINFOOD partner countries

As we have found in the previous deliverable submitted in this work package (D1.3), in general, retail spaces in Europe currently do not valorise NUCs, meaning that there hardly exists an enabling food environment that make it easy - or sometimes, even possible - for consumers to choose NUCs. The initiatives and value chains discussed later in the present report are examples of the outliers as they are organisations that have managed to successfully value NUCs in some ways. To further illustrate the wider food environment within which they operate in, in this section we present some key conclusions gathered from studying the national-level statistics on the NUCs studied in the DIVINFOOD project. Our aim is to illustrate the scales in which the neglected and underused grains and legumes involved in the project are cultivated and consumed.

3.1 Data collection strategy

To compile the statistical data, DIVINFOOD partners in each country filled out a template where we aimed to gather information on all DIVINFOOD NUCs, but especially the ones cultivated within the framework of the project in each country or Living Lab region. We requested data to be collected for the following indicators: yearly production (tonnes), import (EUR), sales (tonnes and EUR) and price/tonne. We aimed to gather time series data, e.g., data for each of the last 10 years. Furthermore, the goal was to attempt to gather data on the distribution of cultivated NUCs into different sales channels and the amounts imported. Finally, we also aimed to collect data on the consumption of NUCs (e.g., per capita consumption of certain NUCs in the participating countries).

It is important to emphasise that it has proved nearly impossible to retrieve the data we aimed to collect. For most countries and most species, the most the partners could retrieve was production data or cultivation area, but more detailed data - especially on sales, imports, prices, etc. - is either unavailable or unreliable. Central Statistical Offices and other institutions rarely gather detailed data on NUCs and oftentimes the production - and especially the consumption - data is lumped together with other legumes or grains, which makes such data not very useful for the purposes of our analysis here. It is also important to note that the way in which data is gathered on NUCs in the various countries is often vastly different which makes the different datasets hard to compare. We would like to stress how important it would be in the future to gather detailed and disaggregated data on various NUCs on national, regional and EU-levels, as it could underline suggested policy changes and aid stakeholders to popularise the cultivation and consumption of NUC legumes and grains.

The data we did manage to collect is included in Appendix 2. Production data for most of the NUCs was more widely available from various Central Statistical Offices than any other data we sought to gather. This was primarily the case for Hungary’s and Italy’s legume production, but also to some extent, Hungary’s einkorn and emmer production and some NUC’s production statistics in Sweden and Switzerland. In these cases, the data was also available for the last ten years, so we

could observe some trends over time. However, other data types are scarcely available or highly unreliable - especially price and general sales data.⁶

3.2 National level statistics

Of course, as we are addressing NUCs here, the production levels are generally very low in each country we studied, compared to the main cash crops that are grown across Europe. Generally speaking, grain legumes are already quite under-utilised as legume production is marginal in Europe, covering less than 3 percent of arable land.⁷ The NUCs involved in the DIVINFOOD project are then of course even more marginalised: for example, Swiss lupin production took place on 318 total hectares in 2023, producing a total of 600 tonnes.⁸ Or, in Hungary, only 5 total tonnes of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) were produced in 2022. Furthermore, 1,041 tonnes of einkorn were produced in Hungary in 2021 (compared to 5,3 million tonnes of wheat in the same year).⁹ Without delving deeper into the data, this first glance already highlights the difficulties that any initiative might face when trying to incorporate NUC grains or legumes into their value chain. The customers who are open to seeking out these NUCs have to do so in a NUC environment that is not very much supporting of their endeavours.

Looking at the data of the last 10 years in the DIVINFOOD partner countries, no clear trends can really be established in the production of various NUCs involved in the project. In most cases, production has fluctuated a lot, resulting in overall decline or stagnation in production levels. For example, Hungarian lupine production stood at 556 tonnes a year, in 2009. After a sharp decline, then fluctuation, the total production was only 132 tonnes in 2022 (Figure 2).

⁶ For data until 2019, a deliverable by the LegValue project can also be consulted as it carried out a detailed analysis of available information. This can be found on the following link: https://www.legumehub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/LegValue_report_d31-report-on-legume-markets-in-the-eu.pdf. (Last visited: 17th of June, 2024.) Furthermore, it needs to be noted here that data on Denmark is not contained in the database we created as it was not available to the partners involved in the project.

⁷ Source: FAO. See: <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/1646579/>. (Last visited: 17th of June, 2024.)

⁸ Source: Swiss Granum

⁹ Source of Hungarian data: KSH

Figure 2. Production of lupines in Hungary (source: KSH)

In France, the data from the last 20 years shows a first sharp decline in pea (*Pisum sativum*) cultivation levels until the end of the 2000s, after which yearly production levels fluctuated around 50.000 tonnes a year (compared to almost 200 thousand tonnes a year in 2000) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Production of peas in France (source: FAOSTAT)

Faba bean production in Sweden fluctuated and remained largely unchanged between 2013 and 2022, with the share of organic production remaining largely unchanged also (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Faba Bean production in Sweden (source: statistikdatabasen)

In Italy, Faba bean (*Vicia Faba*) production also stagnated largely. However, it is produced in overall larger quantities than in e.g., Sweden or other countries (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Production of Faba beans in Italy (source: Istat)

The same fluctuation and overall unchanged production levels are true for Hungarian einkorn production (Figure 7). For emmer, only the sowing area data is reliable, where a strong decline can be observed between 2017 and 2022 - from 583 hectares to 44 hectares (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Sowing area of Emmer in Hungary (source: KSH)

Figure 7. Production of einkorn in Hungary (source: KSH)

In other cases, already low levels of production have declined further, such as in the case of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) in Hungary: whilst in 2015, 1,467 tonnes were produced, this fell to only 234 tonnes by 2022 (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Production of common beans in Hungary (source: KSH)

Another clear example of this declining trend is lupine cultivation in France: whilst in the early 2000s, the country produced over 30 thousand tonnes of lupines yearly, this dropped to the third of this level, to 11 thousand tonnes in 2022 (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Lupine production in France (source: FAOSTAT)

Fortunately, some positive trends can also be highlighted from the data we have gathered. For example, Italian chickpea production has approximately doubled between 2013 and 2023 (from approx. 12,000 tonnes to 24,000 tonnes) - whilst it has to be stressed that it was also much higher in some in-between years (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Production of chickpeas in Italy (source: Istat)

Another positive trend can be seen in France with the country’s lentil cultivation levels: even if some fluctuations could be observed, French lentil production almost tripled between 2000 and 2022 from 11 thousand tonnes a year to 29 thousand tonnes a year (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Production of lentils in France. (source: FAOSTAT, Agreste)

Swiss lupine production is also steadily increasing - of course, it is still in very low numbers, with an estimated 700 tonnes being produced in 2024 (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Production of lupines in Switzerland. (source: Swiss Granum)

Hungary also presents a few positive examples when it comes to lentil and chickpea production. According to the KSH statistical analysis, Lentil production has grown from practically non-existent levels (e.g., 2 tonnes produced in 2013) to 217 tonnes in 2022. Chickpea production has seen a similar trend, with 143 tonnes produced in 2022 - a growth from 9 tonnes in 2012. However, it needs to be noted that - as with most NUCs involved in the DIVINFOOD project - these levels are still extremely low, and other issues - such as the fact that most of this produced lentil is exported or that a lot of the chickpea is used as animal feed - hinder local consumers' access to these legumes as well.

3.3 General trends in NUCs production at the national level

Overall, whilst we highlighted the general insufficiency of the available data about various NUCs involved in the DIVINFOOD project, in this section we aimed to illustrate a few visible characteristics and trends of NUC cultivation in the partner countries of Europe. Again, NUCs are neglected- and underutilised precisely because they are cultivated - and consumed - in very low levels throughout the continent. These low cultivation levels affect the ability of consumer-citizens to access these NUCs and also shape the ways in which the various short- and mid-tier chains discussed in the rest of this paper can operate. From the limited data, we highlighted a few historic trends from the last decade, which, in most cases suggest a stagnating - or often even declining - trend in most NUCs' cultivation levels, but some positive examples were also demonstrated.

4. Survey methodology

4.1 Identification of initiatives valuing/selling NUCs

In order to identify food environments in the seven DIVINFOOD countries that are conducive to the development of NUCs/NUCs-based products, an extensive search on the internet was made during the first trimester of 2023 to gather initiatives corresponding to short and mid-tier chains that are involved in the selling or in the valorisation of cereals and legumes NUCs. Although the focus was on finding initiatives dealing with NUCs, and in particular with the NUCs of the DIVINFOOD project, we expanded the search to initiatives that sold also other cereals and/or legumes. We used these search parameters because the definition of NUCs is country-specific and much information available on the internet for some initiatives (especially the shops) are not detailed enough to assess whether or not they deal specifically with NUCs. Taking into account initiatives dealing with other cereals and/or legumes has also enabled us to increase the number of initiatives in the database.

Identification of initiatives on the internet was made following the same purposive sampling procedure (Patton 1990) as described in a previous work lead by members of DIVINFOOD Task 1.2 (see Loconto and Garrido-Garza 2021). It consisted on using keywords translated into the languages of each country on “google search” and “google advanced search”. Keywords consisted of the 16 NUCs from the DIVINFOOD list, but also to NUCs that are specific to each country, and to generic terms like “ancient/old cereals/legumes”, coupled with keywords on marketing channels (examples of search: “lupin and CSA”, “producer of old cereals and direct sales”). Communication channels (mainly websites or Facebook or Instagram accounts of the initiative that emerged) were then scanned and only those initiatives associated with one or more features of short and mid-tier supply chains were kept. The kind of initiatives identified were thus very varied, ranging from farmers (kept only if they mentioned a selling channel, which are very different in terms of size, legal and collaboration forms - isolated farmers, farmers in different forms of associations such as farmer groups or cooperatives), community supported agriculture, physical market places, processors (such as bakers, millers, brewers, specialised in the sorting/processing of cereals/legumes, of processed products made from cereals/legumes (e.g. canned food, humus...)), restaurants, agritourism promoters, associations of conservation of old varieties or genetic conservation, all kind of stores favouring short sales chains (farmers’ drives, farmers’ stores, producers’ stores, bulk stores, local products stores - the importance of legumes/cereals and the extent of their offer - sometimes also containing non-food - is variable for these types of initiative) and online platforms aiming at linking producers and consumers together (e.g., “Acheter à la source” ; “La ruche qui dit oui” ; “Farm2Fork Kft” ; “Salento Km0”). In addition to direct searches on the internet, these online platforms mapping short and mid-tier chains were also used to find and locate more efficiently other more relevant initiatives.

From the communication channels (mainly from the initiatives’ websites, but also from online platforms, Facebook, Instagram accounts or from internet posts) of the identified initiatives, a database was developed with the following fields: Name of the initiative; Country; Official website link; Facebook link; E-mail; Contact website; and if available, their public statement corresponding to their “About us” (retrieved from the page “about us”, “who we are”) and their self-description (mainly retrieved from the “first page” of their communication channel or if not detailed, consisting of reconstructed information from elements found regarding their crops,

products, main activities, missions). “About us” and “Description” fields were translated in English with the help of google translate tool.

We tried to collect data as homogeneously as possible, following the procedure explained. However, collection was shared by 5 different members of the INRAE and Agri Kulti teams (1 for Denmark and Sweden, 1 for France, 1 for Hungary, 1 for Italy, 1 for Portugal and Switzerland) which may have led to a greater risk of introducing some bias in the data.

The sampling resulted in a database of 1,268 initiatives (see table below for details on the number of initiatives collected per country, see Appendix 2 to access the database).

Country	N	%
Denmark	172	13.6
France	382	30.1
Hungary	163	12.9
Italy	186	14.7
Portugal	105	8.3
Sweden	166	13.1
Switzerland	94	7.4
Total	1,268	100.0

Table 1. Number of initiatives included in the database per country

In order to gain a better understanding of the initiatives in our database that promote agrobiodiversity, and to give us an insight on the communication messages and values they put forward, a lexical analysis was carried out using the CorText manager platform on the 846 initiatives for which we were able to retrieve a 'description' text.

The figure below represents the map of co-occurrence of the most relevant noun phrases (monogram to up to 3 words) that were extracted from the 'description' texts. 311 terms were kept and plotted in a network mapping. Extracted terms give an overview of commercial activities of the initiatives, characteristics/values they highlight and products they handle.

products (such as shops, online platforms...), while the lower part concerned those having an agricultural/production activity (such as farmers). Terms related to processing/food service are located in the central cluster of the map and seem to link “production” and “selling” clusters. The number of initiatives associated with each cluster give an indication of the proportion of each initiatives’ type in our database.

The cluster which brings together the largest number of initiatives (i.e. 211 – named ‘rotations & ground’), join both terms related to agriculture (farm, cultivation, organic agriculture, conservation agriculture...) and to processing of ‘basic’ products (flour, bread, bakery, pasta, millers...). The initiatives in this cluster focus their communication on cereals (wheat, rye, grains, corn, einkorn, ancient/old varieties, buckwheat, spelt...) and legumes (chickpeas, lentils, peas, square peas...). They communicate on biodiversity (local biodiversity, ancient varieties, new varieties¹¹...), farming techniques (soil, ground, organic agriculture, crop rotation, green manures...) and traditional processing activities (natural sourdough bread, stone millstone, wood-fired oven, traditional technique...). ‘Visit the farm’ is also an activity linked to this type of initiatives. This cluster is most strongly associated with France, Italy and Switzerland.

A second cluster is linked by the term biodiversity, ancient grains, and farm to a medium-sized cluster (named ‘agricultural company & company’ - 53 initiatives - which puts this cluster in 7th place in terms of number of initiatives relative to the other clusters of the network 7). The initiatives in this medium-size cluster emphasise their territorial anchorage and their willing of transmission (territory, generation, heritage, small village). They talk about farming techniques, but in a way that seems more generic than the previous cluster (natural resources, organic crops, land). Agricultural companies in Italy are over-represented on it.

Two other small/intermediate clusters are found in the lower part of the network. ‘Federal office for agriculture & plant genetic resources’ bring 7 initiatives together (10th cluster in the network in terms of number of initiatives), almost only in Switzerland and focusing on the conservation of local varieties, genetic resources and diversity. Many links are shared with the cluster ‘wild plants & medicinal plants’ (48 initiatives - 8th cluster of the network). The initiatives of this cluster highlight permaculture, horticulture, botanical garden, small-scale garden activities, and are focused on herbs, flowers and wild plants. They communicate on old seeds. These initiatives seem to seek a connection with the general public (public awareness, guided tours). They are mostly located in Switzerland and Portugal.

The ‘organic pulses & support local producers’ cluster is made of only 2 initiatives (last cluster of the network in terms of size). They are a producer of organic pulses without any other communication and a cooperative of organic producers of legumes and cereals in France.

In the centre of the map is the intermediate-sized cluster (86 initiatives – 5th cluster of the network in terms of size), named ‘kitchen & ingredients’. Its highlights terms transcribe processing activities or linkage to meals (kitchen, raw materials, cuisine, dishes, menu, lunch, gastronomy, flavours...). We find here initiatives such as restaurants, hotels, guesthouses or initiatives such as farm shops, market gardeners, processors (e.g., baker) with a food service activity. They

¹¹ New, in this context, means that they have not been used before. It refers to a NUC and not a modern variety of wheat.

communicate mainly on the convivial/naturality aspects (experience, natural ingredients, organic ingredients, harmony with nature, real butter...). The two Nordic countries (Sweden and Denmark) are the most represented in this cluster.

Another small cluster (6 initiatives – 11th cluster of the network in terms of size), named 'organic shop & respect for nature', is located in the middle of the network and brings together mainly organic shops with none or few other dimensions expressed in their communication. Portugal, Italy and Switzerland are the most associated to this cluster.

The cluster 'honey & cheeses' (3rd in terms of importance with 91 initiatives) bring together initiatives that deal in fact with a large number and/or specific food products that were not in our target (e.g. chocolate, tea, jams, meat, wine, etc...). This cluster meets also initiatives having delivery activities such as baskets, online shops, and farmers' stores. They communicate a little on the quality of the products (quality farm agriculture, selection of quality products) and highlight the locality, but rather at a regional or even a national level (local agriculture, regional products, national products). Sweden, Portugal and Denmark are the most associated to this cluster.

We find then the 4th cluster in terms of importance, 'circuit & transparency' (88 initiatives). This cluster is clearly positioned on the 'producer – consumer' link and working in a producer partnership manner (the most frequent terms are: producers, farmers, association, collaboration/partner producers, committed, members). We find initiatives such as CSA, platforms, producer stores. Their communication seems to be focused on the description of their operation (direct sale, distribution, circuit, contract, volunteers, points of sale...), on the very local area (terroir, local farms, proximity...), on the aspects of sustainability (rural areas, sustainable agriculture...), on solidarity (social ties, maintenance of peasant agriculture, fair remuneration and guarantee, fair price...), on quality, transparency and authenticity. These initiatives come mainly from France.

'Bulk and waste' represents the 2nd largest cluster with 151 initiatives. In here we find large initiatives that sell local products or which offer a large range of products (cleaning products, large number...) – mainly stores, including the bulk type. They communicate mainly on environmental aspects (waste, respect, eco-responsible, responsible consumption, selection of sustainable operations, carbon footprint, vegan products, seasonal products...) and by highlighting the local (local products, short circuit, development of the local economy, small local producers, farmers from the region), economic (economy, fair trade, attractive prices...) and quality (high quality, quality local products...) aspects. France and Portugal are the most associated to this cluster.

'Health food & minerals' (67 initiatives - 6th cluster of the network in terms of importance) includes initiatives - mainly shops - that are more focused on communicating the health/nutrition and naturalness aspects of products (health food, guarantee, vitamins, minerals, natural choice, organic food, biodynamic food ...). These initiatives are more linked to the Nordic countries and to Portugal.

Finally, a small cluster called 'Agricultural products & ecological transition' (14 initiatives – 9th cluster of the network) captures initiatives that are guided by a project or are mission first, or that promote their brand. Here we find large companies working collectively and communicating on their brand, and companies whose vocation is to offer labels (terms most frequently cited: bio, sector, brand, mission). Their communication is often around ecological aspects (sustainable

production, ecological transition, impact on the environment). They are more associated to Italy, Switzerland and France.

4.2 Survey instrument

A questionnaire was developed in order to gather more information about the identified initiatives, the NUCs they deal with and a selection of variables was made so to establish a value-based chain typology (i.e., notion of transparency, communication, supply/selling interactions, economic sustainability performance).

The questionnaire (see Appendix 3) consisted of a total of 45 questions and 48 optional sub-questions and was designed to be simple, quick to answer, adapted to each type of initiatives and with a target of a maximum filling time of 15 minutes. Questions were divided into five parts:

- Part 1: initiative's profile (year founded, number of locations, city location, commercial activities, description, social missions pursued)
- Part 2: products and NUCs treated by the initiative, different information about the NUCs (origin, share activity related to NUCs, etc...), organisation of the supply and selling chains
- Part 3: digital tools used, communication (communication means used, qualities promoted, etc...)
- Part 4: certification systems used, NUCs' production communication, benefits perceived from the selling/valorisation of NUCs, NUCs' price and margin
- Part 5: competition perceived around NUCs, NUCs' production, processing and selling challenges.

The online survey was developed within the European's commission platform "EU Survey", first in English, then translated into the seven DIVINFOOD countries' languages (i.e., German, French, Hungarian, Italian, Portuguese, Danish, Swedish) with the help of the automatic transcription tool offered by the EU application¹² and finalised thanks to corrections by native speakers among the DIVINFOOD partners working in WP1.

1,179 initiatives of the database (i.e., all initiatives for which contact information could be found in the public sphere) were contacted, mostly by e-mailing via the EU survey platform (a few of them, without e-mail, were contacted via their website contact form or their Facebook application). The e-mail consisted of a text explaining the objective of the DIVINFOOD project and of the questionnaire, the reason why there were being contacted (i.e., found their company's website which suggested that they are involved in selling/valorising NUCs), the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) information, the contact information of the task's leader and the link to the survey in their native language¹³.

¹² EU Survey function <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>

¹³ The online survey can be found here:
https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/DIVINFOOD_NUCsalesBenefits

The questionnaire was opened between January 31th and April 17th, 2024. In an attempt to increase the response rate, several reminders were sent to the initiatives during the data collection period.

A total of 122 initiatives answered the questionnaire (see Table 2 for details of the number of respondents per country). This corresponds to a response rate of around 10% for the population (ranging from 5% for Sweden to 15% for Hungary), in line with response rates generally obtained for this type of online survey.

Questionnaire's results file was extracted from the EU Survey platform in an Excel format and analysed using the English version for the response form. All open free text fields completed in languages other than English were translated using the "Google translate" tool and mistranslations that would have impacted the data analysis were corrected. Data were imported and processed into R software (R Core Team, 2022). Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were calculated for each question, for the sample as a whole and crossing by type of initiatives (see Section 5).

5. Survey results

5.1 Introduction

This part of the deliverable presents the descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) of each question of the online survey. The purpose of this survey was to collect original data from those initiatives who are valorising NUCs in the currently “unfavourable” food environment, in order to better understand how value for agrobiodiversity is being created. Specifically in terms of the objectives of this deliverable, we were interested in collecting data from those initiatives who are making use of both their physical and digital food environments in order to develop better chains that value the NUCs that are being studied by the DIVINFOOD project partners.

Except for the « Survey description » part, where 122 answers were collected, statistics presented are related to the 78 initiatives having declared that they deal with NUCs (Q3.3). Indeed, the objective of the questionnaire was to collect information relating to the activities linked specifically to the commercial aspects of valorising NUCs. Therefore, if initiatives answered “no” or “don’t know” to the question about whether they “dealt with NUCs”, the questionnaire was closed and no further questions were asked. Thus, for those initiatives that had been purposively selected because the research team thought that they were dealing in NUCs, and thus contacted to participate in the survey but declaring in fact they were not (44 initiatives), only profile information (part 1 of the questionnaire) and the type of food that they traded are available.

The 78 “NUCS respondents” grouped initiatives with very different profiles in terms of number and type of commercial activities. Although there may be overlaps in activities, initiatives have been classified into five types (farmers, intermediaries, processors, shops and other - see Table 3 taking into account their major role determined with the help of their declared commercial activities (Q2.7), their self-description (Q2.11) and the information about their communication channels.

The “farmer” category includes initiatives involved in an “agricultural” production activity (whatever their other declared activities are). This category accounts for the majority of the sample (n=35, 44.8% of the 78 initiatives – 15 in France, seven in Italy, six in Hungary, three in Portugal and in Switzerland, one in Sweden and none in Demark). Almost all of these initiatives are also engaged in processing activities (i.e., they are millers, bakers, processors of pasta, processed products, and/or of seasonings, or have sorting and packaging activities), thus confirming conclusions from an earlier study that the majority of farmers participating in values-based supply chains are in fact producer-intermediaries (Loconto et al., 2021). Only nine of these 35 initiatives don’t seem to present this kind of processing activities.

Moreover, most “farmers” (n=21) appear to be “individual” (i.e., no particular characteristics/links to other farmers or cooperatives highlighted in their description). Five “farmers” seem to work more in a collective manner: a farm enterprise in Italy is part of a network promoting regional food and providing third-party activities (e.g., storage centre/mill) to other small businesses in its area; a collective of militant farmers and citizens that makes claims to food/farmer autonomy in France; three initiatives present a strong part of processing activities

and work with a network of partners (two in France including one claiming to be associated with local partners; one in Italy - who also produce and sell seeds for sowing to farmers - aiming at developing a supply chain of quinoa in collaboration with partners specialised in processing). Two farmers in Switzerland work with the ProSpecieRara label (a label created by a Swiss foundation on heritage and genetic diversity); four farmers highlight their links with seed conservation associations/centres (two in Italy and one in Sweden and in France). Finally, two initiatives in Hungary and Portugal seem to be small scale vegetable farms focused on crop diversity with research/education/links with consumer as their main objective. Furthermore, two farms in Italy have the status of being a “social farm”, which is a special legal category for farms that operate as social enterprises.

The “shop” category includes the initiatives in charge of a “physical” sales outlet (n=17, 21.8% of the sample – eight in France, three in Denmark and in Portugal, two in Sweden, one in Hungary, and none in Italy or in Switzerland). Types and product ranges (i.e., food or food & non-food) vary according to these initiatives. They include bulk stores, organic stores, local products stores. Three of them seem to integrate consumers’ participation (two cooperative stores in Portugal and France, and a participatory non-profit supermarket in France); three others have a link with producers (run by a farmers' collective in France) and the final one is situated within the common area of a ‘Third place’ in France.

In the “intermediary” category are the initiatives whose main role is to act as a link between producers and consumers (n=11, 14.1% of the sample – five in France, and in Hungary, one in Italy, and none in Portugal, Denmark, Sweden or Switzerland). We find here initiatives that act as a CSA or that provide online platforms allowing consumers to find/order local products.

The “processor” category includes initiatives that process products but without any agricultural activity (n=8, 10.3% of the sample – two in Denmark Italy and Sweden, one in France and in Hungary, and none in Portugal, or Switzerland). Two in Sweden are bakers associated with a café; one in Denmark is a restaurant; one in Hungary is a miller; two in Denmark and Italy are bakers; and two in France and Italy are companies that process, sort, and package cereals/legumes.

The “other” category includes initiatives that have specialised activities such as inputs production, education, advertising or research (n=7, 8.9% of the sample – five in Switzerland, one in France and in Portugal, and none in Denmark, Sweden, Hungary or Italy). Two of these in Portugal and Switzerland are seed production companies and four are associations implicated in the conservation/diffusion of traditional seed varieties (1 in France and 2 in Switzerland). These have agroecosystem-adapted crops or are committed to the preservation, enhancement and development of the natural (animal and plant genetic diversity) and cultural heritage. The last one in Switzerland defines itself as an independent knowledge hub committed to sustainable solutions for the agri-food industry.

Finally, when we talk about “short chains” in this result part, we are referring to initiatives that have declared having at most 1 intermediary between them and the producer for their supply chain or at most 1 intermediary between them and the consumer for their selling chain; about “medium chain” if they have declared 2 to 4 intermediaries and about “long chain” if they have declared more than 5 intermediaries.

In the following section we will present the descriptive statistics of the sampled initiatives (those 78 who responded ‘yes’ to dealing with NUCs). We have organised our reading of the data mostly according to the actor type as this reading offers a better overview of the results. Most of the questions required multiple choice responses. In that case, results’ tables (such as Table 7) therefore present the number of times each option was selected out of the whole sample, independent of the different combinations of multiple responses. The numbers thus contain the multiple responses chosen by the initiatives. In the text, we also mention the patterns of responses (i.e., the combinations of options constituting the answers) that are most frequently found within the sample. To disambiguate the way the results were observed, we used the term “the most cited combination of answers were” in the text, even if the most frequent response turns out to be the selection of a single modality only and not the combination of several modalities.

5.2 Database description

In this section, we provide a very short description of the database that we constructed from the application of the method described above.

Q2.3: Initiatives’ main location

Country	N	%
Denmark	15	12.3
France	39	32.0
Hungary	22	18.0
Italy	16	13.1
Portugal	9	7.4
Sweden	8	6.6
Switzerland	13	10.7
Total	122	100.0

Table 2. Number of initiatives responding to the questionnaire per country

The number of total responses collected per country is in line with the number of initiatives listed in the database (i.e., average response rate of 10%, ranges from 5% in Sweden to 15% in Hungary), with France dominating the sample. We explain the higher numbers received from France according to two factors: 1) the French database was the most complete with 370 initiatives, whereas the second highest number of initiatives was Denmark with 164; 2) the survey was launched by INRAE, a French public research organisation that is well known and highly trusted in the French agri-food sector. Please see the methods section for more information about the survey method used.

Q3.3: Among the foods covered by your initiative, do you consider any to be neglected or underutilised crops (NUCs, e.g., legumes or cereals from old, local or indigenous varieties)? NUCs are “domesticated plant species that have been cultivated or consumed as food throughout human history, but have been reduced in importance over time...with many of them actually disappearing” (da Silva, FAO, 2012)

Dealing with NUCS	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Process or N	Shop N	All N	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Process or %	Shop %	All %
Yes	35	11	7	8	17	78	66.0	57.9	70	53.3	68	63.9
No	8	2	2	4	4	20	15.1	10.5	20	26.7	16	16.4
I don't know	10	6	1	3	4	24	18.9	31.6	10	20.0	16	19.7
Total	53	19	10	15	25	122						

Table 3. Number of initiatives having declared dealing with NUCs by type of initiative

Despite the fact that we carried out a targeted search and contacted those initiatives that the researchers had identified as being involved in the sale or in the valorisation of NUCs, 44 initiatives – representing all 5 types of actors and of all 7 countries - declared that they did not know or did not deal with NUCs (36.1% of the total respondents of the questionnaire). Several explanations are possible for this result. First, even among the researchers, it is difficult to determine precisely the type of products treated by the initiative. For example, our reading of the information found on their websites may have misinterpreted the actual activities of the company. For example, 11 initiatives claimed that they did not deal with cereals/legumes. Second, the proposed definition of NUCs in this question may have been interpreted more or less severely depending on the initiative (particularly for the term "actually disappearing"). Finally, at least a few initiatives (online platforms and shops) said in the questionnaire comments that they don't really know the products that they sold on their platforms or that they didn't have the necessary information to add knowledge on the NUCs topic and selected the "no" or "don't know" responses rather than filling in the questionnaire.

The analysis of the **free text questions (Q3.6/3.7 - Please specify the varieties of cereals/legumes that you consider as NUCS)** and **Q3.13 (Why do you think these are NUCs?)** also seem to show an initiative-dependent interpretation of the notion of NUCs. Appendix 4 summarises the NUCs from cereals and legumes that were cited by the initiatives. These tables show that the level of details given varied according to initiatives. Thus, for example, some initiatives quoted very specific varieties of lentils (e.g. "gotlandslins") while other initiatives stuck to generic terms such as simply "lentils". Other initiatives considered the term NUCs in a very broad sense (for example, in Italy they have declared "lentils" as NUCs, which is not really the case as this is a very common pulse in many regions of the country), while others, whom we know to be involved with lentils from their websites, had only cited very specific varieties as NUCs (e.g. "Azuki bean") without mentioning lentils. In addition, some respondents had declared NUCs to be a small part of their actual production (e.g., a farmer described himself as a producer of ancient cereals (spelt, einkorn, evolutionary mixtures of ancient grains, millet, buckwheat) in rotation with legumes (chickpeas, peas, soy) but only responded "einkorn, spelt" as NUCs in questions Q3.6/3.7 - without evoking any legumes).

Appendix 5 summarises the justifications of NUCs identity that was provided by the initiatives. The reasons provided cover a range of very different themes (which are found across all initiatives' types/countries). Among the main themes we found:

1. NUCs are unknown (little-known products by consumers, rarely present or absent from traditional commercial channels, few grown, not care by the industry...) (cited by n=42 initiatives, 53.8%);

2. There are particular seeds/varieties (local ecotypes, peasant seeds, not referenced in the official catalogue, ancient, abandoned, authentic, lack seeds...) (n=29, 37,2%);
3. There are difficulties to grow them (little value, not profitable, low productivity, little volumes...) (n=23, 29.5%);
4. They provide agro-ecological benefits (organic/agro-ecology production, not needing external inputs, great potential as sustainable, preserve biodiversity...) (n=13, 16.7%);
5. They provide nutritional benefits (better digestibility, low gluten strength, great interest both from a nutritional point of view, healthy, rich in protein, with a broad spectrum of essential amino acids...) (n=13, 16.7%);
6. They are difficult to process (need for dehulling after harvesting for its use, need great baking skills...) (n=6, 7.7%).

5.3 Descriptive analysis of the NUCs initiatives

In this section, we present the results of our questionnaire and first level analysis regarding the way in which the organisation of the food chains is valuing NUCs and the agrobiodiversity that they represent.

5.3.1 Profiles of the initiatives

In this first section, we describe a number of general characteristics of the entries found in our database in order to identify actor types, the diversity of commercial activities and the role of NUCs within a broader entrepreneurial strategy. The literature on alternative agri-food movements and on fair trade explain that the types of companies who engage in values-based food chains often have social missions. We explore this aspect also in this section.

Q2.3: Main location of initiatives dealing with NUCs

Country	n	%
Denmark	5	6.4
France	30	38.5
Hungary	13	16.7
Italy	10	12.8
Portugal	7	9.0
Sweden	5	6.4
Switzerland	8	10.3
Total	78	100.0

Table 4. Number of NUCs initiatives by country

Initiatives responding negatively to the question about whether they deal with NUCs are found in all seven countries and across all actor types. Thus, the “NUCs’ initiatives” sample reflects a similar distribution to that of all respondents with more than a third of respondents located in France. Denmark, Portugal and Sweden are the least represented, amounting to less than 10% of the initiatives (see Tables 2, 3 and 4).

Q2.2: Year funded

Year	n	%
=< 2000	14	17.9
2001 - 2010	13	16.7
2011 - 2020	45	57.7
>= 2021	6	7.7
Total	78	100.0

Table 5. Number of initiatives by funded year

The sample is mostly made up of recent initiatives, with 51 (65.4%) founded in or after 2011. “Intermediaries” are all founded after 2011 while all of the “other” initiatives were founded before 2011 (except one seed company founded in 2015). Among the 14 oldest initiatives, there are seven farmers (1875 to 2000), two processors (1819 and 1989), four others (1958 to 1999) and one shop (1989).

Q2.6: How many other locations do you have?

Number of locations	n	%
0	48	61.5
1	16	20.5
2	7	9.0
3-5	6	7.7
>10	1	1.3
Total	78	100.0

Table 6. Number of locations per initiative

The sample is mostly made up of initiatives with a single location (n=48, 61.5%). The initiative which has declared more than 10 locations is an “intermediary”. It is an online platform aiming to provide open-source digital services to short food chains in France. The “Shops” all declared zero other locations, except a shop in France, which works closely with a farmer (defining itself as a “family business”). These results suggest that the shops involved in the value chains valuing NUCs are all rooted in the communities that they serve.

Q2.7: How would you describe your commercial activities?

Activities	All n	All %
Food production	38	48.7
Selling food/retail	37	47.4
Processing	19	24.4
Education	11	14.1
Other	11	14.1
Agro-tourism	6	7.7
Transporting or delivery service	6	7.7

Activities	All n	All %
Advertising/marketing/promotion/valorisation	6	7.7
Research	6	7.7
Inputs production	5	6.4
Food storage/warehouse	5	6.4
Wholesaling	4	5.1
Food service	4	5.1
Blogging	1	1.3

Table 7. Number of initiatives that selected each activity

NB: number of activities selected by initiatives not limited

Q2.7: Number of commercial activities selected by type of initiative

# activities	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
1	9	7	4	5	15	40	25.7	63.6	57.1	62.5	88.2	51.3
2	9	2	2	1	1	15	25.7	18.2	28.6	12.5	5.9	19.2
3	10	0	0	1	1	12	28.6	0.0	0.0	12.5	5.9	15.4
4	2	2	0	0	0	4	5.7	18.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.1
5	3	0	1	1	0	5	8.6	0.0	14.3	12.5	0.0	6.4
6	2	0	0	0	0	2	5.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.6
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 8. Number of activities selected by type of initiative

This question clarified the profiles of the different types of actors that responded to the questionnaire (see the introduction to this section). Even if the majority of the sample declared only one commercial activity (n=40, 51.3%), percentages of each commercial activities and the high number of combinations of commercial activities cited across the sample reflects the diversity of profiles in short and mid-tier food chains valuing agrobiodiversity. Food production and selling food/retail are the most cited activities (respectively n=38, 48.7% and n=37, 47.4%) in line with the sampling strategy.

Farmers' category seems to have a slightly more widely distributed profile than the other categories (see Table 8). This result confirms the producer-intermediary role of the majority of the farmers in our database.

Q2.12: Does your initiative have a social mission?

Social missions	N	%
Yes	48	61.5
No	20	25.6
I don't know	10	12.8
Total	78	100.0

Table 9. Number of initiatives declaring having a social mission

Q2.13: What are these missions intended to fight?

Social missions	All n	All %	Declared social mission %
Unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices	39	50.0	81.2
Biodiversity decline	38	48.7	79.2
Unfair remuneration of producers	34	43.6	70.8
Environmental degradation	31	39.7	64.6
Climate change	26	33.3	54.2
Unfair global trade	22	28.2	45.8
Food insecurity	18	23.1	37.5
Gluten intolerance	18	23.1	37.5
Malnutrition	18	23.1	37.5
Overconsumption of meat	17	21.8	35.4
Obesity	7	9.0	14.6
Food fraud	5	6.4	10.4
Undernutrition	4	5.1	8.3
Other	3	3.8	6.2
No social mission or don't know	30	38.5	

Table 10. Number of initiatives that selected social missions

NB: number of social missions selected by initiatives not limited

Q2.13: Number of social missions selected by type of initiative

# of social missions	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	19	2	2	5	2	30	54.3	18.2	28.6	62.5	11.8	38.5
1	1	0	0	0	2	3	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	3.8
2	0	1	2	1	1	5	0.0	9.1	28.6	12.5	5.9	6.4
3	1	1	0	1	0	3	2.9	9.1	0.0	12.5	0.0	3.8
4	2	3	2	0	0	7	5.7	27.3	28.6	0.0	0.0	9.0
5	3	0	1	0	2	6	8.6	0.0	14.3	0.0	11.8	7.7
6	3	2	0	0	0	5	8.6	18.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4
7	1	0	0	0	2	3	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	3.8
8	3	1	0	1	3	8	8.6	9.1	0.0	12.5	17.6	10.3
9	1	0	0	0	1	2	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	2.6
10	0	0	0	0	2	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	2.6
11	1	0	0	0	1	2	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	2.6
12	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.0	9.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
13	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	1.3

# of social missions	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 11. Number of social missions selected by type of initiative

Thirty-eight percent (38.5%) of the whole sample (n=30) declared not being guided or not knowing whether their initiatives were guided by a social mission. The number of social missions selected by the initiatives varies across the sample, with 18 of them having one to four missions (37.5% of the initiatives declaring social missions); 22 (45.8%) having five to eight social missions and eight (16.7%) having nine to 13 social missions. Farmers' and processors' categories seem to present the highest proportion of initiatives without social mission.

“Unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices” and “Biodiversity decline” are the most cited social missions (respectively, n=39, 81.2% and n=38, 79.2% of those declaring social missions) followed by “unfair remuneration of producers” and “environmental degradation” (n=34, 70.8% and n=31, 64.6%).

A general tendency to combine social missions is found across the sample. The most cited combination is found only three times and concerned the four above-mentioned missions. However, almost all the initiatives claim to be concerned with production conditions (i.e. selection of “unsustainable practices”, “biodiversity decline” and/or “unfair remuneration of producers”). Only three initiatives did not select at least one of these three missions: they are a social farm (in Italy, claiming that their “social farm” is their mission), a shop (in Denmark, claiming another mission of “ignorance of the best nutrition”) and a producer (in Hungary, a miller claiming “Malnutrition + Gluten intolerance” missions).

This clearly positions these initiatives that have a social mission as being concerned for the environment, but more specifically being concerned about the current models of agriculture that are unfair to both the agroecosystems and the farmers. The importance of ancient cereals and legumes for health purposes, either for a vegetarian diet or for nutrition or gluten concerns, does not seem to be major drivers for those initiatives included in this study (n=28, 58.3% had selected at least one of the five entries related to nutrition).

5.3.2 Plant-based foods and NUCs

This part of the questionnaire was created in order to collect data about what NUCs are being valued in current food chains. The literature suggests that the number of intermediaries, the origin of the products, the types of contracts and the types of consumers are useful indicators of value that can be created for products through the market. We therefore developed questions that would enable us to measure this value for the ancient cereals and legumes that are the focus of this study.

In the previous deliverable 1.3, we reviewed the literature on the retail food environment for NUCs and we explained the consumer food environment and the 4Ps (product, placement, promotion and price). The questions that we included now on this section of our questionnaire were designed to enable us to collect data on these four aspects of the consumer food environment and better understand how different types of values-based chains are enabling the creation of benefits from NUCs in current consumer food environments.

Q3.1: What food does your initiative deal with? (i.e. that you produce, process, sell, promote/value and/or certify, depending on your initiative's activities)

Type of food treated	All n	All %
Cereals/cereal-based products	69	88.5
Legumes/legume-based products	61	78.2
Vegetables/vegetables-based products	47	60.3
Seeds/seed-based products	44	56.4
Fruits/fruit-based products	36	46.2
Nuts/nut-based products	29	37.2
Other	12	15.4

Table 12. Type of food categories treated by the initiatives

NB: number of food categories selected by initiatives not limited

Q3.1: Number of food categories treated by type of initiative

# of food categories	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
1	5	1	3	1	0	10	14.3	9.1	42.9	12.5	0.0	12.8
2	11	0	1	1	0	13	31.4	0.0	14.3	12.5	0.0	16.7
3	11	0	1	2	2	16	31.4	0.0	14.3	25.0	11.8	20.5
4	4	0	1	2	1	8	11.4	0.0	14.3	25.0	5.9	10.3
5	3	0	0	2	4	9	8.6	0.0	0.0	25.0	23.5	11.5
6	1	6	1	0	9	17	2.9	54.5	14.3	0.0	52.9	21.8
7	0	4	0	0	1	5	0.0	36.4	0.0	0.0	5.9	6.4
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 13. Number of food categories selected by type of initiative

These results are in line with sampling strategy: only three initiatives claimed to be not concerned by cereals or by legumes (one is a vegetable farmer in Switzerland, one is a seed producer in Switzerland, and the last one is a CSA in Hungary, which nevertheless selected “legumes” for the type of NUC that it dealt with).

We found that farmers tend to still be rather specialised in their production, declaring the least number of food categories compared to the other actor types (n=27, 77.1% of this category deals with less than three food types). Intermediaries all declared six or seven food categories (except the CSA in Hungary which have selected only “vegetables”), processors declared between one and five food categories, whereas the majority of shops selected five or more food categories (n=14, 82.3% deals with five to seven categories).

The majority of cited combinations of food categories were: all categories except “other” (n=14, 17.9%); legumes + cereals (n=8, 10.3%); cereals alone (n=7, 9%); legumes + cereals + seeds (n=7, 9%); all seven categories (n=5, 6.4%).

Q3.3: What NUCs does your initiative deal with? (i.e. that you produce, process, sell, promote/value and/or certify, depending on your initiative's activities)

Type of NUCS treated	All n	All %
Cereals/Cereal-based products	67	85.9
Legumes/Legume-based products	38	48.7
Vegetables/vegetable-based products	28	35.9
Fruits/fruit-based products	15	19.2
Seeds/seed-based products	11	14.1
Nuts/nut-based products	6	7.7
Other	3	3.8

Table 14. Type of NUCs categories treated by the initiatives

NB: number of NUCs categories selected by initiatives not limited

Initiatives NUCS specialisation	All n	All %
NUCS cereals	39	50.0
NUCS legumes cereals	28	35.9
NUCS legumes	10	12.8
NUCS other	1	1.3

Table 15. NUCs' specialisation of the initiatives

NB: "NUCS legumes" category groups the initiatives dealing with legumes only or with legumes and other categories - excluding cereals. "NUCS other" groups initiatives that deal with neither legumes nor cereals

Q3.3: Number of NUCs categories treated by type of initiative

# of NUCS categories	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
1	18	3	3	2	4	30	51.4	27.3	42.9	25.0	23.5	38.5
2	11	2	2	5	7	27	31.4	18.2	28.6	62.5	41.2	34.6
3	3	1	1	1	3	9	8.6	9.1	14.3	12.5	17.6	11.5
4	2	3	0	0	2	7	5.7	27.3	0.0	0.0	11.8	9.0
5	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.0	9.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
6	1	1	1	0	1	4	2.9	9.1	14.3	0.0	5.9	5.1
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 16. Number of NUCs categories selected by type of initiative

Our results are in line with the sampling strategy. Only one initiative - the vegetable farmer in Switzerland – is not concerned by NUCs from cereals or from legumes. Initiatives focusing solely on cereals are the most numerous (n=39, 50%), followed by those mixing cereals and legumes (n=28, 35.9%), whereas initiatives dealing with only with legumes are less frequent (n=10, 12.8%) (see Table 15).

The majority of the initiatives deal with only one (n=30, 38.5%) or two (n=27, 34.6%) NUCs categories. The five initiatives declaring five or six NUCs categories have also declared a high number of food categories, they are: an association in Switzerland implicated in animal and plant heritage/genetic diversity; a farmer in Switzerland working with the ProSpecieRara label; a shop in France (in a third place – given many generic NUCs); an online platform in France (aiming to provide open source digital services to short food chains) and a CSA in France (given many generic NUCs).

In general, the initiatives tend to declare fewer NUCs categories than food categories: 25.6% gave as many food categories as NUCs categories (n=20); 21.8% gave one more food category than NUCs categories (n=17); 21.8% declared two more food categories than NUCs categories (n=17); 15.4% declared three more food categories than NUCs categories (n=12) and 10 (12.8%) declared between four and six more food categories than NUCs categories (i.e., they declared six to seven food categories and only one NUCs). In this final group, we find: two intermediaries in Hungary, two intermediaries in France and six shops (one in Hungary and in Sweden and, two in France and in Portugal). (two initiatives selected more NUCs categories).

The most cited combinations of NUCs categories are: cereals alone (n=25, 32.1%); legumes + cereals (n=12, 15.4%); cereals + vegetables (n=8, 10.3%); legumes alone (n=5, 6.4%); legumes + cereals + vegetables + fruits (n=5, 6.4%).

Appendix 4 summarises the NUCs varieties from cereals and from legumes quoted by the initiatives. For cereals (n=67 initiatives concerned), the NUCs cited correspond mainly to the category of wheat (n=84 citations), followed by einkorn (n=17 citations), and spelt (n=16 citations). Maize, rye, buckwheat, barley, fonio and teff were rarely declared (less than five citations). For legumes (n=38 initiatives concerned), the declared NUCs included lentils (n=20), peas (n=16), common beans (n=16), and chickpeas (n=12). Faba beans and lupines were rarely cited (four citations).

Q3.14: What percentage of your activity is related to NUCs?

NUCS share activity	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
<5%	3	7	1	3	6	20	8.6	63.6	14.3	37.5	35.3	25.6
5 - 25%	12	1	2	2	9	26	34.3	9.1	28.6	25.0	52.9	33.3
26 - 50%	6	1	1	0	1	9	17.1	9.1	14.3	0.0	5.9	11.5
51 - 75%	3	0	0	1	0	4	8.6	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	5.1
76 - 95%	6	2	0	0	0	8	17.1	18.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.3
>95%	5	0	3	2	1	11	14.3	0.0	42.9	25.0	5.9	14.1
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 17. Share of activity dedicated to NUCs by type of initiative

NUCs represent a small part of the main commercial activity for the majority of respondents. We found that it was less than 5% for 25.6% of them (n=20) and between 5 and 25% for 33.3%

(n=26). The share of activity linked to NUCs seems to be more evenly distributed for farmer compared to the intermediary, processor and shop categories. In these latter three, NUCs generally compose less than 25% of their commercial activities (respectively 72.7%, 62.5%, and 88.2% of the category vs. 42.9% for the farmers). Indeed, we see again here the tendency of farmers to be specialised.

The respondents declaring more than 95% of their activity linked to NUCS were: five farmers (all in France, two with strong processing activities related to cereals/legumes and working with collaboration with partners – they adopted a broad definition of NUCs; and three farmers-processors, specialised in ancient wheat varieties); three other types of initiatives (all associations focused on preserving varieties/ natural and cultural heritage – one in France and two in Switzerland); two processors (a baker focused on ancient cereals in Italy, and a bread factory with 100% spelt bread in Denmark); and a shop (in a third place where the NUCs definition is very broad and include all categories).

NUCs made up 76 to 95% of the commercial activity for six farmers and two intermediaries in our sample. The two intermediaries are a CSA in France dealing with a broad definition of NUCs across all categories, and a online platform in Italy. This online platform claims the protection and enhancement of the environmental and cultural heritage and works with NUCs in all food categories. The six farmers include: one in Switzerland working with the ProSpecieRara label; one small scale vegetable farm focused on crop diversity in Hungary; two individual farmers in France mainly focused on production of einkorn or wheat populations varieties; and two farmers working in a collective manner and rather specialised in cereals and legumes (one in France in association with citizen collective and one in Italy).

Even if the terms “old, ancient, cereals, legumes, varieties” seem to be less present in the descriptions of the initiatives that have declared less than 25% of their activity linked to NUCs, the distribution of our results are probably also partly related to the interpretation of the NUCs’ definition by respondents. We can only infer the extent to which these interpretations were broadly inclusive or narrowly exclusive in their interpretation. For example, a farmer declared less than 25% of their activity related to NUCS. Yet in the description they said that they produced modern and ancient wheat, small spelt, legumes including lentils, split peas, chickpeas and instead only declared two ancient varieties of wheat as NUCs. Some similar initiatives also reported a surprising range of percentages for their NUCs activities.

Q3.15: What is the origin of the NUCs that your initiative deals with?

NUCS origin	All n	All %	Declared origin %
Same region	42	53.8	56.8
Same country	36	46.2	48.6
Same municipality	21	26.9	28.4
Same continent	14	17.9	18.9
Outside Europe	7	9.0	9.5
Not concerned by sourcing, origin issues	3	3.8	

NUCS origin	All n	All %	Declared origin %
Don't know	1	1.3	

Table 18. Origin of NUCs treated by the initiatives

NB: number of NUCs origin selected by initiatives not limited

Q3.15: Number of NUCs origin selected by type of initiative

Number of NUCS origin	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	2	0	0	1	1	4	5.7	0.0	0.0	12.5	5.9	5.1
1	20	8	4	2	7	41	57.1	72.7	57.1	25.0	41.2	52.6
2	9	3	3	3	6	24	25.7	27.3	42.9	37.5	35.3	30.8
3	3	0	0	2	1	6	8.6	0.0	0.0	25.0	5.9	7.7
4	1	0	0	0	1	2	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	2.6
5	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	1.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 19. Number of NUCs origin selected by the initiatives

Only three initiatives declared not to be sourcing NUCs. These are two farmers who probably interpreted the question as referring to purchasing NUCs outside of their farm, and one processor with a large part of its commercial activity related to seed quality and producing their own raw materials in Italy. One cooperative store in France claimed that they did not know the origin of their products.

Most initiatives declare one (n=41, 55.4% of the initiatives declaring an origin) or two origins (n=24, 32.4%) for their NUCs. Three initiatives declared four or five different origins: one shop in a third place in France, a participatory non-profit supermarket in France and a farmer in Switzerland working with the ProSpeciRara label (they declared between three and six NUCs categories).

The most frequent combinations of origin are from the: same region selected alone (n=19, 25.6%); same country selected alone (n=13, 17.6%); same region and same country (n=9, 12.2%); same municipality selected alone (n=5, 6.8%).

The “same region” and “same country” are the most frequently origins selected (by about half of the initiatives, respectively n=42, 56.8% and n=36, 48.6%).

Of the five initiatives that source exclusively from the same municipality, they are all individual farmers (two in Hungary and in France and a small agroforestry production of vegetables for household consumption in Portugal) and thus are selling their own production through direct sales or through their own consumption.

Among the most “distant” origins, outside Europe was only mentioned once by a diversified organic shop in Portugal declaring “Khorasan wheat” as a NUC (but which nevertheless said to

give priority to national/local products in its description). The same continent origin was cited alone three times (by a seed company in Switzerland, an association of seeds conservation in France, and an individual farmer in France who declared “old maize, old wheat, camellia and hemp” as their NUCs). Outside Europe was also selected in combination with other origins by six additional initiatives: a farmer in Italy (who is developing a quinoa supply chain, implicated in a research project and is trying to procure new lupine seeds from south America; an association in Switzerland that is working on *in situ* adaptation of crops; two processors (one in France sorting and packaging dried vegetables and cereals; and an organic bread factory in Denmark citing some specific NUCs), two shops (a participatory non-profit supermarket in France, and an organic shop in Portugal – this last one declaring some specific NUCs). Among these six initiatives, three listed very specific NUCs that have their origins in Africa and Latin America (i.e. chia, teff, fonio, cassava) which can explain this selected extra-EU origin.

These results suggest that the value chains are territorially anchored – but not at the municipality level and more at the level of the European regions or even nationally. This suggests that the majority of our initiatives are sourcing their NUCs through short and mid-tier chains that rely upon regional and national chains.

Q3.16 and Q3.19: Do the NUCs that your initiative deals with come directly from producers? If indirectly, how many intermediaries (excluding the producer and your initiative) are involved for the supply of NUCs?

NUCS Supply chain	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Own producer	10	0	3	0	0	13	28.6	0.0	42.9	0.0	0.0	16.7
Own producer + Direct	5	0	0	0	0	5	14.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4
Own producer + Direct + Short supply chain (1 int.)	2	0	0	0	0	2	5.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.6
Direct supply chain	9	7	0	2	7	25	25.7	63.6	0.0	25.0	41.2	32.1
Direct + Short supply chain (1 int.)	4	2	2	2	3	13	11.4	18.2	28.6	25.0	17.6	16.7
Direct + Short and Medium supply chain (1-2 int.)	0	0	0	1	1	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	5.9	2.6
Direct + Indirect - don't know the numbers of int.	0	1	1	0	2	4	0.0	9.1	14.3	0.0	11.8	5.1
Direct + Medium supply chain (1-2 int.)	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	1.3

NUCS Supply chain	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Direct + Medium supply chain (3 int.)	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	1.3
Short supply chain (1 int.)	0	0	0	0	2	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	2.6
Short and Medium supply chain (1-2 int.)	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.0	9.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Medium supply chain - don't know the number of int. (3 int.)	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	1.3
Medium supply chain (4 int.)	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Long supply chain (5 int.)	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Indirect - don't know the number of int.	1	0	0	0	1	2	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	2.6
Don't know the type of supply chain	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.0	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0	1.3
Not concerned with NUCs sourcing/origin issues	2	0	0	1	0	3	5.7	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	3.8
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 20. Type of NUCs supply chains

A little more than half of the initiatives included in our study are associated with a 100% direct supply chain (n=43, 55.1% corresponds to “own producer” or “own producer + direct” or “direct supply” chains) followed by a hybrid direct + short and/or mid-tier supply chain (n=19, 24.4% - with only four initiatives having a mid-tier chain with only up to three intermediaries: they are three processors (a baker/café in Sweden, a bread factory and a restaurant in Denmark) and a store in France).

Four (4, 5.1%) initiatives have a hybrid direct and indirect supply chain, without knowing the number of intermediaries: they are one “other” (independent knowledge hub in Switzerland), an online platform (aimed at providing open-source digital services to short supply chains in France), and two shops (participatory non-profit supermarket and a bulk store in France).

Only five initiatives (6.4%) don't source directly: they are two stores with an intermediary (in Sweden and Denmark), a CSA with one to two intermediaries (in Hungary) and two farmers with four to five intermediaries (an individual in Switzerland and a small agroforestry production in

Portugal). Only three initiatives have an indirect supply chain without knowing the number of intermediaries (two diversified (food and non-food) shops in Portugal and a farmer claiming to have a great diversity of both plant and animal production activities in France. One other initiative (association for the development of site-adapted crops) in Switzerland do not know its type of supply.

Finally, three initiatives do not source NUCs. These are two farmers and the one processor with activities in seed quality and producing its own raw materials already were mentioned above.

These results further confirm the composition of our database as mostly short value chains that are territorially anchored but there are small percentage of mid-tier chains, that are sourcing to processors and food service providers, who generally have just one location.

Q3.18: If directly, what type of contracts are established with producers for the supply of NUCs?

Type of supply contract	All n	All %	Having direct supply %
Own producer	20	25.6	33.3
1 time sale	18	23.1	30.0
Annual contract	13	16.7	21.7
Long-term contract	10	12.8	16.7
Auction	0	0.0	0.0
Other	13	16.7	21.7
Indirect supply	9	11.5	
Not concerned by sourcing, origin issues	3	3.8	
Don't know the type of contract (direct supply)	5	6.4	
Don't know the type of supply (direct or indirect)	1	1.3	

Table 21. Type of NUCs supply contract (for direct supply)

NB: number of contracts selected by initiatives not limited

When asked about the types of contracts that are used, those initiatives that source directly for at least a part of their products (n=66), mostly rely on a single type of contract for their sourcing (n=42, 63.6% vs. n=6, 9.1% declaring two types of contracts and n=13, 19.7% being their own producer and n=5, 7.6% not knowing the type of contract).

That is, however, the largest consistency found in terms of the contracts as the specific type of contract found across the sector is quite variable and is not specific to short or mid-tier value chains. Instead, they vary between 1-time sales and annual contracts, which are slightly more used than long-term contracts.

These results suggest that the market demand (and also, perhaps the supply) is not consistent enough to enable the actors in the value chain to make longer term commitments that go beyond

one year. The high number of “other” and “don’t know” responses suggest that indeed the NUCs related activities are not significant enough in terms of sales to warrant entering into long term agreements among supply chain actors. Instead, one’s own production is often sufficient and purchasing on demand is feasible based on non-contractual relationships between the retailers and the producers. Additionally, this is also a sector that is characterised by experimentation and seed exchanges, which means that the social engagement goes beyond pure market exchanges. This may be an additional reason why actors claim not to use so many binding contracts.

Q3.20: and Q3.23: Does your initiative sell NUCs/NUC-based products directly to consumers? How many intermediaries are there between your initiative and the consumer?

NUCS Selling chain	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Direct sales	17	8	1	4	14	44	48.6	72.7	14.3	50.0	82.4	56.4
Direct + Short sales circuit (1 int.)	13	1	0	3	3	20	37.1	9.1	0.0	37.5	17.6	25.6
Direct + Medium sales circuit (2 int.)	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Direct + Short and Medium sales circuit (1-3 int.)	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Direct + Don't know	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Short sales circuit (1 int.)	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Short and Medium sales circuit (1-3 int.)	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.0	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0	1.3
Don't know	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Not concerned by food sale	0	2	5	1	0	8	0.0	18.2	71.4	12.5	0.0	10.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 22. Type of NUCs selling chains

The sample is made up almost exclusively of initiatives with 100% direct sales to consumers (n=44, 56.4%) or with a hybrid direct + short and/or mid-tier chains (n=22, 28.2%). Only two initiatives have up to two intermediaries between themselves and the food consumers. They are both farmers with processing activities, one is an individual farmer in Hungary and the other is working with a collective of farmers in France. On the other side, only two initiatives don’t sell directly to consumers at all. They are a seed conservation association and a farmer selling to professionals in a mid-tier chain.

Only one initiative did not know how their products reached consumers. This was a small individual farmer working in collaboration with other producers and with an association of traditional varieties in Italy. Another farmer implicated in a network of committed growers, whose distribution and sales are carried out by another company in Sweden, declared that they did not know how? these products reached consumers, but this farmer also had their own direct sales to consumers.

This leaves us with eight initiatives (10.3%) who are not selling food. Five of these are in the “other” actor type category, two are online platforms; and the final one is a processing company that is engaged in many activities linked to quality declared seeds production and sales, as well as farm advice.

Logically, rates of initiatives with an exclusively direct sales tend to be higher for the intermediary and shop categories as their type of enterprise is directly consumer facing (i.e., online platforms, CSA and shops).

Q3.21: Can you estimate the share (%) of the NUCs/NUC-based products of your initiative that is sold directly to consumers?

Share direct sales	All n	All %	Having hybrid sells %
=< 10%	8	10.3	34.8
11 - 50%	6	7.7	26.1
51 - 89%	6	7.7	26.1
>= 90%	3	3.8	13.0
Direct or indirect sales only or not concerned by food sales	55	70.5	

Table 23. Share of NUCS' sold directly to consumers, for initiatives with a hybrid selling chain

The proportion of NUCS sold directly to consumers varies across the 23 initiatives having a hybrid direct/indirect sale chain. The three that declared selling their NUCS almost exclusively directly to consumers (+90% of their sales) are three individual farmers: two in France working with traditional wheat varieties (a baker and a producer of flour and pasta) and one in Hungary (a small-scale vegetable farm focused around diversity and with a strong involvement of consumers).

The analysis across these two questions – sourcing directly from farmers and selling directly to consumers – provides an important insight about the type of value chains that are operating and valuing NUCs. This first point is that there is a wide variety of modalities of sourcing and selling NUCs - thus diversity in marketing channels is confirmed as a core strategy. The second point is, as a general rule, NUCs are sourced directly from farmers and there is usually up to two intermediaries (including farmers' collectives, processors, retailers and food service companies) between the producers and the consumers. These results suggest that we are dealing in short and mid-tier chains as a core supply chain organising mechanism.

Q3.22: How would you describe the consumers of the NUCs/NUC-based products you sell?

Type consumers	All n	All %	Made direct sale %
Repeat consumers	39	50.0	65.0
Frequent consumers	29	37.2	48.3
One-off consumers	17	21.8	28.3
Members of a loyalty program	8	10.3	13.3

Type consumers	All n	All %	Made direct sale %
Don't know	7	9.0	
Indirect sales only or not concerned by food sales	11	14.1	

Table 24. Type of NUCs consumers

NB: number of consumers types selected by initiatives not limited

Among the initiatives that sell at least some of their NUCs directly to consumers, the majority mentioned a single type of consumers (n=38, 63.3% of the 60 initiatives which declared a type of consumers).

The remaining 36.7% (n=22) claim to have a diversity of consumer types ranging from two to four. The most cited combinations of consumer types are: repeat consumers (once monthly) selected alone (n=19, 31.7%); Frequent consumers (once a week or more) selected alone (n=13, 21.6%); One-off consumers (single purchase) and repeat consumers (once monthly) (n=6, 10%); One-off consumers (single purchase) and repeat consumers (once monthly) and frequent consumers (once a week or more) (n=6, 10%); Repeat consumers (once monthly) and frequent consumers (once a week or more) (n=5, 8.3%).

Over the sample, “repeat consumers” and “frequent consumers” are the consumer types that are the most frequently cited (selected by respectively n=39, 65% and n=29, 48.3%).

These results suggest that those consumers who are purchasing NUCs know where to find them and consistently return to purchase them. The NUCs sellers thus have a rather loyal customer base. There is also evidence of other consumers who are testing the products, perhaps coming back eventually to purchase the NUCs again.

5.3.3. Digital tools and communication of the initiatives

In short and values-based chains, previous studies have noted that there is an increased reliance upon digital tools that can be used for both marketing and communication purposes (Loconto et al. 2021; Garrido-Garza et al. 2024). This information is particularly important for the design of DIVINFOOD’s WP1 as Tasks 3 and 4 will consist of experimenting with partners on the marketing and communication capacities of different tools as we try to add value to NUCs in the consumption domain. We therefore designed this portion of the questionnaire in order to help us to better understand how value is created for NUCs through current digital and other means of communication.

Q4.1 and Q4.6: Do you use online platforms? Do you rely on other means of communication?

Type of general communication	All n	All %	Declared communication %
Online platforms	72	92.3	94.7
Word of mouth	63	80.8	82.9
Labels	33	42.3	43.4
Brochures/flyers	30	38.5	39.5

Type of general communication	All n	All %	Declared communication %
Workshops/trainings	25	32.1	32.9
Sales point display	17	21.8	22.4
Posters	12	15.4	15.8
Other	9	11.5	11.8
TV	5	6.4	6.6
Radio	4	5.1	5.3
No communication	2	2.6	

Table 25. Type of communication means used by the initiatives for their general communication

NB: number of communication means selected by initiatives not limited

Q4.1 and Q4.6: Number of general communication means used by type of initiative

# general communication means used	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	1	0	0	1	0	2	2.9	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	2.6
1	1	1	0	1	1	4	2.9	9.1	0.0	12.5	5.9	5.1
2	5	2	2	0	5	14	14.3	18.2	28.6	0.0	29.4	17.9
3	11	4	0	3	2	20	31.4	36.4	0.0	37.5	11.8	25.6
4	12	3	3	2	4	24	34.3	27.3	42.9	25.0	23.5	30.8
5	3	1	2	1	1	8	8.6	9.1	28.6	12.5	5.9	10.3
6	0	0	0	0	3	3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	17.6	3.8
7	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
8	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	1.3
9	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 26. Number of communication means used by the initiatives for their general communication

Almost all of the initiatives communicate about the products that they sell. Only two initiatives declared that they do not communicate. These are one individual farmer with a small 4-hectare farm and a processor with strong activity linked to seed and raw materials in Italy.

Diversity again reigns in terms of communication strategies. Most initiatives use three to four communication media (n=44; 57.9% of those who communicate) and six initiatives (7.9%) are found to use from six to nine media to communicate. These highly communicative initiatives are four shops (a bulk store in Sweden, one in a third place, and two consumer run shops in France) and two farmers (an individual farmer under the ProSpecieRara label in Switzerland and a farmer and citizen collective in France).

The most cited combinations of communication used are: Online platforms and Word of mouth and Labels (n=9, 11.8%); Online platforms and Word of mouth (n=7, 9.2%); Online platforms and Word of mouth and Labels and Workshops/trainings (n=5, 6.6%).

We have only one online platform, who is focused on creating a solidarity economy network, that did not select one of the three main forms of communication found across the sample (i.e., online platform, word of mouth and label). This online platform communicates via “Workshops/trainings”, demonstrating that there is indeed a distinction about the purpose of digital tools and the role that they can play in valuing NUCs. In other words, having an online platform does not mean that marketing function is the same as the communication or information function.

Three additional initiatives do not communicate via online platforms. They are two individual farmers in France communicating via Word of mouth, Labels, Brochures, labels, brochures, ales point displays and one shop in Denmark where they communicate via Word of mouth.

Sale point displays are rarely used by the initiatives included in our sample, being cited by only 17 initiatives (22.4%), with no clear difference across actor types or countries.

Q4.2: Which platforms do you use?

Type of general communication	All n	All %	Declared online communication %
Facebook	59	75.6	81.9
Your own website	56	71.8	77.8
Instagram	47	60.3	65.3
Other	10	12.8	13.9
YouTube	9	11.5	12.5
Whatsapp	9	11.5	12.5
LinkedIn	9	11.5	12.5
TikTok	8	10.3	11.1
Another company's website	2	2.6	2.8
X – Twitter	1	1.3	1.4
No use of online platforms	6	7.7	

Table 27. Type of online platforms used by the initiatives for their general communication

NB: number of online platforms selected by initiatives not limited

The initiatives mainly use several online tools for general communication. Here again, diversity is an important communication strategy as only 11 initiatives reported that they used only one tool (15.3% of those using online platforms). To the extreme, eight initiatives (11.1%) communicated using five and up to eight tools (three “3 others”: associations in France and Switzerland and a seed company in Portugal), two shops (a cooperative store in Portugal, and a bulk store in Sweden), one processor and two farmers working with partners in France and in Italy).

The most cited combinations of online tools were: Own website and Facebook and Instagram (n=12, 16.6%); own website and Facebook (n=7, 9.7%); Own website and Facebook and Instagram (n=6, 8.3%), Instagram and Whatsapp (n=6, 8.3%).

Overall, Facebook and their Own company website, were the most often selected by the initiatives (respectively n=59, 81.9% and n=56, 77.8%). Only two initiatives didn't select at least one of these two tools: an individual farmer in France (using only an open-source tool dedicated to CSA management) and a baker/café in Sweden, using only Instagram.

Q4.4: For which of the following purposes do you use online platforms?

Purpose of online communication	All n	All %	Declared online platforms %
Information/content sharing	59	75.6	81.9
Marketing/selling purposes	55	70.5	76.4
Create/maintain a community around your initiative	51	65.4	70.8
Activism	19	24.4	26.4
Other	2	2.6	2.8
No use of online platforms	6	7.7	

Table 28. Purpose of online platforms used by initiatives for their general communication

NB: number of purposes selected by initiatives not limited

The use of social media platforms was mostly multi-purpose. Only 13 initiatives (18.1%) selected one unique purpose and to the extreme, 13 selected four to five purposes.

The most cited combinations of use included: Marketing/selling purposes and Information/content sharing and create/maintain a community around your initiative (n=22, 30.6%); the same three uses plus activism (n=12, 16.6%); Marketing/selling purposes and Information/content sharing (n=9, 12.5%).

There was only one initiative that did not select the three most cited purposes. This was a farmer who is part of a network of committed growers in Sweden, who declared that he used its "own and others' e-platforms for increased accessibility."

There are 17 initiatives who do not use online platforms for "marketing" purposes. This group includes all of the "other" actor types, except for the two seed companies, and one single organic shop in Portugal.

Q4.8: Do you actively promote the consumption of NUCs/NUC-based products?

Promotion of NUCS	All n	All %
Yes	56	71.8
No	15	19.2
I don't know	7	9.0
Total	78	100.0

Table 29. Number of initiatives that actively promote NUCs' consumption

Q4.9: Which of the following qualities of NUCs/NUC-based products do you promote?

NUCS qualities promoted	All n	All %	Declared guarantee system %
Environmental/landscape preservation	43	55.1	76.8
Promoting local agriculture	43	55.1	76.8
Health and nutrition	42	53.8	75.0
(Agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration	40	51.3	71.4
Culture and gastronomy	28	35.9	50.0
Diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian	12	15.4	21.4
Good value for money	10	12.8	17.9
Affordable price	7	9.0	12.5
Medical properties	6	7.7	10.7
Other	4	5.1	7.1
No NUCs' promotion or Don't know	22	28.2	

Table 30. NUCs' qualities promoted by the initiatives

NB: number of qualities selected by initiatives not limited

Q4.9: Number of NUCs' qualities promoted by type of initiative

# of NUCS qualities promoted	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	9	4	2	2	5	22	25.7	36.4	28.6	25.0	29.4	28.2
1	2	1	0	0	0	3	5.7	9.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8
2	0	0	2	1	1	4	0.0	0.0	28.6	12.5	5.9	5.1
3	5	2	2	0	3	12	14.3	18.2	28.6	0.0	17.6	15.4
4	10	0	1	3	2	16	28.6	0.0	14.3	37.5	11.8	20.5
5	5	1	0	1	4	11	14.3	9.1	0.0	12.5	23.5	14.1
6	3	2	0	0	0	5	8.6	18.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4
7	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	1.3
8	1	1	0	0	2	4	2.9	9.1	0.0	0.0	11.8	5.1
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 31. Number of NUCs' qualities promoted by the initiatives

The majority of initiatives (n=56, 71.8%) included in this sample are actively promoting the consumption of NUCs. There is no major difference among countries or actor types for those who do not know or do not promote NUCs.

When initiatives do communicate about NUCs, most of them highlight between three to five qualities (n=39, 69.6% of the initiatives that do active promotion of NUCS). The four initiatives that communicate on the greatest number of qualities (i.e. eight qualities) are: an online platform in France (with the mission of supporting sustainable agriculture), a farmer implicated in a network of committed growers in Sweden, a shop in a third place, and a consumer-run shop in France).

The most cited combinations of qualities that the initiatives promote are: Health and nutrition and Environmental/landscape preservation and (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration and Culture and gastronomy (preserving identity and heritage) and Promoting local agriculture (n=8; 14.3% of the initiatives that communicate). The second most commonly found combination of qualities are: Health and nutrition, and Environmental/landscape preservation and (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration and Promoting local agriculture (n=4; 7.1%). The third most frequent combination is Health and nutrition (e.g. rich in iron, fibre and protein) and Environmental/landscape preservation and (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration (n=3, 5.4%).

Overall, the four qualities, Environmental/landscape preservation, Promoting local agriculture, Health and nutrition, and (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, are the most cited by the initiatives (from 71.4 to 76.8% of the initiatives that communicate about NUCs). Only two initiatives don't cite any of these four qualities. The first is a shop in France that works in close collaboration with a farmer and communicates "Good value for money" and how NUCs can stimulate a "diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian." The other is a farmer in Hungary that promotes their NUCs as part of "Culture and gastronomy."

In sum, this data also supports the previously cited result about the initiatives' social missions. The majority of those are promoting NUCs for their environmental benefits, but in communication to consumers, we do see a higher frequency of health-related messages.

Q4.11: What communication channels do you use to promote NUCs/NUC-based products?

Communication means for NUCS promotion	All n	All %	Declared NUCS communication %
Online platforms	48	61.5	85.7
Word of mouth	35	44.9	62.5
Labels	25	32.1	44.6
Brochures/flyers	16	20.5	28.6
Workshops/trainings	13	16.7	23.2
Sales point display	8	10.3	14.3
Posters	6	7.7	10.7
TV	6	7.7	10.7
Radio	3	3.8	5.4

Communication means for NUCS promotion	All n	All %	Declared NUCS communication %
Other	2	2.6	3.6
No active promotion of NUCS	15	19.2	
Don't know if active promotion of NUCS	7	9.0	

Table 32. Type of communication means used by the initiatives for NUCs promotion

NB: number of communication means selected by initiatives not limited

Q4.11: Number of communication means used for NUCS' promotion by type of initiative

# of communication means for NUCS promotion	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	9	4	2	2	5	22	25.7	36.4	28.6	25.0	29.4	28.2
1	5	2	0	1	0	8	14.3	18.2	0.0	12.5	0.0	10.3
2	5	2	2	3	7	19	14.3	18.2	28.6	37.5	41.2	24.4
3	10	1	1	0	2	14	28.6	9.1	14.3	0.0	11.8	17.9
4	3	2	2	2	0	9	8.6	18.2	28.6	25.0	0.0	11.5
5	1	0	0	0	2	3	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	3.8
6	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
8	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	1.3
9	1	0	0	0	0	1	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 33. Number of communication means used by initiatives for NUCs promotion

There is no major difference in communication patterns when the initiatives promote NUCs or when they communicate more generally about their initiative (see Table 32): online platforms and word of mouth are the most often used (respectively n=48, 85.7% of the initiatives which promote NUCs and n=35, 62.5%); poster, radio, TV, and “other” were selected by less than 11% of the initiatives. However, the proportion of initiatives communicating specifically about NUCs is lower (n=56, 71.8% of the sample) than the proportion of initiatives that communicate more generally (n=76, 97.4%).

When initiatives do communicate about NUCs, they also tend to use fewer forms of communication than the number used for the general communication. The distribution is as follows: 19 initiatives gave the same number of modes of communication for NUCS and for their general communication (33.9% of the initiatives that communicate on NUCS); 18 had one more form for general communication (32.1%), while 15 (26.9%) had two to four more means for their general communication than they used to promote NUCs. There were only four initiatives (7.1%) that had one to three more communication modes for NUCS compared to their general communication strategy. We found here: an online platform in Italy that is building a solidarity economy network, a seed producer in Switzerland, an individual farmer in Sweden that is part of

a network of committed growers, and an individual farmer in Switzerland working with the ProSpeciRara label.

The majority of initiatives used two to three communication means for promoting NUCs (n=33; 58.9% of the initiatives that communicate on NUCs), with only six initiatives (10.7%) using five to nine means of communication: these are three shops (a bulk purchasing store in Sweden, an in third place, and a consumer run store in France), three farmers (an individual under ProSpecieRara label in Switzerland, a social farm with strong educational activities in Italy, and a collective of farmers and citizens in France).

The most cited combinations of means of communication were: Online platforms and Word of mouth and Labels (n=7, 12.5% of those doing NUCS promotion); Online platforms selected alone (n=6, 10.7%); Online platforms and Word of mouth (n=6, 10.7%); Online platforms and Labels (n=5, 8.9%).

Only a processor (a company in France specialised in the sorting and packaging of dried legumes and cereals) didn't select one of the three main means of communication found across the sample (i.e. online platforms, word of mouth, and labels). Instead, it communicates about NUCS via "Posters and TV". We also found that seven initiatives do not communicate via online platforms, all of whom are farmers (five in France, and one in Hungary, and in Portugal).

As noted for the general communication, sales point displays are rarely used (cited only by eight farmers or shops, 14.3% - only one of them didn't declare this entry for its general communication). Tasting campaigns were carried out by five initiatives, loyalty promotion by two initiatives, and promotional bundles or placing NUCs on display inside the stores was mentioned only once. A single initiative declared "other" forms of promotion of NUCs and indicated an engagement of the "Local origin producer".

Q4.15: Do you do any of the following to promote NUCs/NUC-based products?

NUCS promotion Actions	All n	All %	Declared NUCS promotion actions %
Talks/speeches	28	35.9	71.8
Cooking demonstrations	13	16.7	33.3
Teaching	13	16.7	33.3
Activism	9	11.5	23.1
Campaigning	6	7.7	15.4
Other	4	5.1	10.3
None of the above	17	21.8	
No active promotion of NUCS or Don't know	22	28.2	

Table 34. NUCs promotional actions carried out by the initiatives

NB: number of promotional actions selected by initiatives not limited

Of the 56 initiatives who actively promote NUCs, 39 (69,6%) do additional promotional activities. About half of them (n=19), do only one additional promotional activity, but there were three initiatives who had conducted four or five supplementary promotional activities for NUCs.

Here again we see a number of combinations of promotional activities that repeat across the initiatives.

Most cited combinations of promotion actions were: Talks/speeches selected alone (n=12, 30.8% of those additional doing promotion actions); Cooking demonstrations selected alone (n=3, 7.7%); Talks/speeches and activism (n=3, 7.7%); Talks/speeches and teaching (n=3, 7.7%).

Overall, talks/speeches are the most common additional activity that was reported by 71.8% of the initiatives (n=28).

Q4.17: Where do you do these activities?

NUCS promotion actions locations	All_n	All_P	Declared NUCS additional promotion actions %
In local events	25	32.1	64.1
In your main location	24	30.8	61.5
On social media	18	23.1	46.2
In a public venue	13	16.7	33.3
In regional events	13	16.7	33.3
In national events	7	9.0	17.9
In your other locations	6	7.7	15.4
Other	3	3.8	7.7
In international events	2	2.6	5.1
No active promotion of NUCS or don't know or don't do this type of actions	39	50.0	

Table 35. Locations of the NUCs' promotional actions carried out by the initiatives

NB: number of locations selected by initiatives not limited

Among the initiatives doing additional promotional activities (n=39), only nine initiatives (23.1%) selected only 1 location. Six initiatives choose between five and up to seven locations.

The top three locations were: “In local events” (n=25, 64.1%), “In your main location” (n=24, 61.5%) and “On social media” (n=18, 46.2%), showing that very local rentals and online events are preferred for this type of action.

International events were cited by two initiatives only and in combination with six other locations, being: an individual farmer in Hungary (a small-scale vegetable farm focused on diversity) and a social farm in Italy.

Q4.19: Do you solicit feedback from consumers?

Consumers feedback	All n	All %
Yes	34	43.6
No	39	50.0
I don't know	5	6.4
Total	78	100.0

Table 36. Number of initiatives seeking consumers' feedback**Q4.20: What communication channels do you use to solicit feedback from consumers?**

Consumer feedback mechanisms	All n	All %	Declared challenges %
Through direct exchanges with the customer	28	35.9	82.4
E-mail	12	15.4	35.3
Through interaction on social media	10	12.8	29.4
Your own website	8	10.3	23.5
Other	1	1.3	2.9
Another company's website	0	0.0	0.0
No consumers' feedback collected	44	56.4	

Table 37. Consumers' feedback systems used by the initiatives

NB: number of feedback systems selected by initiatives not limited

Only 34 initiatives (43.6%) collect consumer feedback. There are no major differences among countries and actor types for those initiatives who responded "No" and "Don't know."

Among the initiatives that collect consumers' feedback (n=34), 17 initiatives (50%) selected only one way to solicit feedback as compared to the other 50% (n=17) that had selected between two and four mechanisms.

The most cited combinations of feedback mechanisms are: Direct exchanges as the only selected option (n=14, 41.2%); e-mail and direct exchanges (n=4, 11.8%); and interactions in social media and direct exchanges (n=4, 11.8%).

Overall, the most frequently used mechanism was through direct exchanges with the consumer (n=28, 82.4% of those declaring a consumer feedback), which is in line with the results regarding the supply chains, whereby the majority of our initiatives are engaged in direct sales.

We found only six initiatives that didn't select "Direct exchanges with consumers." Instead, they selected online communication means (i.e., own website, social media interaction and/or e-mail), there are found in all countries, except for Denmark and Sweden and among all actor types, except processors.

5.3.4 Production, quality and prices

The literature on value chains noted a ‘quality turn’ that has occurred since the 1980s in particular, but has grown significantly since the turn of the millennium. The literature demonstrates that many farmers and intermediaries began to compete on a range of qualities that were signalled to consumers through a range of labels. This shifted the competition from being mostly about price, towards a competition whereby price was understood in relation to the quality that was being communicated. In the questionnaire, we therefore constructed a series of questions that allowed us to better understand this relationship between quality and price and how this translated into perceived benefits from the sale of NUCs.

Q5.1: Do you guarantee the quality of the NUCs/NUC-based products you sell or promote?

Guarantee quality	All n	All %
Yes	52	66.7
No	26	33.3
Total	78	100.0

Table 38. Number of initiatives guaranteeing NUCs' quality

Q5.2: How is this quality of NUCs/NUC-based products guaranteed?

Guarantee systems	All n	All %	Declared guarantee system %
Third party certification	37	47.4	71.2
Consumer feedback	24	30.8	46.2
Self-declaration	12	15.4	23.1
Social control	4	5.1	7.7
Business-to-business (B2B) verification	4	5.1	7.7
Participatory guarantee system	3	3.8	5.8
Other	2	2.6	3.8
No guarantee systems	26	33.3	

Table 39. NUCs' guarantee systems used by the initiatives

NB: number of guarantee systems selected by initiatives not limited

Q5.2: Number of guarantee systems used for NUCS by type of initiative

# of NUCS guarantee systems	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	9	4	4	3	6	26	25.7	36.4	57.1	37.5	35.3	33.3
1	16	2	1	3	7	29	45.7	18.2	14.3	37.5	41.2	37.2
2	8	2	2	1	1	14	22.9	18.2	28.6	12.5	5.9	17.9
3	2	1	0	1	3	7	5.7	9.1	0.0	12.5	17.6	9.0
4	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.0	18.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.6
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 40. Number of NUCS' guarantee systems used by initiatives

One third of the initiatives in our sample (n=26; 33.3%) does not use a guarantee system. When initiatives do provide a guarantee, they typically use only one certification system (n=29; 55.7% of the initiatives that certify), with only seven and two initiatives using respectively three and four certification systems. These triple-guaranteed actors are two farmers in Switzerland (one under the ProSpecieRara label), three shops (two cooperatives with consumers implication and a bulk shop respectively in Portugal, France and Denmark), one processor (baker specialised in traditional cereals in Italy), and an online platform in France (aiming at support sustainable agriculture). The quadruple-guaranteed initiatives are two online platforms (one in Hungary and one in Italy).

The most cited combinations of certification systems used include: Third-party selected alone (n=19; 36.5% of the initiatives that certify) followed by Third party certification and Consumer feedback (n=7; 13.5%); Consumer feedback selected alone (n=5; 9.6%); Self-declaration selected alone (n=4; 7.7%).

Overall, Third-party certification predominates the sector, with only 15 initiatives (28.8%) found in all countries, except Portugal and Switzerland, using other forms of guarantee.

Among these 15 initiatives, seven are farmers who use consumer feedback and/or self-declaration. Of the four intermediaries, three are online platforms using self-declaration or a mix of consumer feedback and business-to-business (B2B) verification or a mix of participatory guarantee systems (PGS) and consumer feedback and business-to-business (B2B) verification and Self-declaration. One is a market/CSA organiser using consumer feedback. The last two intermediaries are processors, one is a baker-café that uses a certification from its supplier, while the other is a restaurant that uses self-declaration. The final two initiatives are shops: a farmers' shop using self-declaration and a bulk store using consumer feedback.

Social control, B2B verification and participatory guarantee systems were less selected, either in isolation or in combination by nine initiatives (17.3%).

Q5.4: What are these guaranteed qualities of NUCs/NUC-based products?

NUCS certified qualities	All n	All %	Declared guarantee system %
Organic	46	59.0	88.5
Place/origin	32	41.0	61.5
Taste	27	34.6	51.9
Nutrition benefits	21	26.9	40.4
Ecosystem services	13	16.7	25.0
Colour	10	12.8	19.2
Tradition	10	12.8	19.2
Size	8	10.3	15.4
Vegan	6	7.7	11.5
Other	5	6.4	9.6
Medical properties	4	5.1	7.7
Easy to cook/process	3	3.8	5.8
Known recipes	1	1.3	1.9
Psychedelic properties	1	1.3	1.9
Religion	0	0.0	0.0
Weight loss	0	0.0	0.0
No guarantee systems	26	33.3	

Table 41. NUCs' qualities guaranteed by the initiatives

NB: number of qualities selected by initiatives not limited

When initiatives use guarantee systems, they typically guarantee less than three qualities (one quality certified (n=11; 21.2%); two qualities certified (n=10; 19.2%); three qualities certified (n=10; 19.2%). Only seven initiatives (13.5%) certify more than seven qualities and up to nine. They are four farmers (two are Swiss farmers, one of whom work with the ProSpecieRara label and 2 in France present huge processing activities and work in collaboration with partners), an online platform in France (aiming at support sustainable agriculture); a processor (baker specialised in traditional cereals in Italy) and a shop (cooperative with consumers implication in Portugal).

The most cited qualities certified combinations are: organic selected alone (n=8; 15.4% the initiatives declaring a certification system); Place/origin + organic (n= 5; 9.6%); Taste + Place/origin + organic (n=4; 7.7%).

Overall, organic quality certification predominates in the sector, with only six initiatives not declaring this quality. They are two "other" initiatives (a seed company and an association promoting seeds/genetic that certified authenticity or seeds qualities - as disease tests), two intermediaries (a market/CSA organiser and an online platform in Hungary), a processor (baker-café in Sweden), and a bulk store in France. Place/origin, taste and nutrition qualities are the following most selected qualities (cited by more than 40% of the initiatives). These results confirm the results from a previous study that focused on short food value chains in the EU (Loconto et al. 2023).

Q5.6: Do you provide information to consumers about how NUCs are grown?

Growing information	All n	All %
Yes	53	67.9
No	25	32.1
Total	78	100.0

Table 42. Number of initiatives providing NUCs' growing information

A majority (n=53, 67.9%) of the surveyed initiatives claim to provide information to their consumers about how NUCs are cultivated. This proportion is equivalent as the one found for NUCs promotion.

However, those initiatives that are promoting NUCs and those declaring that they transmit information about how the NUCs are grown, are not all the same initiatives. In other words, among the 22 initiatives that do not promote NUCs actively, 13 of them do provide information to consumers about the growing conditions. While among the 56 that do promote NUCs, 16 of them do not communicate how the NUCs are grown. Farmers and processors tend to present highest proportion of initiatives communicating on growing (more than 77% of them, while this proportion is around 50% for the other initiatives).

Q5.8: How do you share this information?

NUCS growing communication means	All n	All %	Declared growing information %
Word of mouth	39	50.0	73.6
Online platforms	32	41.0	60.4
Labels	21	26.9	39.6
Workshops/trainings	13	16.7	24.5
Sales point display	9	11.5	17.0
Brochures/flyers	7	9.0	13.2
Posters	4	5.1	7.5
Other	4	5.1	7.5
Radio	2	2.6	3.8
TV	1	1.3	1.9
No growing information provided	25	32.1	

Table 43. NUCs' growing information communication means used by the initiatives

NB: number of communication means selected by initiatives not limited

The responses to this question are fully aligned with the responses received for the general communication and with the NUCs promotion. The only slight difference observed is that word of mouth communication is slightly more cited than online platforms (n=39, 73.6%) for the growing information.

As found in the case of the promotion of NUCs, the majority of respondents used two to three communication means (n=33; 62.3%), while only 12 (22.6%) initiatives used just one form of communication. We found just three initiatives (5.7%) that used a large diversity of communication channels (five or seven). These are farmers (one in Switzerland under the ProSpeciRara label and one collective of farmers and citizens in France), and a participatory non-profit supermarket in France.

The most frequently cited combinations of communication channels are: Online platforms and word of mouth (n=9, 16.9%); Word of mouth without another option selected (n=7, 13.2%).

Q5.10: What benefit(s) does the sale or promotion of NUCs/NUC-based products provide for your initiative?

Benefits of NUCS sales	All n	All %	Declared benefits %
Environmental	51	65.4	79.7
Cultural	30	38.5	46.9
Economic	27	34.6	42.2
Social	25	32.1	39.1
Political	13	16.7	20.3
Other	9	11.5	14.1
Provide(s) no additional benefits	14	17.9	

Table 44. Benefits of NUCs' promotion/sale perceived by the initiatives

NB: number of benefits selected by initiatives not limited

Q5.10: Number of perceived benefits of NUCs promotion/sale by type of initiative

# of benefits for NUCS sells	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
0	6	0	1	1	6	14	17.1	0.0	14.3	12.5	35.3	17.9
1	5	4	2	2	3	16	14.3	36.4	28.6	25.0	17.6	20.5
2	13	6	1	4	2	26	37.1	54.5	14.3	50.0	11.8	33.3
3	5	0	1	1	3	10	14.3	0.0	14.3	12.5	17.6	12.8
4	4	0	0	0	0	4	11.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.1
5	2	1	1	0	3	7	5.7	9.1	14.3	0.0	17.6	9.0
6	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.0	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0	1.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 45. Number of perceived benefits of NUCs' promotion/sales by type of initiative

An important finding is that only 14 initiatives (17.9% of the whole sample) declared not to make any profit from the sale or the valorisation of NUCs. These initiatives are found across all countries and initiative types, except for intermediaries.

When they declared benefits, a majority of them selected one to two choices (n=42; 65.6% of those which perceived benefits). We also found a dedicated group of 12 (18.8%) initiatives that perceived between four to six benefits from their sales of NUCs.

The most frequently cited combinations of benefits are: Environmental selected alone (n=8; 12.5%), followed by all five benefits selected (n=7; 10.9%); Economic and Environmental (n=7; 10.9%); Cultural and Environmental (n=6; 9.4%); Social and Environmental (n=5; 7.8%).

Overall, as is the case with the results related to the social missions and the qualities communicated about NUCs, the environmental benefits predominate among our responses (selected by n=51, 79.7%). Only 13 initiatives in France, Hungary, Italy and Portugal did not select receiving an environmental benefit (20.3% - of all types of initiatives).

Q5.17 Do you sell or promote NUCs/NUC-based products only when they are in season?

NUCS in season promotion sells	All n	All %
Yes	28	35.9
No	33	42.3
I don't know	17	21.8
Total	78	100.0

Table 46. Number of initiatives promoting or selling NUCs only in season

The responses given by initiatives in response to this question are mixed and are essentially guided by the type of products they dealt with (fresh vs. dried/processed products).

5.3.5 Price, competition, demand and challenges

The literature on value chains also attempts to understand how value is created within food environments that can offer enabling or disabling conditions for the sale of NUCs. While NUCs are, by definition, quite rare and incomparable to other products because they are neglected, and thus both supply and demand are typically low, it is important to try to look at their markets in context in order to better understand how value is created.

We therefore used these final questions of the questionnaire as a mean to understand whether or not there are enabling food environments of NUCs in the 7~seven countries that we studied.

Q5.19: How do the consumers prices of NUCs/NUC-based products compare to similar non-NUC products?

NUCS consumer price	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Higher	25	5	3	7	12	52	71.4	45.5	42.9	87.5	70.6	66.7
Lower	1	0	0	1	2	4	2.9	0.0	0.0	12.5	11.8	5.1
The same	9	6	4	0	3	22	25.7	54.5	57.1	0.0	17.6	28.2
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 47. Estimated NUCs consumers' price by the initiatives

A majority of initiatives (n=52; 66.7%) consider the consumer price of NUCs to be higher when compared to similar non-NUCs products. This higher proportion is found across all types of initiatives and countries. Only four initiatives found NUCs to be cheaper. These were three in Denmark: an organic shop, a bulk store selling various NUCS such as ancient grains, and a restaurant selling lentils, chickpeas, and red and purple wheat. The last initiative was a farmer in Italy that is developing a quinoa value chain.

Q5.20: How do the profit margins you make for NUCs/NUC-based products compare to similar non-NUC products?

NUCS margin	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
Higher	11	2	0	3	1	17	31.4	18.2	0.0	37.5	5.9	21.8
Lower		1	2	4	5	21	25.7	9.1	28.6	50.0	29.4	26.9
The same	15	8	5	1	11	40	42.9	72.7	71.4	12.5	64.7	51.3
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 48. Estimated NUCs margin by the initiatives

Half of our respondents (n=40, 51.3%) found that the profit made from NUCs is similar to that made from similar non-NUCs products. The proportion of answers for this question seems to be smaller for farmer and processor categories.

Q6.2: How high is the competition?

NUCS competition	Farmer n	Intermediary n	Other n	Processor n	Shop n	All n	Farmer %	Intermediary %	Other %	Processor %	Shop %	All %
High	3	1	0	2	2	8	8.6	9.1	0.0	25.0	11.8	10.3
Low	5	3	0	1	2	11	14.3	27.3	0.0	12.5	11.8	14.1
Medium	12	2	1	1	4	20	34.3	18.2	14.3	12.5	23.5	25.6
No competition	13	3	2	4	6	28	37.1	27.3	28.6	50.0	35.3	35.9
Don't know if competition	2	2	4	0	3	11	5.7	18.2	57.1	0.0	17.6	14.1
Total	35	11	7	8	17	78						

Table 49. Estimated level of competition for NUCs' by the initiatives

The level of competition of NUCs is widely perceived as non-existent or low (n=39, 50% of the initiatives vs. only eight (10.3%) considering the level of competition as high). These eight initiatives facing high competition are: two shops (a bulk store in Hungary, and a participatory non-profit supermarket in France); two processors (a baker specialised in traditional cereals in Italy; and a bread factory in Denmark); an online platform in Italy that is developing a solidarity economy network; and finally, three farmers (a social farm in Italy, a farm in Portugal with many activities, a farmer in France with strong processing activities and working in close collaboration with partners).

Q6.3: What are the main challenges of producing NUCs?

NUCS production Challenge	All n	All %	Declared challenges %
Lack of markets	45	57.7	69.2
Unavailability of seeds	27	34.6	41.5
Unfavourable agronomic conditions	21	26.9	32.3
Other	7	9.0	10.8
Lack of integrated cropping systems	6	7.7	9.2
Lack of organic inputs	3	3.8	4.6
No specific NUCs production challenges	13	16.7	

Table 50. NUCs' production challenges perceived by the initiatives

NB: number of challenges selected by initiatives not limited

Only 13 initiatives (16.7% of the whole sample) declared no specific production challenge linked to NUCs. These responses were found across all countries except for Portugal, Sweden and Switzerland and all initiatives' types except the 'other' category.

Half of those declaring production challenges selected one modality (n=34; 52.3%). Maximum number of challenged observed is for an initiative who declared facing four challenges. This initiative is the online platform aiming at develop a solidarity economy network in Italy.

The most cited combinations of challenges identified are: Lack of market selected alone (n=20; 30.8%) followed by Unavailability of seeds and of markets selected alone (n=7; 10.8%); by Unfavourable agronomic conditions and Lack of markets (n=7; 10.8%); and by Unavailability of seeds selected alone (n=6, 9.2%).

Overall, the lack of a market is the most frequently cited challenge for producing NUCs, with only 21 initiatives (32.3%) not selecting this option. The initiatives were of all types and found in all countries, except Denmark. This response confirms some of our earlier interpretation of the results about the absence of long-term contracts among our initiatives, most likely due to a lack of demand and supply.

Q6.6: What are the main challenges of processing NUCs?

NUCS processing Challenge	All n	All %	Declared challenges %
Insufficient demand	27	34.6	55.1
Physical qualities	12	15.4	24.5
Other	9	11.5	18.4
Insufficient supply	8	10.3	16.3
Too much competition among products	7	9.0	14.3
Organoleptic qualities	6	7.7	12.2
Lack of tasty recipes	3	3.8	6.1
No specific NUCs processing challenges	29	37.2	

Table 51. NUCs' processing challenges perceived by the initiatives

NB: number of challenges selected by initiatives not limited

A little more than a third of the initiatives (n=29, 37.2%), declared no specific processing challenge linked to NUCs. This response was found across all countries and all types of actors.

The majority of those declaring processing challenges selected one option only (n=31; 63.2). The maximum number of challenges is observed for an independent knowledge hub in Switzerland, who declared that they faced four challenges.

The most cited combinations of challenges found are: Insufficient demand selected alone (n=14, 28.6%); Other selected alone (n=5, 10.2%).

Overall, “Insufficient demand” was the most often chosen by the initiatives (n=27, 55.1%). This most cited challenge is in line with those observed for production and selling. This result further confirms an earlier analytical point in that there remains a lack of demand through the value chain, which in turn can partly explain the reliance on one’s ‘own production’ and direct sales so to ensure the consistency of supply to loyal consumers.

Q6.9: What are the main challenges of selling NUCs?

NUCS selling challenge	All n	All %	Declared challenges %
Lack of consumers awareness	52	66.7	88.1
Lack of consumers knowledge of how to cook them	31	39.7	52.5
Too much competition among products	14	17.9	23.7
Limited product range	6	7.7	10.2
Physical qualities	5	6.4	8.5
Lack of tasty recipes	5	6.4	8.5
Organoleptic qualities	2	2.6	3.4
Other	2	2.6	3.4

NUCS selling challenge	All n	All %	Declared challenges %
No specific NUCs/NUC based-products selling challenges	19	24.4	

Table 52. NUCs' selling challenges perceived by the initiatives

NB: number of challenges selected by initiatives not limited

Nineteen initiatives (24.4%) declared no specific selling challenge linked to NUCs, independent of their country of origin or their actor type.

The majority of those declaring selling challenges selected several options (n=40; 67.8%). The maximum number of sales challenges is observed in two initiatives declaring four challenges: an online platform that supports sustainable agriculture in France and a farmer also in France with multiple activities.

The most frequently cited combinations of challenges found are: Lack of consumer awareness and Lack of consumer knowledge of how to cook them (n=14, 23.7%); Lack of consumer awareness selected alone (n=13, 22.3%); Too much competition among products and Lack of consumer awareness and Lack of consumer knowledge of how to cook them (n=7, 11.8%).

Overall, the most selected challenge is in line with the ones observed for production and processing ("Lack of consumer awareness", n=52, 88.1%), although this was more selected for selling than for production and processing. In this context, it was framed as a "Lack of consumer awareness" as it is indeed the consumers themselves that constitute the demand further upstream.

5.4 Conclusions from reading the descriptive statistics of the survey

The main conclusions that we can draw from the analysis of the responses to this survey is that NUCs are currently being valued in food environments that are not very well suited to their promotion. Competition with non-NUC comparable products exists, but the main problem is a lack of demand for these products.

We have found rather surprising similarities across the seven countries studied, with the majority of differences being found between different actor types.

With regards to the objective of better understanding the food chains that are valuing (agro)biodiversity, we must start from the observation that the vast majority of these chains are short or mid-tier chains. We see producers who are adding on intermediary functions to their own work and thus creating short chains for processed goods (e.g., bread). We also observe a large category of intermediary actors who are sourcing both directly and indirectly from farmers and selling both directly and indirectly to consumers. The origins of the NUCs that are sold are generally multiple and thus span from the same municipality to the same country for the majority of initiatives. This observation suggests that there may be a number of elements linked to how these initiatives are setup and governed that might provide a more nuanced understanding of how value is created.

We develop a value chain typology in the next section in order to advance this more nuanced understanding of values creation.

6. Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing (agro)biodiversity

As described in Section 1, one of the objectives of Task 1.2 is to explore the relevance and prevalence of NUCs in the food environments of the seven project countries. Specifically, we aim to understand the significance of NUCs and NUC-based products in various short and mid-tier value chains, and how these value chains, in turn, contribute to the penetration of NUCs in food environments.

To this end, we developed a typology of chains that successfully value (appreciate, incorporate, sell) NUCs, based on data collected from various online resources and via our online survey. The typology focuses on short and mid-tier value chains that are valuing NUCs, specifically those related to our project, namely legumes and minor cereals. The typology helps to understand the characteristics of the different value chains that successfully value NUCs and offer insights and best practices for value chain actors on how to effectively introduce and deliver these products to consumers.

As introduced in the literature review, we have identified a number of characteristics of value chains that can help us to identify patterns and trends in how (agro)biodiversity, and NUCs in particular, are being valued in current food environments.

We draw upon the four foundational theories of value chains presented in section two and we operationalised these into a series of variables that enabled us to cluster the initiatives and identify subtle differences in how the value chains are organised.

The first characterisation that is needed for describing a value chain is the identification of the primary activities that are carried out. Porter (1985) had identified four key activities: inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing & sales and services. We used the identification of these aspects in our approach to identify the **actor type** according to the core focus of their operations. We have consolidated these into the following types: farmer, intermediary (online platform or CSA), processor (including restaurants), shop and other (including research, education, tourism).

We also identified the way in which inbound and outbound logistics are organised by identifying the number of **intermediaries** supplying inputs/products and those that are responsible for on-selling the products. This enabled us to identify the lengths of the chains in a rather rudimentary way. An important point to remember while reading this typology is that our sampling bias means that we are dealing mostly with short and mid-tier chains. We have not included in our sample the long value chains that may be linking the production of legumes and cereals with supermarkets across Europe. Future research should be conducted through interviews with the initiatives in our database in order to gain more detailed information about the nature of the intermediaries who are supplying and on selling NUCs in the longer chains that we identified here.

The marketing, sales and services activities are captured in our data through the identification of **communication strategies**. The literature (Garrido-Garza et al. 2024) suggests that

communication, and digital market infrastructures in particular, are being used in value chains in order to market/sell products and services, but also to provide information, which can lend itself to education or advocacy activities.

An important point, which is indeed the main pivot point in distinguishing the four types of value chains, is the role of what has been referred to as the “supply chain captain”. This is the key actor who governs the value chain and is thus considered to be the initiative that has been included in our study. Following Gereffi’s (1994) governance typology that separates the way in which this captain coordinates (i.e., drives) the activities upstream and downstream from their operation, five modalities may be defined: hierarchy, captive, relational, modular, and market. These governance forms indicate the extent to which the value chains are vertically integrated or based on market and other economic relations. In our typology, we clarified the types of contracts with suppliers and the types of interactions with consumers.

Moreover, in an attempt to better understand the values aspect of value chains, we looked to the recent literature on values-based supply chains (Feenstra and Hardesty 2016; Ostrom et al. 2017) and van der Ploeg’s (2012) notion of nested markets (Osti and Carrosio 2020; van der Ploeg and Schneider 2022). The question of the nature and types of the quality guarantees and the competitive nature of prices for NUCs, open up the possibilities for understanding the extent to which transparency, fairness and other social values are combined within the market exchanges.

Finally, recent literature has opened up the debate about mission first companies within values-based chains that are increasingly changing the nature of how organisations prioritise the way they manage their businesses and how they engage in their broader communities (Low and Davenport 2009; Collins and Kahn 2017). We have taken this into consideration as we explored the **number and types of missions declared** and the way that these interact with the declared **benefits from selling NUCs**.

In sum, we identified discriminating characteristics among the ‘captains’ who are valuing NUCs as they manage the relations up and down the value chains that link producers and consumers. They are grouped together under the following four characteristics:

- Primary activities
- Governance and coordination among actors
- Transparency and communication
- Missions

We conducted cluster-based statistical analysis of our data in order to group these captains within four discrete types of chains that value (agro)biodiversity. Based on a first clustering, we organised a participatory modelling workshop whereby we presented this typology and received feedback from project participants and external experts, including ‘consumption influencers’ (see glossary for definition). The experts’ feedback led us to draw up a second typology, which we submitted to the DIVINFOOD partners for validation at the project’s annual meeting in June 2024. A summary and additional material on these workshops are available in Appendix 6 of this document and in the space dedicated to DIVINFOOD in the Zenodo open access directory (see links in Appendix 6).

6.1 Characterisation of the ideal type clusters

As previously explained, in an attempt to assess whether the profiles of initiatives can be identified taking into account variables that may reflect key concepts found in the value-based chains literature. What we know from this literature is that values-based food supply chains pay attention to three core elements: the level of transparency in the communication of quality, the ways in which coordination among actors is carried out, and the concern over paying fair prices to producers.

When we read our empirical data according to these characteristics, we can identify two aspects that have set the initiatives, and the value chains that they lead, apart. These are the degree to which they are communicating about the qualities and benefits of NUCs up and down their chains between producers and consumers on the one hand, and on the other hand, the extent to which NUCs are embedded within the core mission of the supply chain captain. The hypothesis here is that the greater the embeddedness within the mission of the lead organisation coordinating the supply chain, and the greater the transparency and communication about the quality up and down that chain, the higher the benefits of agrobiodiversity in food environments.

Communication about NUCs	Quality Communicators	Active Promoters
	High level of communication about NUCs Low level of integration of NUCs into their core mission	High level of communication about NUCs High level of integration of NUCs into their core mission
	Silent Sellers	Mission First
	Low level of communication about NUCs Low level of integration of NUCs into their core mission	Low level of communication about NUCs High level of integration of NUCs into their core mission
Integration of NUCs in the core mission of the supply chain captain		

Table 53. Typology of chains that value NUCs

Based on the above matrix, we developed four clusters using the responses to the following question as proxies for the degree of active promotion of NUCs and the degree of separating the NUCs from the core mission of the supply chain captain. The criteria we used were: declared social missions (Q2. 13), perceived benefits of NUCs sales/valorisation (Q5.10), communications channels used to promote NUCs (Q4.11), promoted qualities of NUCs (Q4.9), certification systems used for NUCs (Q5.2) and certified qualities of NUCs (Q5.4). Each question was recorded by determining the number of modalities chosen by the initiative to answer to the question, in order to transcribe the extent of how initiatives are missions driven, the extent of perceived benefits of agrobiodiversity, their level of communication and certification. The matrix was then submitted to a Hierarchical Cluster Analysis by using the Ward's method (Factoextra package in R) grouping the initiatives into four different profiles. To understand what defines the four profiles, score means of each question were calculated for each of them (Table 54).

Cluster	nb_social_missions	nb_benefits_selling_nucs	nb_nucs_communications	nb_quality_promoted	nb_certifications	nb_guaranteed_qualities
1 (n=21)	4.86	2.86	3.14	4.48	2.43	5.19
2 (n=26)	2.58	1.38	0.27	0.27	0.69	0.92
3 (n=16)	0.12	1.25	2.62	4.62	0.62	2.56
4 (n=15)	7.27	2.60	3.13	4.00	0.47	0.87

Table 54. Average score per cluster for social missions, NUCs' perceived benefits, NUCs' communication and NUCs' certification questions

NB: In the table, nb is an abbreviation for number.

Cluster 1, which we have labelled as **Active Promoters** Type, is characterised by **the greater use of certification systems** (no initiative in this cluster does not certify; 95% of them declare at least two certification systems) and by **the certification of a high number of qualities** (almost all initiatives certifying more than four qualities are found in this cluster - these initiatives represent 81% of the cluster's headcounts). Furthermore, this cluster tends to declare a rather high number of social missions (62% of them declare four missions or more; the cluster obtains the second highest average on this indicator); to perceive a high number of benefits from the sale/valorisation of NUCS (57% of them declare at least three benefits; highest average on this indicator); to declare several communication channels (this cluster presenting the highest proportion of initiatives using three to four means of communication; highest average obtained for this indicator together with Cluster 4); and to promote a high number of qualities (67% of them declare promoting four or more qualities, second highest average on this indicator).

Cluster 2, or the **Silent sellers** cluster, is characterised by initiatives **that do not communicate** (81% of them declare no means of communication; those that do communicate use a maximum of two means of communication, with few qualities promoted - maximum two). In addition, this cluster tends to declare none or fewer social missions (39% declare no social mission and 27% declare three or fewer social missions, median score obtained on this indicator); to perceive none or fewer benefits (31% of them perceive no benefits; 58% one to two benefits; lowest average obtained on this indicator together with Cluster 3). The profile in terms of certification is shared as for Clusters 3 and 4 - with 46% of them not certifying - the slightly higher average obtained for this cluster is explained by the presence of a few initiatives (11% of the cluster) using two or three certification systems. When they certify, they guarantee few qualities (46% one or two qualities and a maximum of three qualities; lowest average obtained together with Cluster 4).

The Quality communicators found in Cluster 3 are characterised by initiatives that **do not declare any social missions** (only one initiative in this cluster declared two social missions). In addition, this cluster tends to perceive none or fewer benefits (19% of them perceive no benefits; the rest declare a maximum of two benefits; lowest average score on this indicator together with Cluster 2); to use a limited number of communication channels (this cluster presents the highest proportion of initiatives using one or two communication systems); on the other hand, they **communicate on a significant number of qualities** (at least three qualities promoted; highest average score for this indicator). Compared with Clusters 2 and 4, this cluster has the lowest proportion of initiatives that do not certify (38%; those that do certify declare only one certification system), and certifies a greater number of qualities than the two previous Clusters (higher proportion of initiatives certifying two or more qualities).

Cluster 4 is characterised by **Mission first** initiatives **declaring a high number of social missions** (they declare at least four social missions; 60% of them declare more than seven social missions). In addition, this cluster tends to perceive a high number of benefits (47% declare at least three benefits, second highest average for this indicator); to declare several communication channels (second highest proportion of initiatives using three to four means of communication; highest average obtained together with Cluster 1) but on a smaller number of qualities than Clusters 1 and 3 (67% with three to four qualities). Compared with Clusters 2 and 3, it has the highest proportion of initiatives that do not certify (53%; those that do certify declare only one certification system); it certifies only on a limited number of qualities, 33% with one or two qualities and a maximum of three qualities).

6.2 Descriptive statistics per type

In order to assess if some characteristics can explain the four identified profiles, descriptive statistics for each of them have been calculated on the other main questions of the survey (Table 55). This has not revealed any specific characteristics among clusters, with the exception of the number of NUCS categories treated, which seems to be greater for Cluster 1, with a higher proportion of initiatives being specialised in legumes-cereals NUCS.

Characteristic	**CL 1**, N = 21	**CL 2**, N = 26	**CL 3**, N = 16	**CL 4**, N = 15	**All** (total= 78)
### Country					
Denmark	1 (4.8%)	3 (12%)	1 (6.2%)	0 (0%)	5 (6.4%)
France	8 (38%)	6 (23%)	8 (50%)	8 (53%)	30 (38%)
Hungary	2 (9.5%)	8 (31%)	0 (0%)	3 (20%)	13 (17%)
Italy	4 (19%)	2 (7.7%)	3 (19%)	1 (6.7%)	10 (13%)
Portugal	2 (9.5%)	3 (12%)	0 (0%)	2 (13%)	7 (9.0%)
Sweden	0 (0%)	1 (3.8%)	4 (25%)	0 (0%)	5 (6.4%)
Switzerland	4 (19%)	3 (12%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.7%)	8 (10%)
### Initiative's type					
Farmer	9 (43%)	10 (38%)	10 (62%)	6 (40%)	35 (45%)
Intermediary	4 (19%)	5 (19%)	1 (6.2%)	1 (6.7%)	11 (14%)
Other	2 (9.5%)	3 (12%)	0 (0%)	2 (13%)	7 (9.0%)
Processor	2 (9.5%)	3 (12%)	3 (19%)	0 (0%)	8 (10%)
Shop	4 (19%)	5 (19%)	2 (12%)	6 (40%)	17 (22%)
### Year funded					
<= 2000	3 (14%)	7 (27%)	3 (19%)	1 (6.7%)	14 (18%)
2001-2010	4 (19%)	3 (12%)	3 (19%)	3 (20%)	13 (17%)
2011-2020	13 (62%)	14 (54%)	10 (62%)	8 (53%)	45 (58%)
>= 2021	1 (4.8%)	2 (7.7%)	0 (0%)	3 (20%)	6 (7.7%)
### Number of food categories treated					
1	3 (14%)	1 (3.8%)	2 (12%)	4 (27%)	10 (13%)
2	1 (4.8%)	7 (27%)	4 (25%)	1 (6.7%)	13 (17%)
3	4 (19%)	6 (23%)	5 (31%)	1 (6.7%)	16 (21%)

Characteristic	**CL 1** N = 21	**CL 2** N = 26	**CL 3** N = 16	**CL 4** N = 15	**All** (total= 78)
4	2 (9.5%)	2 (7.7%)	2 (12%)	2 (13%)	8 (10%)
5	4 (19%)	1 (3.8%)	1 (6.2%)	3 (20%)	9 (12%)
6	5 (24%)	7 (27%)	2 (12%)	3 (20%)	17 (22%)
7	2 (9.5%)	2 (7.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.7%)	5 (6.4%)
### Number of NUCs categories treated					
1	5 (24%)	10 (38%)	9 (56%)	6 (40%)	30 (38%)
2	4 (19%)	12 (46%)	6 (38%)	5 (33%)	27 (35%)
3	4 (19%)	1 (3.8%)	1 (6.2%)	3 (20%)	9 (12%)
4	5 (24%)	2 (7.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	7 (9.0%)
5	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (1.3%)
6	2 (9.5%)	1 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.7%)	4 (5.1%)
### NUCs' specialisation					
NUCS cereals	7 (33%)	16 (62%)	9 (56%)	7 (47%)	39 (50%)
NUCS legumes	0 (0%)	3 (12%)	3 (19%)	4 (27%)	10 (13%)
NUCS legumes cereals	14 (67%)	6 (23%)	4 (25%)	4 (27%)	28 (36%)
NUCS other	0 (0%)	1 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (1.3%)
### NUCs' share activity					
<5%	3 (14%)	9 (35%)	3 (19%)	5 (33%)	20 (26%)
5 - 25%	8 (38%)	10 (38%)	4 (25%)	4 (27%)	26 (33%)
26 - 95%	6 (29%)	5 (19%)	7 (44%)	3 (20%)	21 (27%)
>95%	4 (19%)	2 (7.7%)	2 (12%)	3 (20%)	11 (14%)
### Supply sales chains					
Own producer; own producer hybrid	5 (24%)	6 (23%)	6 (38%)	3 (20%)	20 (26%)
Direct supply chain only	11 (52%)	7 (27%)	4 (25%)	3 (20%)	25 (32%)
Other	5 (24%)	13 (50%)	6 (38%)	9 (60%)	33 (42%)
### Sales chains					
Direct sales only	14 (67%)	15 (58%)	9 (56%)	6 (40%)	44 (56%)
Hybrid, short or medium sales chain	4 (19%)	7 (27%)	7 (44%)	8 (53%)	26 (33%)
Not concerned by food sales	3 (14%)	4 (15%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.7%)	8 (10%)
### NUCs' consumer price					
Lower	1 (4.8%)	1 (3.8%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	4 (5.1%)
The same	4 (19%)	10 (38%)	4 (25%)	4 (27%)	22 (28%)
Higher	16 (76%)	15 (58%)	10 (62%)	11 (73%)	52 (67%)
### NUCs' margin profit					
Lower	8 (38%)	5 (19%)	6 (38%)	2 (13%)	21 (27%)
The same	9 (43%)	16 (62%)	7 (44%)	8 (53%)	40 (51%)
Higher	4 (19%)	5 (19%)	3 (19%)	5 (33%)	17 (22%)
### NUCs' competition					

Characteristic	**CL 1**, N = 21	**CL 2**, N = 26	**CL 3**, N = 16	**CL 4**, N = 15	**All** (total= 78)
Low	6 (29%)	2 (7.7%)	3 (19%)	0 (0%)	11 (14%)
Medium	5 (24%)	8 (31%)	5 (31%)	2 (13%)	20 (26%)
High	4 (19%)	2 (7.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (13%)	8 (10%)
No competition	4 (19%)	8 (31%)	7 (44%)	9 (60%)	28 (36%)
Don't know if competition	2 (9.5%)	6 (23%)	1 (6.2%)	2 (13%)	11 (14%)

Table 55. Summary of descriptive statistics per cluster (Percentage by column)

6.3 Case studies that illustrate the typology

In order to better understand the characteristics of each type of initiative that we have identified, we present in Appendix 7 a short description of initiatives found in our database that represent the characteristics of each of the four types of short and mid-tier chains that value agrobiodiversity.

One of the largest challenges that we faced creating the typology was the specificity of each initiative and finding patterns that could exemplify the diversity found in the value chains. We present seven initiatives for each of the four types of value chain; thus, we have selected one of each type in each of our seven countries. The purpose of this selection is to illustrate the diversity found across initiatives; we do not make the claim that the cases presented here are necessarily representative of all of the initiatives in the database. However, they are rather typical for each cluster (Table 56).

The fact that some countries do not have a case example for each type of value chain is most likely due to the low response rate and not due to an absence of this type of initiative in the country.

	Active promoters	Silent sellers	Quality communicators	Mission first
Denmark	Genfyld - Emballagefri købmand	Kornsang	Torup Spisehus	n/a
France	Odyssee d'engrain	Les Champs de blé earl	Earl la Ferme du Bois du Treuil	La Cagette de Montpellier
Hungary	Farm2Fork Kft.	Jóllét Muhely Egyesület	n/a	MagosVölgy Ökológiai Gazdaság
Italy	UnSacco, pieni di grani antichi	Azienda agricola Zordan Tiziano	Toscanatura Bio	Tularù Società Agricola
Portugal	Quinta dos 7 Nomes CRL	Terra bio Lda	n/a	Quinta do Arneiro
Sweden	n/a	Boställets vedugnsbageri	Artisan Bread AB	n/a
Switzerland	Biohof Las Sorts+ Bergkartoffln aus dem Albulatal	Verein Erlebniswelt Roggen Erschmatt	n/a	AGRIDEA

Table 56. Selected case studies

6.4 Challenges for valuing NUCs in food environments

As part of the survey, we asked respondents to reflect upon the challenges that they faced in producing, processing and selling NUCs up and down their value chains. The largest challenges that were reported were the following (see Q6.3 to Q6.9 sections for more details):

Challenge	Value Chain Activity
Unfavourable agronomic conditions	Production
Unavailability of seeds	Production
Lack of integrated cropping systems	Production
Lack of organic inputs	Production
Lack of markets/Insufficient demand	Production, Processing, Selling
Physical qualities	Processing, Selling
Organoleptic qualities	Processing, Selling
Lack of tasty recipes	Processing, Selling
Too much competition among products	Selling
Lack of consumer awareness	Selling
Lack of consumer knowledge of how to cook them	Selling
Limited product range	Selling

Table 57. Value chain challenges for NUCs

With regard to the responses received about how to overcome these challenges (Q6.5, 6.8 and 6.11 of the questionnaire), we see a number of interesting trends, according to the different types of values chains. We summarize these in the following sections.

Figure 14. Overcome production challenge

Figure 15. Overcome process challenges

Figure 16. Overcome selling challenges

6.4.1 Active promoters' responses

The responses provided by the group of initiatives that represent the "active promoters" value chains are in line with their focus on product quality and the formalised link between producers and consumers, embodied in the use of guarantee schemes. These initiatives also represent the highest number of responses to the question about value chain challenges. For example, in response to production challenges, these initiatives propose providing more information to consumers on healthier diets, better promotion of products and nutritional and

environmental/biodiversity benefits. They also favour public policy support for organic farmers and breeding improvements.

In response to the processing challenges, in these initiatives there is a focus on technical protocols, economic support, incentivising production and sale, as well as significant support for producers, particularly organic producers. They show a wealth of ideas on how to overcome the selling challenges, focused again on working with consumers to understand the positive effects on human health. They propose a number of initiatives with youth and schools to introduce early the benefits of this type of food. Support for organic production is again mentioned.

6.4.2 Silent sellers' responses

The silent sellers suggest engaging in more collaboration and contact among farmers so to provide support for selection, sharing harvesting tools, and attaining lower costs by organise bulk purchases and consolidate to a single supplier. For food processing challenges, they suggest collaboration with small-scale companies and direct marketers. Support for processing investment and a shift to focusing on quality is also suggested. Reducing the quantity of imported low-cost, low-quality products or ensure that they are easily identifiable as being of lower quality (which is not very respectful of the environment and producers) was found as a suggestion in this group. There is also a call for favourable pricing policies and marketing support to increase the consumer understanding of being part of a food system. The responses from these initiatives are very much in line with the nature of their value chain relations focusing on maintaining longer chains that do not actively communicate the qualities of NUCs.

6.4.3 Quality communicators' responses

The quality communicators are very closely aligned with all of the responses from the active promoters' actors. In the above displayed maps, their clusters are even embedded within the active promoters' clusters. The quality communicators insist on farmers' freedom to choose to produce NUCs, but they are seeking more information about the characteristics of typical/local production, the choice of seeds and the higher prices for producers. The concerns for the qualities that are communicated transparently from producers to consumers, show that providing support to the producers for dealing with production risks and properties in the genetic population will help them to alleviate processing difficulties. Consumer information is the main response from this group, particularly about the importance of promoting more informed choices by consumers through different media. The lack of knowledge about NUCs is seen as the key challenge for selling them.

6.4.4 Mission first responses

The mission first initiatives are the most engaged in their direct relationships with the producers. They suggest that practical demonstrations, knowledge exchange, the use of certified seeds and cultivation technologies can resolve many challenges. Innovation is key for the producers of NUCs and the associations in this group focus on providing technical assistance for biodiversity conservation. For the processing concerns, reduction of competition between artisans and greater knowledge sharing among professionals is the way to go. They suggest having more recipes for NUCs available and communicated within the agri-food industry. For the selling challenges, they claim that despite excellent intentions, there is some lack of knowledge in terms of financial management among producers/artisans of processed products. They also lament the small

volumes available. They suggest increasing the quality standards and lowering prices as a way to increase awareness.

6.5 Benefits perceived from the sale/valorisation of NUCS

As part of the survey, we also asked respondents to explain the different benefits they derived from the sale or promotion of NUCS, from an environmental, cultural, economic, social and/or political point of view (see Q5.10 section for more details). The number of benefits perceived by the initiatives was used as a variable to determine the typology. In this part, we look more closely at the types of benefits received and at the explanations of what these benefits mean (Q5.11 to Q5.15). The 5 figures below provide an overview of which benefits were received from the promotion of sales of NUCS.

Figure 17. Overview of the environmental benefits of selling/valuing NUCS expressed by the 4 clusters

Figure 18. Overview of the cultural benefits of selling/valuing NUCS expressed by the 4 clusters

Figure 19. Overview of the economic benefits of selling/valuing NUCS expressed by the 4 clusters

Figure 20. Overview of the social benefits of selling/valuing NUCS expressed by the 4 clusters

Figure 21. Overview of the political benefits of selling/valuing NUCS expressed by the 4 clusters

6.5.1 Active promoters' responses

As detailed in section 6.2 and illustrated by the figures, active promoters is the cluster that has reported the greatest number of benefits resulting from the sales or promotion of NUCS, with high proportions of initiatives having selected each type of benefits.

In terms of environmental benefits (n=16 initiatives), initiatives of this cluster put forward positive impact on biodiversity, on (local) ecosystems, the use of more sustainable, agroecological or organic practises, with the use of more adapted varieties to the territory and for which yield maximization is not the primary goal.

For cultural benefits (n=11 initiatives), this is the only cluster that talk about the preservation of gastronomic heritage (maintain the knowledge of the use of different varieties in the kitchen, maintenance of the communities' food identity...). Preserving/valorisation of traditional cultivation methods is also expressed. NUCs are also perceived as a mean to create a link between producers and consumers and to valorise product (strong bond; People better understand the value of local food culture and history as well as the job of farmer and bread making; Food education; product valorisation).

From an economical point of view (n=10 initiatives), NUCS are perceived as a niche product and with added-value (more added value; additional value for the production of small farmers; some consumers are buyers for this reason alone; Niche production with history). They allow to increase income especially for small initiatives (creating financial sustainability; Increases our income through a holistic concept; makes it possible to make a crop viable on a small area, through the valorization of products and transformation; direct financing of small sustainable producers).

From a social point of view (n=13 initiatives), NUCs are perceived as a way to raise awareness of consumers (Contribution to connect people with agricultural tradition; Consumers understand and adhere more to our peasant approach.; Popularize healthy products; Food education; People are more careful to health and balanced diet, and have a higher sensitivity to biodiversity and environment) Supporting local economy (supporting local producers by creating sustainable financial networks; mitigation of the depopulation of towns and countryside; decent income for the producer, for the consumer no intermediary) and network creation allowing seeds and knowledge exchange are also expressed (Varieties are exchanged; knowledge is passed on; Do not use new and modified seeds outside of their origin, avoid imports).

From a political point of view (n=7 initiatives), they expressed mainly the benefit of gaining their independence from the seed industry (strengthen independence from seed industry and patent; food self-determination of communities and less dependence on multinationals and globalized trade systems; we are independent for the production of our seeds). Again, NUCS can create better awareness (better political awareness; Political initiatives on the subject of agriculture can make a visible difference to people; increase awareness and make more people aware of the importance of agrobiodiversity).

6.5.2 Silent sellers' responses

Cluster 2 is the one that express the least benefits from the sale or promotion of NUCS. For those that do, it's the environmental benefit that is the most widely received.

For the environmental aspects (n=15 initiatives), initiatives of this cluster put also forward mainly positive impacts on biodiversity. They said that NUCS are produced organically or with more sustainable practices, adapted to crop rotations, preserving soils (Soil fertility can also be improved; nitrogen via legume crops), that are more adapted (have good competition against wild plants; adaptability of mixtures; requiring no fertilization (not require fertilization but only rotations with intercropped green manures). Contrary to the other clusters, they also put forward the small-scale production conditions and their short chain organisation (produced and distributed locally in a short circuit; local product; local products, limited unnecessary transport).

Cultural benefits expressed (n=6 initiatives), deal mainly with the preservation of the traditional crops/culture. Promotion of local territory, a way to demonstrate another way to grow and eat and a mean to pick up interest of consumers are also ideas that was expressed.

Better income is expressed as the main economic benefit (better agricultural income; considerable part of our income; fairer remuneration for the producer; Revenue; require fewer technical means to grow them). Diversification of products, seed autonomy and local economy are also expressed (n=6 initiatives).

For social benefits (n=4 initiatives), NUCS allowed to connect consumers with producers, help creating network of people aware of the problems of loss of diversity in food and the consumption of healthier products.

From a political point of view, two benefits were justified: 1) independence from industry and food standardization, and 2) producing food to maintain soil quality and people's health, creating networks of help and support and ethical consumption.

6.5.3 Quality communicators' responses

Sellers in this cluster have mostly expressed cultural and environmental benefits (social and political benefits were not selected in this group).

Environmental benefits (n=9 initiatives) deal mainly with better/good production for the environment (agronomics benefits; it's better; No agrochemicals; avoiding inputs, e.g. einkorn spelt does not require external inputs). Biodiversity, adaptation to organic agriculture, the promotion of crop rotation, and the transition to a more plant-based diet were also quoted.

From a cultural point of view (n=8 initiatives), NUCS have the advantage of preserving cultural and genetic heritage (Continuity of the peasant act; Preservation of cultural heritage; Maintains know-how; Safeguarding genetic heritage) and is a way to raise awareness of consumers on production aspects (the opportunity is created to talk about how and what was cultivated until the advent of modern agriculture; we try to build up more consciousness in the consumer; Discussions on practices that offer another production model. Sharing a common ideal that brings people together). The transition to a more plant-based diet was also quoted.

From an economical point of view (n=2 initiatives), NUCS create local economies and allow more attractive selling prices.

6.5.4 Mission first responses

Like the active promoters' cluster, mission first initiatives also declared a high number of benefits from the sale or promotion of NUCS, mainly environmental, economic and social.

From an environmental point of view (n=11 initiatives), the following advantages were expressed: preservation of soils (Preservation of agricultural soils; Increase of the organic matter in the soil; improve soil quality), production that is better for the environment (Producers whose environmental methods are virtuous find new outlets and increase their production; preserve the environment ; I don't burden the environment with chemicals; are looking actively for species and varieties that can be grown under low input organic conditions - enabling us to have environmentally low impact farming methods), they are favourable to crop rotation (legumes are favourable in the crop rotation); bringing biodiversity was also quoted and adapted to climate change.

Those who selected the cultural benefits (n=5 initiatives) emphasize that NUCS helps to create link with the consumers or with the local environment (More people at our events; Growing a wide variety of crops makes us an interesting partner with art/ cultural and gastronomic projects; participation in the breeding of wheat in the field; producer/consumer meeting, sharing the responsibility for a better environment).

Lots of different economic benefits (n=9 initiatives) emerged from this group. NUCS allow differentiation (Our products are unique and valuable to our consumers, we don't really have competition in the region); are added-value products (The value of a good quality ecological product is higher; Increasing the value of wheat); allows to attract consumers (More customers across all of our activities); favouring short chains (The cooperative sells more to its members and buys more from its suppliers. Consumers benefit from our unique low margin system and the non-profit purpose of the structure); imply consumers (Customer and turnover contribution); revitalize and allow sale of national products; provide a good gross margin and great regularity of yield.

From a social point of view (n=8 initiatives), NUCS allows to build networks and social links (Social link between producers, amateur gardeners, researchers of the association; More solidarity in our initiatives; Our activities attract a large number of dedicated supporters and volunteers, strengthening the community embeddedness of our farm; Social connection, mutual aid, neighbourhood atmosphere; Creating a community; Contact between consumers and producers). Production of healthy food is also expressed.

For political benefits (n=4 initiatives), NUCS seems to be a way to mobilise citizen and stakeholders (More citizen coherence; Dissemination of environmental, economic, social and therefore political issues among all stakeholders; Creating a local community aware of the importance of the protection of the landscape). Transition toward less meat was also quoted.

The insights from these responses serve two purposes in our analysis. First, the challenges and benefits expressed by our respondents confirm the analytical value of clustering the initiatives according to these four types of value chains, coherent in their approaches to transparency about communicating values and their proposals for increasing the benefits that can be gained from NUCs in marketing. Second, these two parts provide greater insights into key aspects of value chain organisation that might highlight those initiatives that are able to create greater benefits for agrobiodiversity in food environments.

6.6 Building SMART Indexes from the findings

The work on building SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound) indexes is being carried out across all WPs in DIVINFOOD. The objective of the work in WP1 is to identify a set of indicators that will point to the value that is being created for NUCs in food environments (SMART Indexes for agrobiodiversity use in marketing).

The analytical work that was carried out to date has identified a number of key data points that could serve to indicate the value of agrobiodiversity for those actors who are selling NUCs.

What we present below is a very first set of indexes that emerged from our literature reviews on food environments and value chains, and our own original empirical analysis of valuing NUCs in current food environments.

Indexes	What does it indicate?	What is being measured?	How to measure?
Differentiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That sellers who value agrobiodiversity are gaining a competitive marketing advantage because they can differentiate themselves from those sellers who only offer mainstream, conventional crop-based products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The benefits gained from offering difficult to find products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NUCs as share of sales Number of different NUCs offered
Consumer loyalty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That a loyal consumer base is being created because there is a class of consumers who actively seek out agrobiodiversity-based products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ability to attract consumers and ensure that they return 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of repeat consumers Percentage of daily & weekly consumers

Fair prices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That agrobiodiversity can create a fairer distribution of value for producers, intermediaries and consumers compared to products made from mainstream, conventional crops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The profit margins retained for the seller from NUCs • The fairness of prices for consumers • The fairness of prices for producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of profit margin for the seller as compared to non-NUCs based products • Level of price received by the producer as compared to non-NUCs based products • Level of price paid by the consumer as compared to non-NUCs based products
Value chain upgrading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That chains valuing agrobiodiversity in food environments offer producers greater opportunities to add value to their operations by diversifying their income and contributing to the local economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The upgrading of value chain activities by producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of producers who are selling NUCs-based products directly to consumers in a given territory
Environmental activism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That marketing agrobiodiversity enables the sellers to participate in the social movements that aim to protect the environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The perceived environmental benefits gained by sellers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of social media posts about the environment, as part of all social media posts • Percentage of environmental benefits claims, as a share of all benefits claims made by the seller in their marketing

Table 58. SMART indexes for agrobiodiversity use in marketing

This first set of indexes will be shared with project partners as inputs to tasks in other work packages, particularly the GxE database in WP5. In WP1, we will work with the agrobiodiversity use criteria and begin to test them with consumers in order to create final SMART indexes for valuing agrobiodiversity in food environments.

7. Conclusions

In this deliverable, our aim was to explore the ways in which short- and mid-tier value chains in the DIVINFOOD partner countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden and Switzerland) might successfully value NUCs in a food environment that generally does not make this valorisation easy, neither for the initiatives themselves, nor for the citizen-consumers. Besides a deep analysis of such food value chains, our goal was to create a typology of these chains in order to assist us - partners of the project and anyone who wishes to set up such chains - in building initiatives that can successfully market NUCs. The insights that we gained in this study allowed us to create a first, tentative list of SMART indexes that will be experimented over the next few years as the DIVINFOOD partners develop new marketing strategies and channels. Specific work with digital tools dedicated to valuing (agro)biodiversity-use will be carried out in Tasks 1.3 and 1.4 of the projects. The analysis in this paper will also aid Work Package 5 of the project in developing new business models. The data collected in this study will also be integrated with the GxE database that is being developed for the Living Labs and the SMART Indexes will also be adapted in the work with the GxE database.

As discussed throughout the report, in our research, we built on the literature review submitted in D1.3 on enabling food environments, and then conducted another literature review - presented in Section 2 of the present Deliverable - on food value chains. To contextualise the NUC environment in which the presented value chains operate, we collected and analysed the - primarily production - data of NUC legumes and ancient grains involved in the project in the participating countries - as presented in Section 3. We then built a database of more than 1,200 initiatives that deal with NUCs, conducted an online survey - as presented in our Survey methodology chapter in Section 4. The analysis of our survey resulted in striking similarities between the various countries, with the majority of differences found between the different actor types, and we found that NUCs are currently being valued in environments not very well suited for their promotion - as presented in Section 5. Based on our survey analysis, we identified four main clusters of initiative-types, which we have called 1) Active promoters, 2) Silent sellers, 3) Quality communicators and 4) Mission first initiatives. In Section 6, we discussed these types in detail, together with case studies from all partner countries to highlight the key differences between the various types of value chains.

Drawing on the overall analysis, we have been able to highlight a number of key results explaining how cereals and legumes NUCS are currently valorised in different food environments across Europe.

In line with other work on short and mid-tier food chains, we found that our sample of initiatives valuing agrobiodiversity, present varied and often multiple activity profiles. The majority of them (44.8%), are involved in an « agricultural activity » - of varying size and governance types - with many of them also involved in processing activities (such as baking, milling). These are then followed in frequency by shops (21.8%), intermediaries (CSA and online platforms, 14.1%), processors (10.3%) and other specific activities (8.9%, which include seed companies, agrobiodiversity conservation associations, private research and extension). The majority of initiatives are rather young, having been founded in or after 2011 (65.4%).

Although we have identified some initiatives, which are highly specialised in NUCs, overall, NUCs represent a small proportion of the activity of the initiatives that we surveyed (less than 25% for 58.9% of the initiatives). In general, they deal with only one or two categories of NUCs (73.1%). Initiatives dealing solely with cereals are the most numerous (50%), followed by those mixing cereals and pulses (35.9%), while initiatives dealing solely with legumes are less frequent (n=10, 12.8%); with wheat category being the most cited cereals NUCs and lentils, peas, common beans, chickpeas for legumes.

The study of supply and sales chains of the initiatives showed that most of these initiatives are short value chains (a large part of the sample is made up of direct (and own producer for supply) or hybrid direct/short supply and sales chains) that are territorially anchored, with mainly one single location site for the initiative (61.5%). However, the declared origins of NUCs suggest that these short supply chains rely upon regional or even national chains, rather than on the municipality level. Furthermore, we observed a wide variety of modalities of sourcing and selling NUCs suggesting that diversity in supply and marketing channels is a core strategy.

Looking at the types of contracts established for the supply of NUCS, the proportion of 'binding' contracts is lower and the results suggest that NUCs related activities are not significant enough in terms of sales to warrant entering into long term agreements among supply chain actors. Instead, one's own production is often sufficient and purchasing on demand is feasible based on non-contractual relationships between the retailers and the producers. Additionally, this is also a sector that is characterised by experimentation and seed exchanges, which means that the social engagement goes beyond pure market exchanges.

The sampled initiatives position themselves primarily around environmental concerns. The social missions are concerned more with the model of agriculture that is unfair to both the agroecosystems and farmers, than with the nutritional benefits of NUCs. The sector relies heavily on organic certification and the perceived benefits from selling NUCs are mainly environmental.

Regarding the communication aspects, there is no major difference in patterns when the initiatives promote NUCs or when they communicate more generally about their initiative. However, more than a quarter of initiatives (28.2%) do not actively promote NUCS. Online platforms and word of mouth are the most often used promoting approaches. They also tend to use fewer forms of communication for NUCs than for their general communication. Sales point displays are rarely used (10.3%) and about half of the initiatives do additional promotional activities (such as talk/speeches). Again, the majority of those promoting NUCs do so on the environmental aspects, but health-related messages are more frequently selected for quality communication. The NUCs sellers have a rather loyal customer base.

Regarding the challenges of producing, processing or selling NUCS, the challenges of insufficient demand and lack of consumer awareness emerged as the most critical.

Together these results lead us to conclude that NUCs are currently being valued in food environments that are not very well suited for their promotion, with the lack of demand for these products remaining the main problem.

8. References

- Agnoletti, M., & Santoro, A. (2022). Agricultural heritage systems and agrobiodiversity. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1-11.
- Amaya, N., Padulosi, S., & Meldrum, G. (2020). Value chain analysis of chaya (Mayan spinach) in Guatemala. *Economic Botany*, 74(1), 100-114.
- Andreotti, F., Bazile, D., Biaggi, C., Callo-Concha, D., Jacquet, J., Jemal, O. M., ... & Van Noordwijk, M. (2022). When neglected species gain global interest: Lessons learned from quinoa's boom and bust for teff and minor millet. *Global Food Security*, 32, 100613.
- Andorfer, V. & Liebe, U. (2012) Research on fair trade consumption—A review. *Journal of Business Ethics* 106(4): 415-435.
- Arfini, F., Amilien, V., Antonioli, F., Bellassen, V., Brennan, M., Fumel, M., Gorton, M., Hartmann, M., Hawes, D. R., Mancini, M. C., Roos, G., Schüssler, J., Tocco, B., Torjusen, H., Tregear, A., Veneziani, M., Vitterso, G. & Yeh, C. 2016. Strengthening European Food Chain Sustainability by Quality and Procurement Policy. Working paper on the conceptual framework and literature review for understanding the social, environmental and economic impact of FQS, SFSC and varying PSFP policies on agri-food chain participants and rural territories. Parma: Università degli Studi di Parma. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01630638>
- Augère-Granier M.-L. (2016) Short food supply chains and local food systems in the EU. *Briefing*. Brussels, Belgium: European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS).
- Bair, J. (2009) *Frontiers of commodity chain research*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Baird, I. G. (2022). Political violence, migration, lack of citizenship, and agrobiodiversity loss in the borderlands of Thailand and Laos. *Geoforum*, 128, 263-275.
- Baldermann, S., Blagojević, L., Frede, K., Klopsch, R., Neugart, S., Neumann, A., ... & Schreiner, M. (2016). Are neglected plants the food for the future?. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 35(2), 106-119.
- Barstow, C., Mukiibi, E., & Zocchi, D. M. (2021). Slow food and NUS: Protecting and promoting endangered food products. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 216-224). Routledge.
- Batur, F., Bocci, R., & Bartha, B. (2021). Marketing farmers' varieties in Europe: Encouraging pathways with missing links for the recognition and support of farmer seed systems. *Agronomy*, 11(11), 2159.
- Bingen, R.J. & Busch, L. (2006) *Agricultural standards: the shape of the global food and fiber system*. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Bogliotti, C., Calabrese, G., El Bilali, H., Rae, I., Platzer, M., Marino, M., ... & Kiene, T. (2021). Voices from the agencies: research for development (R4D) agencies supporting efforts to conserve and promote the sustainable use of NUS. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 365-384). Routledge.
- Boltanski, L. & Thévenot, L. (2006 [1991]) *On justification: Economies of worth*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Borelli, T., Beltrame, D., Wasike, V. W., Samarasinghe, G., Tan, A., & Hunter, D. (2021). The BFN mainstreaming toolkit. A roadmap to using neglected and underutilized species for food system change. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 163-173). Routledge.

- Borelli, T., Hunter, D., Padulosi, S., Amaya, N., Meldrum, G., de Oliveira Beltrame, D. M., ... & Tartanac, F. (2020). Local solutions for sustainable food systems: The contribution of orphan crops and wild edible species. *Agronomy*, 10(2), 231.
- Brenton, S. (2018) (Political) Consumers and certification schemes: The ethics of global production and trade. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 31(6): 755-784.
- Bullock, G. & van der Ven, H. (2020) The Shadow of the Consumer: Analyzing the Importance of Consumers to the Uptake and Sophistication of Ratings, Certifications, and Eco-Labels. *Organization and Environment* 33(1): 75-95.
- Caetano, C. M., Cuellar, R. D. P., Juajibioy, J. L. M., Ávila, L. N. V., Nunes, D. G. C., & de Pazdiora, B. R. C. N. (2015). Participatory breeding: tool for conservation of neglected and underutilised crops. *Acta Agronómica*.
- Callon, M., Méadel, C. & Rabeharisoa, V. (2002) The Economy of Qualities. *Economy and Society* 31(2): 194-217.
- Camacho-Henriquez, A., Kraemer, F., Galluzzi, G., Haan, S. D., Jäger, M., & Christinck, A. (2015). Decentralized collaborative plant breeding for utilization and conservation of neglected and underutilised crop genetic resources. In *Advances in plant breeding strategies: breeding, biotechnology and molecular tools* (pp. 25-61). Springer, Cham.
- Campanaro, A., Tommasi, N., Guzzetti, L., Galimberti, A., Bruni, I., & Labra, M. (2019). DNA barcoding to promote social awareness and identity of neglected, underutilised plant species having valuable nutritional properties. *Food Research International*, 115, 1-9.
- Carrera, L. (2009) I Gruppi di Acquisto Solidale. Una protesta solida nella società liquida. . *Partecipazione e Conflitto* 3: 95-122.
- Carrington, M., Chatzidakis, A., Goworek, H. & Shaw, D. (2020) Consumption Ethics: A Review and Analysis of Future Directions for Interdisciplinary Research. *Journal of Business Ethics*. DOI: 10.1007/s10551-020-04425-4.
- Caspi, C. E., Sorensen, G., Subramanian, S. V., & Kawachi, I. (2012). The local food environment and diet: a systematic review. *Health & place*, 18(5), 1172-1187.
- Chable, V., Nuijten, E., Costanzo, A., Goldringer, I., Bocci, R., Oehen, B., ... & Rossi, A. (2020). Embedding cultivated diversity in society for agro-ecological transition. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 784.
- Cavazzani, A., Gaudio, G. & Sivini, S. (2006) Politiche, governance e innovazione per le aree rurali. Napoli: INEA-ESI.
- Chiffolleau, Y. (2008) Les circuits courts de commercialisation en agriculture : diversité et enjeux pour le développement durable. In Maréchal G. (eds), *Les circuits courts alimentaires*, Dijon, Educagri.
- Chiffolleau, Y., Darrot, C., & Maréchal G. (2020). *Manger au temps du coronavirus Enquête sur nos systèmes alimentaires*. Apogée, 160 p.
- Chiffolleau, Y. & Dourian, T. (2020) Sustainable Food Supply Chains: Is Shortening the Answer? A Literature Review for a Research and Innovation Agenda. *Sustainability* 12(23): 9831.
- Chiffolleau, Y. & Loconto, A.M. (2018) Social Innovation in Agriculture and Food: Old Wine in New Bottles? *The International Journal of Sociology of Agriculture and Food* 24(3): 306-317.
- Chkanikova, O. (2016) Sustainable Purchasing in Food Retailing: Inter organisational Relationship Management to Green Product Supply. *Business Strategy and the Environment* 25(7): 478-494.

- Chkanikova, O. & Lehner, M. (2015) Private eco-brands and green market development: Towards new forms of sustainability governance in the food retailing. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 107: 74-84.
- Christopher, M. (2023). *Logistics and supply chain management* (Sixth Edition. ed.). Hoboken, NJ: Pearson.
- Cochoy, F. (2010) 'How to build displays that sell'. *Journal of Cultural Economy* 3(2): 299-315.
- Collins, J.L. & Kahn, W.N. (2017) The hijacking of a new corporate form? Benefit corporations and corporate personhood. *Economy and Society*. DOI: 10.1080/03085147.2016.1239342. 1-25.
- Conroy, M.E. (2007) *Branded! How the 'Certification Revolution' Is Transforming Global Corporations*. Gabriola Island, BC: New Society Publishers.
- Da Cunha, M. A., Paraguassú, L. A. A., Assis, J. G. D. A., Silva, A. B. D. P. C., & Cardoso, R. D. C. V. (2020). Urban gardening and neglected and underutilised species in Salvador, Bahia, Brazil. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*, 16(1), 1-16.
- Darr, D., Chopi-Msadala, C., Namakhwa, C. D., Meinhold, K., & Munthali, C. (2020). Processed baobab (*Adansonia digitata* L.) food products in malawi: from poor men's to premium-priced specialty food? *Forests*, 11(6), 698.
- de Bakker, F.G.A., Rasche, A. & Ponte, S. (2019) Multi-Stakeholder Initiatives on Sustainability: A Cross-Disciplinary Review and Research Agenda for Business Ethics. *Business Ethics Quarterly* 29(3): 343-383.
- De Boef, W.S., Subedi, A., Peroni, N., Thijssen, M., & O'Keeffe, E. (Eds.). (2013). *Community Biodiversity Management: Promoting resilience and the conservation of plant genetic resources*. Routledge.
- Dinsa, F.F., Stoilova, T., Nenguwo, N., Aloyce, A., Tenkouano, A., Hanson, P., & Keatinge, J. D. H. (2015). Traditional vegetables: improvement and development in sub-Saharan Africa at AVRDC-The World Vegetable Center. *Acta Horticulturae*, 1102, 21-28.
- Dixon, J. (1999) A cultural economy model for studying food systems. *Agriculture and Human Values* 16(2): 151-160.
- Drugova, T., Curtis, K.R. & Akhundjanov, S.B. (2020) Are multiple labels on food products beneficial or simply ignored? *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics* 68(4): 411-427.
- Dubuisson-Quellier, S. & Lamine, C. (2004) Faire le marché autrement. L'abonnement à un panier de fruits et de légumes comme forme d'engagement politique des consommateurs. *Sciences de la Société* (62): 144-167.
- DuPuis, E.M. & Goodman, D. (2005) Should we go "home" to eat?: toward a reflexive politics of localism. *Journal of Rural Studies* 21(3): 359-371.
- FAO (2014) *Developing sustainable food value chains. Guiding principles*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, et al. (2020) *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2020. Transforming food systems for affordable healthy diets*. Rome, FAO. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Feenstra, G. & Hardesty, S. (2016) Values-based supply chains as a strategy for supporting small and mid-scale producers in the United States. *Agriculture* 6(3): 39.
- Feng, J., Glass, T. A., Curriero, F. C., Stewart, W. F., & Schwartz, B. S. (2010). The built environment and obesity: a systematic review of the epidemiologic evidence. *Health & place*, 16(2), 175-190.

- Fold, N. & Larsen, M.N. (2008) *Globalization and Restructuring of African Commodity Flows*. Uppsala, Sweden: Nodiska Afrikainstitutet
- Fouilleux, E. & Loconto, A (2017) Voluntary standards, certification, and accreditation in the global organic agriculture field: a tripartite model of techno-politics. *Agriculture and Human Values* 34(1): 1-14.
- Freidberg, S.E. (2004) *French beans and food scares: culture and commerce in an anxious age*. New York, N.Y.: Oxford University Press.
- Friedland, W.H. (1984) Commodity systems analysis: An approach to the sociology of agriculture. In: Schwarzweiler HK (ed) *Research in Rural Sociology and Development*. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, pp.221–235.
- Galt, R., O'Sullivan, L., Beckett, J., & Hiner, C. (2012). Community supported agriculture is thriving in the Central Valley. *California Agriculture*, 66(1), 8-14.
- Garrido-Garza, F., Loconto, A. & Robinson, D. (2024) Market formation for short food supply chains in the context of transformative social innovation. *Journal of Rural Studies* (under review)
- Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J., & Sturgeon, T. (2005) The governance of global value chains. *Review of International Political Economy* 12(1): 78 - 104.
- Gereffi, G. & Korzeniewicz, M. (1994) *Commodity chains and global capitalism*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Gibbon, P. & Ponte, S. (2005) *Trading down: Africa, value chains, and the global economy*. Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.
- Giuliani, A., Padulosi, S., & Hoeschle-Zeledon, I. (2004, August). Linking rural communities'livelihoods with markets of underutilised species: Case study in syria. In *XV International Symposium on Horticultural Economics and Management* 655 (pp. 297-306).
- Girard, F., & Frison, C. (2018). Introduction: Commoning the seeds: The future of agrobiodiversity and food security. In *The Commons, Plant Breeding and Agricultural Research* (pp. 1-20). Routledge.
- Giuliani, A. (2012). *Developing markets for agrobiodiversity: Securing livelihoods in dryland areas*. Routledge.
- Goodman, D. (2003) The quality 'turn' and alternative food practices: reflections and agenda. *Journal of Rural Studies* 19(1): 1-7.
- Granheim, S. I., Løvhaug, A. L., Terragni, L., Torheim, L. E., & Thurston, M. (2022). Mapping the digital food environment: A systematic scoping review. *Obesity Reviews*, 23(1), e13356.
- Gustafson, A., Hankins, S., & Jilcott, S. (2012). Measures of the consumer food store environment: a systematic review of the evidence 2000–2011. *Journal of community health*, 37(4), 897-911.
- Harris, J., Van Zonneveld, M., Achigan-Dako, E. G., Bajwa, B., Brouwer, I. D., Choudhury, D., De Jager, I., De Steenhuijsen Piters, B., Dulloo, M. E. & Guarino, L. (2022). Fruit and vegetable biodiversity for nutritionally diverse diets: Challenges, opportunities, and knowledge gaps. *Global Food Security*, 33, 100618.
- Hebinck, A., Vervoort, J. M., Hebinck, P., Rutting, L. & Galli, F. (2018) Imagining transformative futures: participatory foresight for food systems change. *Ecology and Society* 23(2).
- Hebinck, P., Schneider, S. & van der Ploeg, J.D. (2014) *Rural Development and the Construction of New Markets*. Taylor & Francis.
- Hermann, M., Kwek, M. J., Khoo, T. K., & Amaya, K. (2011, June). Collective action towards enhanced knowledge management of neglected and underutilised species: Making use of Internet

- opportunities. In *II International Symposium on Underutilised Plant Species: Crops for the Future-Beyond Food Security 979* (pp. 65-77).
- Hernández-Gómez, M.S. (2009, July). Little-known tropical fruits: use and perspectives. In *International Conference on Postharvest and Quality Management of Horticultural Products of Interest for Tropical Regions 906* (pp. 109-113).
- Hoeschle-Zeledon, I., & Jaenicke, H. (2006, December). A strategic framework for global research and development of underutilised plant species: a contribution to the enhancement of indigenous vegetables and legumes. In *I International Conference on Indigenous Vegetables and Legumes. Prospectus for Fighting Poverty, Hunger and Malnutrition 752* (pp. 103-110).
- Hunter, D., Borelli, T., Beltrame, D. M., Oliveira, C. N., Coradin, L., Wasike, V. W., ... & Tartanac, F. (2019). The potential of neglected and underutilised species for improving diets and nutrition. *Planta*, 250(3), 709-729.
- Hunter, D., Roskrige, N., Semese, S. A., Clarke, P., & Turpin, G. (2021). Neglected and underutilized species and indigenous foodways of Oceania. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 147-160). Routledge.
- Islam, M.S. (2008) From pond to plate: Towards a twin-driven commodity chain in Bangladesh shrimp aquaculture. *Food Policy* 33(3): 209-223.
- Jaeger, M., Giuliani, A., & van Loosen, I. (2017). Markets, consumer demand and agricultural biodiversity. In *Routledge Handbook of Agricultural Biodiversity* (pp. 482-496). Routledge.
- Janssen, M. & Hamm, U. (2014) Governmental and private certification labels for organic food: Consumer attitudes and preferences in Germany. *Food Policy* 49, Part 2(0): 437-448.
- Johns, T., & Eyzaguirre, P. B. (2006). Linking biodiversity, diet and health in policy and practice. *Proceedings of the nutrition society*, 65(2), 182-189.
- Jones, S. K., Estrada-Carmona, N., Juventia, S. D., Dulloo, M. E., Laporte, M. A., Villani, C., & Remans, R. (2021). Agrobiodiversity Index scores show agrobiodiversity is underutilised in national food systems. *Nature Food*, 2(9), 712-723.
- Jordan, N. R., Dorn, K., Runck, B., Ewing, P., Williams, A., Anderson, K., Felice, L., Haralson, K., Goplen, J. & Altendorf, K. (2016). Sustainable commercialization of new crops for the agricultural bioeconomy Sustainable commercialization of new bioeconomy crops. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene*, 4.
- Juventia, S. D., Jones, S. K., Laporte, M. A., Remans, R., Villani, C., & Estrada-Carmona, N. (2020). Text mining national commitments towards agrobiodiversity conservation and use. *Sustainability*, 12(2), 715.
- Kimura, A. H. (2021). Pickles and agrobiodiversity: a foodway and traditional vegetable varieties in Japan. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 38(4), 1079-1096.
- King, E. O., Muniappan, K., Parida, P. K., Mishra, S., Natarajan, K., Nongrum, M. S., Chinnadurai, M., Rangad, C. O., Roy, S. & Meldrum, G. (2021). Community-centred value-chain development of nutri-millet: Challenges and best practices in India. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 245-262). Routledge.
- Kliem, L., & Wolter, H. (2022). How do consumers perceive open-source seed licenses? Exploring a new credence attribute. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*.
- Kneafsey, M., Venn, L., Schmutz, U., Balázs, B., Trenchard, L., Eyden-Wood, T., Bos, E., Foster, G. & Blackett, M. (2013) *Short Food Supply Chains and Local Food Systems in the EU. A State of Play of their Socio-Economic Characteristics*.
- Kropp, C., Antoni-Komar, I. & Sage, C. (2020) *Food System Transformations: Social Movements, Local Economies, Collaborative Networks*. Taylor & Francis.

- Law, J. (1991) Power, discretion and strategy. In: Law J (ed) *A Sociology of Monsters: Essays on Power, Technology and Domination*. London: Routledge, pp.165-191.
- Li, X., & Siddique, K. H. (2020). Future Smart Food: Harnessing the potential of neglected and underutilised species for Zero Hunger. *Maternal & child nutrition*, 16, e13008.
- Li, X., Yadav, R., & Siddique, K. H. (2020). Neglected and underutilised crop species: the key to improving dietary diversity and fighting hunger and malnutrition in Asia and the Pacific. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 7, 593711.
- Liyanagamage, T. M., De Silva, D. A. M., Karunaratne, A. S., O'Reilly, P., & Nilmalgoda, H. (2017, April). Value chain analysis of underutilised crops of different farming systems in Sri Lanka. In *IV International Conference on Postharvest and Quality Management of Horticultural Products of Interest for Tropical Regions 1278* (pp. 179-184).
- Lochetti, G. (2021). Development of seasonal calendars for sustainable diets—experiences from Guatemala, Mali and India. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 174-181). Routledge.
- Loconto, A. (2012). Value Chains and Chains of Values: Tracing Tanzanian Tea. In F. Arfini (Ed.), *Local Agri-Food Systems in a Global World: Market, Social and Environmental Challenges* (pp. 195-214). Newcastle upon Tyne, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Loconto, A. (2017) Models of Assurance: Diversity and Standardization of Modes of Intermediation. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 670(1): 1-21.
- Loconto, A. & Busch, L. (2010) Standards, techno-economic networks, and playing fields: Performing the global market economy. *Review of International Political Economy* 17(3): 507 - 536.
- Loconto, A., & Garrido-Garza, F. (2021). Formal and informal European quality assurance initiatives offering a connection between local gastronomy and small-scale farmers. Paris: LISIS for AgriKulti and Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture. Retrieved from <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-03173144>
- Loconto, A., Garrido-Garza, F., & Dufeu, I. (2023). Innovations for Sustainable Food Systems: Focusing on Agroecology and Participatory Guarantee Systems. *Journal of Rural Problems*, 59(1), 37-44. doi:10.7310/arfe.59.37
- Loconto, A. & Hatanaka, M. (2018) Participatory Guarantee Systems: Alternative Ways of Defining, Measuring, and Assessing ‘Sustainability’. *Sociologia Ruralis* 58(2): 412-432.
- Loconto, A., Jimenez, A., Vandecastelaere, E., & Tartanac, F. (2018) Agroecology, local food systems and their markets. *Ager. Revista de Estudios sobre Despoblación y Desarrollo Rural*. DOI: 10.4422/ager.2018.15.(25): 13-42.
- Loisel, J.P., François, M., Chiffolleau, Y., Hérault-Fournier, C., Sirieix, L., & Costa, S. (2016) La consommation alimentaire en circuits courts : enquête nationale. *Programme CODIA : Circuits courts en Europe : opportunités commerciales et dialogue avec la société*. Paris: Gret.
- Low, W. & Davenport, E. (2009) Organizational Leadership, Ethics and the Challenges of Marketing Fair and Ethical Trade. *Journal of Business Ethics* 86(0): 97-108.
- Lokhandwala, Z. (2022). Peasants’ Rights as New Human Rights: Promises and Concerns for Agrobiodiversity Conservation. *Asian Journal of International Law*, 1-16.
- Luziatelli, G., Sørensen, M., & Jacobsen, S. E. (2020). Current uses of Andean Roots and Tuber Crops in South American gourmet restaurants. *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science*, 22, 100270.

- Lysák, M., Ritz, C., & Henriksen, C. B. (2019). Assessing consumer acceptance and willingness to pay for novel value-added products made from breadfruit in the Hawaiian Islands. *Sustainability*, *11*(11), 3135.
- Mabhaudhi, T., Chimonyo, V. G., Chibarabada, T. P., & Modi, A. T. (2017). Developing a roadmap for improving neglected and underutilised crops: A case study of South Africa. *Frontiers in plant science*, *8*, 2143.
- Macready, A. L., Hieke, S., Klimczuk-Kochańska, M., Szumiał, S., Vranken, L. & Grunert, K. G. (2020) Consumer trust in the food value chain and its impact on consumer confidence: A model for assessing consumer trust and evidence from a 5-country study in Europe. *Food Policy* *92*: 101880.
- Marsden, T., Banks, J. & Bristow, G. (2000) Food Supply Chain Approaches: Exploring their Role in Rural Development. *Sociologia Ruralis* *40*(4): 424-438.
- Mbosso, C., Boulay, B., Padulosi, S., Meldrum, G., Mohamadou, Y., Berthe Niang, A., ... & Sidibé, A. (2020). Fonio and bambara groundnut value chains in mali: issues, needs, and opportunities for their sustainable promotion. *Sustainability*, *12*(11), 4766.
- Meier, C., & Oehen, B. (2019). Consumers' valuation of farmers' varieties for food system diversity. *Sustainability*, *11*(24), 7134.
- Meinhold, K., & Darr, D. (2021). Using a multi-stakeholder approach to increase value for traditional agroforestry systems: The case of baobab (*Adansonia digitata* L.) in Kilifi, Kenya. *Agroforestry Systems*, *95*(7), 1343-1358.
- Mensi, A., & Udenigwe, C. C. (2021). Emerging and practical food innovations for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) target 2.2. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, *111*, 783-789.
- Milano, M. Z., & Cazella, A. A. (2021). Environmental effects of geographical indications and their influential factors: A review of the empirical evidence. *Current Research in Environmental Sustainability*, *3*, 100096.
- Morimoto, Y., Maundu, P., Mahinda, E. G., & Kirori, D. (2021). Enhancing the use of underutilized food crops: Partnerships in a success story of a pop cereal business in Kenya. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 182-197). Routledge.
- Mudau, F. N., Chimonyo, V. G. P., Modi, A. T., & Mabhaudhi, T. (2021). Neglected and underutilised crops: A systematic review of their potential as food and herbal medicinal crops in South Africa. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, *12*.
- Nakandala, D., Smith, M., & Lau, H. (2020) Shared power and fairness in trust-based supply chain relationships in an urban local food system. *British Food Journal* *122*(3): 870-883.
- Nizar, N. M. M., Jahanshiri, E., Sinin, S. S. M., Wimalasiri, E. M., Suhairi, T. A. S. T. M., Gregory, P. J., & Azam-Ali, S. N. (2021). Open data to support agricultural diversification (version October 2020). *Data in brief*, *35*, 106781.
- Notaro, V., Padulosi, S., Galluzzi, G., & King, I. O. (2017). A policy analysis to promote conservation and use of small millet underutilised species in India. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, *15*(4), 393-405.
- Ochieng, C.M.O. (2008) Comparative capitalism and sustainable development: Stakeholder capitalism and co-management in the Kenyan fisheries sub sector. *Natural Resources Forum* *32*: 64-76.
- Osti, G. and Carrosio, G. (2020) Nested markets in marginal areas: Weak prosumers and strong food chains. *Journal of Rural Studies* *76*: 305-313.

- Ostrom, M. (2008) Community supported agriculture as an agent of change is it working? *Remaking the North American Food System: Strategies for Sustainability*. 99-120.
- Ostrom, M., De Master, K., Noe, E. & Schermer, M. (2017) Values-based Food Chains from a Transatlantic Perspective: Exploring a Middle Tier of Agri-food System Development. *International Journal of Sociology of Agriculture & Food* 24(1): 1-14.
- Padulosi, S., Bala Ravi, S., Rojas, W., Valdivia, R., Jager, M., Polar, V., & Gotor, E. (2011). Experiences and lessons learned in the framework of a global UN effort in support of neglected and underutilised species. In *II International Symposium on Underutilised Plant Species: Crops for the Future-Beyond Food Security* 979 (pp. 517-532).
- Padulosi, S., Amaya, K., Jäger, M., Gotor, E., Rojas, W., & Valdivia, R. (2014). A holistic approach to enhance the use of neglected and underutilised species: The case of Andean grains in Bolivia and Peru. *Sustainability*, 6(3), 1283-1312.
- Padulosi, S., Meldrum, G., Mathur, S., & Hunter, D. (2021). Mainstreaming NUS for nutrition-sensitive agriculture: A holistic approach. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 43-57). Routledge.
- Padulosi, S., & Hunter, D. (2021). Landmark NUS events and key publications. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 19-42). Routledge.
- Padulosi, S., King, E. I. O., Hunter, D., & Swaminathan, M. S. (Eds.). (2021). *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security: Promoting Neglected and Underutilised Species*. Routledge.
- Pallante, G., Drucker, A. G., & Sthapit, S. (2016). Assessing the potential for niche market development to contribute to farmers' livelihoods and agrobiodiversity conservation: Insights from the finger millet case study in Nepal. *Ecological Economics*, 130, 92-105.
- Parkinson, T.L. (1975) The Role of Seals and Certifications of Approval in Consumer Decision-Making. *Journal of Consumer Affairs* 9(1): 1-14.
- Patton, M.Q. (1990). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Pereira, L., Frantzeskaki, N., Hebinck, A., Charli-Joseph, L., Drimie, S., Dyer, M., Eakin, H., Galafassi, D., Karpouzoglou, T., Marshall, F., Moore, M.-L., Olsson, P., Siqueiros-García, J. M., Van Zwanenberg, P. & Vervoort, J. M. (2022). Leveraging the potential of wild food for healthy, sustainable, and equitable local food systems: learning from a transformation lab in the Western Cape region. *Sustainability Science*, 1-20.
- Phillipov, M. & Gale, F. (2020) Celebrity chefs, consumption politics and food labelling: Exploring the contradictions. *Journal of Consumer Culture* 20(4): 400-418.
- Pirsch, J., Shrut, G. & Grau, S.L. (2007) A Framework for Understanding Corporate Social Responsibility Programs as a Continuum: An Exploratory Study. *Journal of Business Ethics* 70(2): 125-140.
- Ponte, S. & Gibbon, P. (2005) Quality Standards, Conventions and the Governance of Global Value Chains. *Economy and Society* 34(1): 1-31.
- Porter, M.E. (1985) *Competitive advantage: creating and sustaining superior performance*. New York, London: Free Press; Collier Macmillan.
- Posadinu, C. M., Rodriguez, M., Madau, F., & Attene, G. (2022). The value of agrobiodiversity: An analysis of consumers preference for tomatoes. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 37(3), 237-247.
- Power, M. (2003) Evaluating the Audit Explosion. *Law & Policy* 25(3): 185-202.

- Quimby, B., & Beresford, M. (2023). Participatory Modelling: A Methodology for Engaging Stakeholder Knowledge and Participation in Social Science Research. *Field Methods*, 35(1), 73-82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X221076986>
- R Core Team (2022) R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.r-project.org/>
- Reed, D. (2009) What do Corporations have to do with Fair Trade? Positive and Normative Analysis from a Value Chain Perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics* 86(1): 3-26.
- Reinecke, J. (2010) Beyond a subjective theory of value and towards a 'fair price': an organisational perspective on Fairtrade minimum price setting. *Organization* 17(5): 563-581.
- Reinecke, J., Manning, S. and von Hagen, O. (2012) The Emergence of a Standards Market: Multiplicity of Sustainability Standards in the Global Coffee Industry. *Organization Studies* 33(5-6): 791-814.
- Renting, H., Marsden, T.K. & Banks, J. (2003) Understanding Alternative Food Networks: Exploring the Role of Short Food Supply Chains in Rural Development. *Environment and Planning A* 35(3): 393-411.
- Resque, A. G., Coudel, E., Piketty, M. G., Cialdella, N., Sá, T., Piraux, M., ... & Le Page, C. (2019). Agrobiodiversity and public food procurement programs in Brazil: influence of local stakeholders in configuring green mediated markets. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1425.
- Rover, O. J., da Silva Pugas, A., De Gennaro, B. C., Vittori, F., & Roselli, L. (2020). Conventionalization of organic agriculture: a multiple case study analysis in Brazil and Italy. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6580.
- Runhaar, H., Buijs, A., & Runhaar, P. (2019). What explains citizens' valuations of and attitudes towards agricultural biodiversity? Results of an exploratory survey of Dutch students. *NJAS-Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, 89, 100303.
- Runhaar, H., Runhaar, P., Bouwmans, M., Vink, S., Buijs, A., & Kleijn, D. (2019). The power of argument: Enhancing citizen's valuation of and attitude towards agricultural biodiversity. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 17(3), 231-242.
- Sacchi, G., Cei, L., Stefani, G., Lombardi, G. V., Rocchi, B., Belletti, G., ... & Vasvari, G. (2018). A multi-actor literature review on alternative and sustainable food systems for the promotion of cereal biodiversity. *Agriculture*, 8(11), 173.
- Salis, M. (2013) Filiere collettive e Alternative Food Network: nuove prospettive per la qualità. In: Meloni B and Farinella D (eds) *Sviluppo rurale alla prova. Dal territorio alle politiche*. Torino: Rosenberg&Sellier, pp.155-180.
- Santilli, J. (2013). Agrobiodiversity: Towards inovating legal systems. In *Renewing innovation systems in agriculture and food* (pp. 167-184). Wageningen Academic Publishers, Wageningen.
- Scaramuzzi, S., Gabellini, S., Belletti, G., & Marescotti, A. (2021). Agrobiodiversity-Oriented Food Systems between Public Policies and Private Action: A Socio-Ecological Model for Sustainable Territorial Development. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 12192.
- Schenk, P., Sunderer, G. & Rössel, J. (2016) Sind Deutschschweizer altruistischer als Deutsche? Ein Vergleich des Konsums fair gehandelter Produkte in Deutschland und der Schweiz. *Berliner Journal Fur Soziologie* 26(2): 145-170.
- Shah, S. S. & Asghar, Z. (2023) Dynamics of social influence on consumption choices: A social network representation. *Heliyon*, 9(6).

- Smith, S. (2010) For Love or Money? Fairtrade Business Models in the UK Supermarket Sector. *Journal of Business Ethics* 92(2): 257-266.
- Swensson, L.F., & Tartanac, F. (2020). Diversifying public food procurement and school feeding. In *Biodiversity, Food and Nutrition* (pp. 206-220). Routledge.
- Tallontire, A. (2007) CSR and regulation: towards a framework for understanding private standards initiatives in the agri-food chain. *Third World Quarterly* 28(4): 775 - 791.
- Tamariz, G., & Baumann, M.D. (2022). Agrobiodiversity change in violent conflict and post-conflict landscapes. *Geoforum*, 128, 217-222.
- Tampaki, M., Koutouzidou, G., Ragkos, A., Melfou, K., & Giantsis, I. A. (2022). Eco-Value and Public Perceptions for Indigenous Farm Animal Breeds and Local Plant Varieties, Focusing on Greece. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11211.
- Taranto, S.R., Alvarez, E.M., & Rojas, W. (2021). Agritourism and conservation of neglected and underutilised native Andean crops in Santiago de Okola, Bolivia. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 198-207). Routledge.
- Timmermann, C., & Robaey, Z. (2016). Agrobiodiversity under different property regimes. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 29(2), 285-303.
- Torres, L.E., Sánchez, J.A.C., del Moral, J.B., & Vargas, A.Á. (2022). Análisis de los compromisos de México frente a la agrobiodiversidad en el sistema agroalimentario: Analysis of commitments of Mexico towards agrobiodiversity in agri-food system. *Ciencia y Tecnología Agropecuaria*, 23(1).
- Van Amstel, M., de Brauw, C., Driessen, P., & Glasbergen, P. (2007). The reliability of product-specific eco-labels as an agrobiodiversity management instrument. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 16(14), 4109-4129.
- Van Amstel-Van Saane, M.H. (2007). *Twilight on self-regulation: A socio-legal evaluation of conservation and sustainable use of agrobiodiversity by industry self-regulation* (Vol. 362). KNAG.
- van der Ploeg, J.D. (2012). *The New Peasantries: Struggles for Autonomy and Sustainability in an Era of Empire and Globalization*. London: Routledge.
- van der Ploeg J.D. and Schneider S. (2022) Autonomy as a politico-economic concept: Peasant practices and nested markets. *Journal of Agrarian Change* 22(3): 529-546.
- Vandebroek, I., Picking, D., Tretina, J., West, J., Grizzle, M., Sweil, D., Green, U. & Lindsay, D. (2021). Root tonics and resilience: building strength, health, and heritage in Jamaica. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 640171.
- Van Dexter, K., & Ingalls, M. (2022). Sowing peace: Violence and agrobiodiversity in the Colombian Amazon. *Geoforum*, 128, 251-262.
- Van Loon, R., Lagneaux, E., Guerra, G. W., Chiriboga-Arroyo, F., Thomas, E., Gamarra, B., ... & Kettle, C. (2021). Barriers to adopting a diversity of NUS fruit trees in Latin American food systems. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 88-108). Routledge.
- Vergueiro, A. L., Kirori, D., Damon, J., Lopez, J. A., Kenya, L., Sharma, M., ... & Sankaranarayanan, V. (2021). Voices from the private sector engaged in the use enhancement of NUS. In *Orphan Crops for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 344-364). Routledge.
- Voinov, A., & Gaddis, E. J. B. (2008). Lessons for successful participatory watershed modeling: A perspective from modeling practitioners. *Ecological Modelling*, 216(2), 197-207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2008.03.010>
- Vonthron, S., Perrin, C., & Soulard, C. T. (2020). Foodscape: A scoping review and a research agenda for food security-related studies. *PLoS One*, 15(5), e0233218.

- Watts, D.C., Ilbery, B. & Maye, D. (2005) Making reconnections in agro-food geography: alternative systems of food provision. *Progress in human geography* 29(1): 22-40.
- Williams, J., Scarborough, P., Matthews, A., Cowburn, G., Foster, C., Roberts, N., & Rayner, M. (2014). A systematic review of the influence of the retail food environment around schools on obesity-related outcomes. *Obesity reviews*, 15(5), 359-374.
- Walker, R. E., Keane, C. R., & Burke, J. G. (2010). Disparities and access to healthy food in the United States: A review of food deserts literature. *Health & place*, 16(5), 876-884.
- Zamar, M. A., & Trillo, C. (2022). Influencia de los actores sociales en la circulación comercial de especies vegetales en ferias y mercado de la ciudad de Córdoba (Argentina) y sus alrededores. *Boletín de la Sociedad Argentina de Botánica*, 57(3), 1-10.
- Zimmerer, K.S., & de Haan, S. (2020). Informal food chains and agrobiodiversity need strengthening—not weakening—to address food security amidst the COVID-19 crisis in South America. *Food Security*, 12(4), 891-894.

9. Appendices

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Appendix 1. Articles included in the NUCs value chain literature review

Source	Description / reason for selection	Theme(s)	Sub-theme	Search term
Agnoletti and Santoro 2022	FAO GIAHS program (heritage sites)	Program	Global program	AB
Amaya et al 2020	Vendor, processing industry, restaurant, consumer, producer surveys	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Value chains	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Andreotti et al 2022	Boom and bust of NUS global demand, market transition/destabilisation	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	All	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Baird 2022	Political violence	Geopolitics, politics	Conflict	AB
Baldermann et al 2016	Storage, processing, trade and retail, consumer, information and communication. Certifications, standards, import-export, traceability	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Regulatory	All Trade and regulatory barriers.	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Barstow et al 2021	Slow Food: NUS as endangered products	Programs	Diverse	NUS, N+U+S
Batur et al 2021	Seed legislation impedes farmer innovation	Regulatory	Seeds	AB
Bogliotti et al 2021	Research for development agencies	Institutions	International	NUS, N+U+S
Borelli et al 2021	Mainstreaming toolkit: nutritional information, farmer support, enabling policy environments, consumer demand	Policy	All	NUS, N+U+S
Borelli et al 2020	Linking research to policy and markets, raise awareness to producers and consumers	Policy Awareness and demand Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Science-to-policy, public procurement policies Nutrition education, dietary guidelines, seasonality calendars Events, gastronomy, food innovations,	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Caetano et al 2016	Participatory breeding	Programs	Seeds	NUC, N+U+C, N+U+S

Camacho-Henriquez et al 2016	Participatory breeding	Programs	Seeds	NUC, NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Campanaro et al 2019	DNA barcoding of NUS to raise consumer awareness and identity	Awareness and demand Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Retail environment Identity	NUS, N+U+S
Chable et al 2020	Community level seed initiatives, marketing, regulatory bottlenecks, policy recommendations	Regulatory Institutional Policy	Seeds	AB
Da Cunha et al 2020	Urban gardens hosting NUS	Local food networks, urban agriculture and gardening	Urban agriculture and gardening	NUS, N+U+S
Darr et al 2020	Processing, packaging and consumer preferences (baobab)	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Processing Consumer demand	NUS, N+U+S
De Boef et al 2013	Commercialisation, value chains, marketing Regulation	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Regulatory	Diverse Diverse	AB
Galt et al 2016	CSA and agrobiodiversity as distinction strategy	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	CSA	AB
Girard and Frison 2018	Seed commons, intellectual property	Regulatory	Commons, intellectual property	AB
Giuliani et al 2004	Production-to-consumption chain, marketing, organisation of production system, modes of circulation, roles of actors	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Value chain Commercialisation Marketing	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Giuliani 2012	Market and value chain analysis	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Value chain	AB, N+U+C, N+U+S
Harris et al 2022	Review of challenges (all)	All	All	AB
Hermann et al 2013	Internet knowledge repositories	Knowledge management	Digitalisation	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Hernandez-Gomez 2009	Little-known tropical fruits	X	x	N+U+S
Hoeschle-Zeledon and Jaenicke 2006	tbd			N+U+C, N+U+S
Hunter et al 2019	All aspects of enabling/constraining environments to NUS mainstreaming	Policy Programs	Dietary guidelines Public and school food procurement	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S

		Value chain	Gastronomy	
Hunter et al 2021	Indigenous foodways	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Value chains	NUS, N+U+S
Jaeger et al 2017	Marketing, value chain, market failure as impure public good	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Value chains	AB
Johns and Eyzaguirre 2006	Policy platforms (regional and international)	Policy	Regional, international	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Jones et al 2021	Agrobiodiversity Index scores	Knowledge management	Measurement/evaluation	AB
Jordan et al 2016	Innovation platform to coordinate social organisation and relation innovation for sustainable commercialisation	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Commercialisation	AB
Juventia et al 2020	Agrobiodiversity Index commitments text mining	Policy	Policy discourse	AB
Kimura 2021	Pickling and heirloom varieties	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Processing Retail environment	AB
King et al 2021	Enhanced processing and market linkages through participatory, multidisciplinary, community-centred and multistakeholder value chain development interventions	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	All	NUS, AB, N+U+C, N+U+S
Kliem and Wolter 2022	Open food seed licences (consumer perceptions)	Consumer Regulatory	Seed	AB
Li et Siddique 2020	FAO: Future Smart Food Initiative, Regional Initiative on Zero Hunger	Programs		NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Li et al 2020	FAO: Future Smart Food Initiative, Regional Initiative on Zero Hunger (Asia-Pacific)	Programs		NUS, NUC, N+U+C, N+U+S
Lochetti 2021	Understanding seasonality: participatory assessment	Programs Knowledge management	Local Participatory	NUS, N+U+S
Luziatelli et al 2020	Gourmet restaurant use of tuber crops	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Restaurants	AB, N+U+C, N+U+S
Lysak et al 2019	Consumer acceptance breadfruit Hawaii	Consumer	Willingness to pay	N+U+C
Mabhaudhi et al 2017	R&D&I roadmap for promoting NUC	Policy	National policy framework	NUC, NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S

Mbosso et al 2020	Rapid Market Appraisal: traders, producers, processors, rural/urban consumers; bottlenecks, policy recommendations	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Consumption Policy	All Survey Recommendations	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Meier et al 2019	Consumer willingness to pay premium (DIVERSIFOOD)	Consumer	Willingness to pay	AB
Meinhold and Darr 2021	Community Based Enterprise, New Product Development. Multistakeholder community pathways. Behavioral changes. Consumers.	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Consumers	All	NUS, N+U+S
Mensi and Udenigwe 2021	Sustainable processing to enhance nutrient bioavailability	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Processing	NUC, N+U+C
Milano and Cazella 2021	Geographical Indications	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Marketing: labelling	AB
Morimoto et al 2021	Popping machine prototype experimentation, marketing, packaging and labeling	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Processing Marketing	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Mudau et al 2022 (systematic review)	Value addition, market structuring (cooperatives, Agribusiness Accelerators), capacity development	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Commercialisation, value chains	NUC, N+U+C, N+U+S
Nizar et al 2020	Open data	Knowledge management	Digitalisation	NUC, N+U+C
Notaro et al 2017	Policy environment for millet	Policy	Policy environment	NUS, N+U+S
Padulosi et al 2014	Program linking and strengthening value chain	Programs	Local program	NUS, N+U+S
Padulosi et al 2011	UN program on entire value chain: value addition technologies, processing standards, capacity building, gender, cultural sensitivity, school programs Food-of-the-poor stigma, crop diversity fairs	Programs Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Consumer awareness	Global All Events	NUS, N+U+S
Padulosi and Hunter 2021	Landmark events, programs, institutions and publications promoting global interest in NUS	Programs Institutions	Global Global	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S
Padulosi et al (Eds.) 2021	Introduction to key book on “orphan crops”	All aspects	All	NUS, N+U+C, N+U+S

Padulosi et al 2021	IFAD program on holistic value chain framework: interdisciplinary, bottom-up, gender-sensitive, indigenous peoples	Programs	International	NUS, N+U+S
Pallante et al 2016	Willingness to pay of urban consumers which compensates for conservation costs	Consumer demand	Willingness to pay	NUS, AB, N+U+C, N+U+S
Pereira et al 2022	Transformation lab	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Processing	NUS, N+U+S
Posadinu et al 2021	Consumer willingness to pay	Consumer	Willingness to pay	AB
Resque et al 2019	Public mediated markets including schools	Programs	Public procurement	AB
Rover et al 2020	AFN	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	AFN	AB
Runhaar et al 2019	Citizens and intrinsic value agrobiodiversity	Consumer	Willingness to pay	AB
Sacchi et al 2018	AFN and local food to promote cereal agrobiodiversity	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	AFN, local food	AB
Santili 2013	Innovative legal systems for agrobiodiversity FAO GHIAS program	Regulatory	Farmer's rights GHIAS	AB
Scaramuzzi et al 2021	Case-study: policy, consumer, value chains	Policy environments Demand Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	xxx	AB
Swensson and Tartanec	Public and school food procurement for agrobiodiversity	Policy, programs	Public procurement	AB
Tamariz and Baumann	Violent conflict and agrobiodiversity	Politics, geopolitics	Conflict	AB
Tampaki et al 2022	Consumer perspectives and eco-labelling	Consumer	Labelling	AB
Taranto et al 2021	Agritourism	Multifunctionality: ecosystem services, conservation, agritourism, etc.	Agritourism	NUC, AB, N+U+C
Timmermann and Robaey 2016	Agrobiodiversity under property regimes	Regulatory	Intellectual property	AB

Torres et al 2022	Policy commitments to agrobiodiversity in Mexico	Policy	Discourse	AB
Torres-Salcido 2022	Participatory certification and alternative markets	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing Consumer	Value chains Perception, prosumption	AB
Van Amstel-Van Saane 2007	Industry self-regulation for agrobiodiversity	Regulatory	Industry	AB
Van Amstel et al 2007	Standards: eco-labels	Regulatory	Labelling	AB
Van Dexter and Ingalls 2022	Violence and agrobiodiversity	Politics, geopolitics	Conflict	AB
Vandebroek et al 2021	Develop Jamaican root cottage industry	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	All	NUS, N+U+S
Vergueiro et al 2021	Role/voice of private sector in promoting NUS	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	All	NUS, N+U+S
Zamar and Trillo 2022	Food fairs (municipal, market, specialised)	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Events	AB
Zimmerer and De Haan 2020	Agrobiodiversity Knowledge Framework: governance of markets, logistics and distribution networks and seed systems	Value chains, processing, commercialisation and marketing	Commercialisation, marketing	AB

NB: Search term acronyms in title are: NUC (“neglected and underutilised crop”), NUS (“neglected and underutilised species”), N+U+C (“neglected” AND “underutilised” AND “crop”), N+U+S (“neglected” AND “underutilised” AND “species”), AB (“agrobiodiversity”)

Table 59. Synthesis table of the 78 reviewed articles from Scopus

Appendix 2. Database on NUC production in the DIVINFOOD partner countries

The database built of initiatives valuing NUCs can be accessed on Zenodo on the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/12775303>

See also the document “Additional material to Appendix 2” with presents national statistics on DIVINFOOD’s NUCs production in the 7 DIVINFOOD countries on Zenodo on the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/12825599>

Appendix 3. Online survey instrument

Valuing food products made from neglected and under-utilised crops

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

1 Introduction

DIVINFOOD aims at developing food chains valuing agrobiodiversity and procuring plant-based food that are good for health, farmers and the planet. To achieve this, a survey is being conducted with all initiatives (companies, farmers, shops, associations, organisations, cooperatives...) that sell or promote neglected and underutilised legumes and cereals (NUCs) in 7 European countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden and Switzerland), such as legumes or cereals from old, local or indigenous varieties. This survey is managed by INRAE and the information will be processed by INRAE.

The decision to take part in this survey is voluntary and should take a maximum of 15 minutes.

See the complete survey instrument in the document “Additional material to Appendix 3” on the following link on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/12826837>

Appendix 4. NUCs currently being valued by short and mid-tier chains

This appendix includes those NUCs from cereals and from legumes that were cited by the initiatives in response to the question “Q3.6/3.7 - Please specify the varieties of cereals/legumes that you consider as NUCs” for each country”.

Figures in brackets indicate the number of initiatives that cited the NUCs in question according to their type (F= farmers; I=intermediaries; O=Other; P= processors; S=Shops).

The line “Number of NUCs cited by initiatives” is given as an indication, as the level/precision of citation is very heterogeneous according to the initiatives. For example, an initiative that cited only "ancient wheat" was counted as a single citation, whereas an initiative that cited many specific varieties of ancient wheats (e.g. Virgilio, Gallio, Ardito) was counted as three citations.

*Sum of initiatives declaring NUCS from cereals is 66 as one initiative varieties that do not belong to the cereal category

	Denmark (n=5)	France (n=30)	Hungary (n=13)	Italy (n=10)	Portugal (n=7)	Sweden (n=5)	Switzerland (n=8)
Number of initiatives with NUCS CEREALS (66)*	5 (2 P ; 3 S)	28 (14 F ; 5 I ; 1 O ; 1 P ; 7 S)	9 (4 F ; 3 I ; 1 P ; 1 S)	9 (6 F ; 1 I ; 2 P)	6 (3 F ; 3 S)	3 (2 P ; 1 S)	6 (2 F ; 4 O)

<p>Number of initiatives without any precisions about the type of NUCS CEREALS (13)</p>	<p>Any citation (1 S)</p>	<p>Local cereals not listed in the official catalogue (1 F) Other varieties of mass selections, names unknown (1 F) Cereals population (2: 1 I ; 1 S) More than 200 varieties without precisions (1 O)</p>		<p>Local varieties (1 P) 25 ancient varieties of grains out of 100 present in Italy (1 P) Many varieties (1 F)</p>	<p>Ancient varieties (1 F)</p>		<p>Numerous varieties (any precision - 1 O) Many varieties (1 O) Any citations (1 F)</p>
<p>Number of NUCS CEREALS cited by initiatives</p>	<p>2 citations (1 P) 3 citations (1 P) 4 citations (1 S) 5 citations (1 S)</p>	<p>1 citation (10 : 5 F ; 3 I ; 2 S) 2 citations (8: 5 F ; 3 S) 3 citations (2: 1 I ; 1 S) 4 citations (1 F) 5 citations (1 P) 6 citations (1 F)</p>	<p>1 citation (5: 1 F ; 3 I ; 1 P) 2 citations (4: 3 F ; 1 S)</p>	<p>1 citation (2 F) 2 citations (1 F) 3 citations (1 I) 6 citations (1 F) 12 citations (1 F)</p>	<p>1 citation (2 S) 2 citations (1 F) 3 citations (2: 1 F ; 1 S)</p>	<p>1 citation (1 P) 2 citations (1 S) 5 citations (1 P)</p>	<p>1 citation (1 F) 2 citations (1 O) 3 citations (1 O)</p>

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WHEAT (84)	Emmer (3: 1 P ; 2 S) Island wheat (1 S) Red wheat (1 P) Purple wheat (1 P)	Ancient varieties (6: 2 F; 1 I ; 3 S) Red Bordeaux wheat (4 F) Poulard wheat (5: 4 F (1 = Turgidum blue); 1 I) Naunette de Lausanne wheat (2 F) Touzelle (2: 1 F ; 1 S) Castelnau wheat (1 F) Red of Lot (1 F) Red of Morvan (1 F) Red of Roc (1 F) Carré de Crête (1 F) Triticale (1 S) Khorasan wheat (1 S) Farro (1 P) Freekeh (1 P) Florence Aurora (1 I) Soft local wheat (1 F) Wheat populations (1 F)	Alakor (hungary variety - 4: 2 F; 1 I; 1 S) Emmer (tönke - 2: 1 F ; 1 S) Bánkút wheat (local variety - 1 F) Starch wheat (1 F)	Inallettabile (2 F) Piave (2 F) Local durum wheat (1 F) Local soft wheat (1 F) Local variety Rieti wheat (1 F) Mallorca (1 I) Saragolla (1 I) Starch wheat (1 F) Trimina (1 I) Autonomy (1 F) Villa Glory (1 F) Frassineto (1 F) Canove (1 F) Gentil Rosso (1 F) Cobra Q population (1 F) Cobra A population (1 F) mixture 180 (1 F) Li Rosi duri mixture (1 F) Andriolo (1 F) Virgil (1 F) Gallio (1 F) Ardito (1 F)	Ancient varieties (1 F) Barbela wheat (1 F) Dew wheat (1 F) Khorasan wheat (2: 1 F; 1 S)	Dala country wheat (1 P) Värmland wheat (1 P) Västgöta wheat (1 P) Emmer (1 P) Öland wheat (1 P) Starch wheat (1 S)	Emmer (2 O) Triticale (1 O) Many varieties of wheat (1 O)
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EINKORN (17)	Einkorn (2 S)	Einkorn (5: 2 F ; 1 I ; 1 P ; 1 S) Einkorn from Haute Provence (2: 1 I ; 1 S) Einkorn wheat (1 F)	Alako rbuza (hungarian variety - 1 F)	Einkorn spelled (1 F) Einkorn wheat (1 F) Einkorn variety Haermanni (1 F)		Einkorn (1 P) Einkorn wheat (1 S)	Einkorn (Triticum monococcum - 1 O)
SPELT (16)	Spelt (3: 2 S; 1 P)	Spelt (3 S) Oberkulmer spelled wheat (1 F)	Spelt (2: 1 P ; 1 F) Tönkölybúza (hungarian local ; 2 I)	Local variety of spelt (1 F)	Spelt (3: 2 F ; 1 S)		Spelt (1 O)
MAIZE (5)		ancient maize (1 F)		Local variety of maize (1 F)	Corasano maize (1 S) White maize (1 F)		Many varieties of maize (1 O)
RYE (5)	Sweder rye (1 S) Swedjer (1 S)			Local variety of rye (1 F)			Forest perennial rye (1 F) Many varieties of rye (1 O)
BUCKWHEAT (5)		Buckwheat (3: 1 I; 1 P ; 1 S - Kasha)	Buckwheat (1 F)		Buckwheat (1 S)		
BARLEY (2)				Local variety of barley (1 F)			Many varieties of barley (1 O)
FONIO (1)	Fonio (1 P)						
TEFF (1)					Teff (1 S)		

NUCS from legumes cited by the initiatives.

	Denmark (n=5)	France (n=30)	Hungary (n=13)	Italy (n=10)	Portugal (n=7)	Sweden (n=5)	Switzerland (n=8)
Number of initiatives with NUCS LEGUMES (38)	3 (1 P ; 2 S)	10 (3 F ; 3 I ; 1 P ; 4 S)	5 (2 F ; 3 I)	6 (3 F ; 1 I ; 2 P)	5 (2 F ; 1 O ; 2 S)	4 (1 F ; 2 P ; 1 S)	6 (1 F ; 5 O)
Number of initiatives without any precisions about the type of NUCS LEGUMES (7)	1 (S) = + many other 1 (S) = any citation	1 (S) = not knowledgeable on the subject + many legumes (any precision)			1 (F) = all indigenous varieties or varieties normally consumed in the country	1 (P) = old country varieties 1 (P) = all local varieties that some growers propagate	1 (O) = numerous varieties (any precision)
Number of NUCS LEGUMES cited by initiatives	4 citations (1 P) Many (1 S)	1 citation (4: 1 I ; 1 F ; 1 P ; 2 S) 2 citations (3: 2 F ; 1 I) 3 citations (1 S) 4 citations (1 I)	1 citation (3 : 1 F ; 2 I) 2 citations (1 I) 4 citations (1 F)	1 citation (3: 1 F ; 1 I ; 1 P) 3 citations (2 F) 4 citations (1 P)	1 citation (1 S) 2 citations (2 : 1 F ; 1 O) 3 citations (1 S) Many (1 F)	4 citations (1 F) 6 citations (1 S) Many (2 P)	1 citation (2 : 1 F ; 1 O) 2 citations (1 O) 3 citations (1 O) Many (2 O)
LENTILS (20)	Beluga lentils (1 P) Puy lentils (1 P)	Lentils (3 : 1F ; 2 I) Green lentils (1 S) Blond lentils (1 S) Lentillons (1 F) Corail lentils (2 F)		Lentils (various types) (1 F) Solento lentils (1 I) Local varieties of red lentils (1 P)	Lentils (1 F)	Gotland lentils (3 : 1 F, 1 P ; 1 S : gotlandslins) Green lentils (Grön lins Anica.) (1 S) Corail Lentils	Lentils (1 O)

						(korallins Rosanna) (1 S)	
PEAS (16)	Green peas (1 S)	Snow peas (1 I)	Green peas (1 F)	Local varieties of peas (1 P) Grass peas (1 F) Roveja (1 F)	Grass peas (Lathyrus sativus) (1 O) Cow peas (vigna unguiculata) (1 O)	Grey peas (3 : 1 P ; 1 F : Stäme gray pea ; 1 S : Gråärt ; 1 F : Rättviksärt) Vreta yellow peas (3 : 1 F ; 1 P ; 1 S : gul ärt Vreta) Autumn sown peas (höstärt) (1 S)	Sweet peas (1 O)
BEANS (16)	Fuegobønner bean (1 S)	Beans (3 : 1 I ; 2 S) Dried beans (1 I) Azuki Bean (1 P)	Beans (1 I) Vigna beans (1 F) Mung beans (1 F) Local heirloom Phaseolus beans (1 F)	Beans (2 : 1 F, 1 P - local varieties)	Black beans (1 F) Azuki beans (1 S) Papo-da-Rola beans (local) (1 S) Catarino Beans (1 S)		
CHICKPEAS (12)	Chickpeas (1 P)	Chickpeas (3 : 1F; 2 I)	Chickpeas (3 : 1 F ; 2 I)	Chickpeas (3 : 2 F, 1 P - local varieties)	Grão preto (1 S)		Chickpeas (1 O)
FABA BEANS (4)	Horse beans (1 P)		Horse beans (1 I)				15 different varieties of vicia

							faba (1 O) Broad beans (1 O)
LUPIN (4)		Lupins (1 S)		Lupins (2 : 1 F ; 1 P)			Lupins (1 O)

Table 60. NUCS from cereals cited by the initiatives

Appendix 5. Definitions of NUCs according to the respondents

This appendix includes the answer to the open response question that asked the initiatives to explain why they considered the varieties that listed to be NUCs (Q3.13)

	n	%
Not known	42	54,0
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By the consumers, less known, little known, little used, not used that much, not asked by consumers, customers don't even know their usage options, consumers need to be informed, need communication (education, no school education, no public catering), don't know how to use, to process/prepare them or know their nutritional benefits... - Not found in the classic sales channels, rarely present or absent from traditional commercial circuits, not found in supermarkets, almost no longer available for purchase, less sold, difficult to obtain nowadays, niche markets, not marketed, do not find buyers on the markets outside of a microcosm of very motivated and informed consumers... - No longer found, few grown, cultivation has almost been abandoned, has been cultivated and used less and less over time, only grown on very little area or for feed mixtures/green manures and have hardly been used in breeding any more, forgotten production, difficult to obtain as few people grow them, not grown by neighbouring farmers, few processed, not care by the industry, not used in baking... 		
Seeds/variety	29	37,0
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local; local ecotypes; indigenous variety; produced locally; endemic varieties - Authentic (compared to intensive production and genetic manipulation) - Peasant seeds, from farmers, from research - Old; still exists in conservatories; have conservation status; used in the past; forgotten; loss; difficult to find; few varieties; now out of use - Rare, endangered varieties - New but rarely used and requiring selection - Not referenced in the official catalogues, in the register of conservation varieties - Varieties gradually abandoned in favour of lineal or hybrid varieties; grains thrown up by the agri-food industry; traditional crops, abandoned for maize and high yielding wheat - Lack of varietal diversity, lack of seeds, lack of technical data 		
Difficult to grow	23	29,5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low productivity; low yield; lack of popularity; less productive varieties; cultivation is also very hardy; grow slowly... - Little value; not profitable; cheaper abroad... 		

- Small crops, limited volume, difficulty in opening sales contracts with distributors; need research; too labour intensive field trials to be incorporated into market production; need human resources have to be dedicated to this kind of research; not adapted to mass distribution; supplanted by commercial varieties; virtually disappeared when farming became an industry; not asked by large baking companies as there is no volume ; grown in non-industrial quantities ; do not meet the expectations of modern varieties, they are cultivated in a very narrow circle, mainly in small-scale conditions; substituted by more productive modern varieties with higher gluten strength...		
Difficult to process	6	7,7
- Loss because difficult to process - Require great baking skills; grains with little gluten, which give flours with low w, defined as non-bread making - Need for dehulling after harvesting for its use		
Provide agroecological benefits	13	16,7
- They are grown biodynamically, which takes care of the soil's fertility and binds; organic production or agroecology; not needing external inputs; low inputs...		
- With a high capacity for adaptation to the environment and resilience; Can also be grown in places with poorer agricultural conditions, resistance is better; naturally resistant to current climatic conditions; adapted to the hot and dry climate, which stores carbon, which improves soil fertility; some can withstand drought better...		
- Are very good for the environment, great potential as sustainable...		
- Preserve biodiversity compared to large corporate varieties...		
- Development of innovative, local and sustainable supply chains, promoting the preservation of genetic diversity...		
Provide health benefits	13	16,7
- Nutritional qualities; healthy; good for the health; nutritional value and effect on human metabolism deserve more attention and consumption; interesting in terms of its nutritional values; great potential as nutritious foods; products of high nutritional quality		
- Better digestibility; more digestible; a low gluten strength, which studies showed as more digestible; great interest both from a nutritional point of view - gluten-free - rich in protein with a broad spectrum of essential amino acids; have great potential as plant-based protein suppliers		
Provide process potential (great potential as food ingredients; can be used well; good opportunities for baked goods or the production of pasta; can be well suited as a bread grain; with high potential...)	4	5,1
Provide organoleptic advantages (better taste, give good bread, appearance, size, regularity)	2	2,6
Authenticity/quality; unmodified	2	2,6

Consumers are looking for, in recent years conscious buyers start looking for them	2	2,6
Higher price, very expensive	2	2,6
Provide diversity in varieties like local varieties, taste, colour, shape	1	1,3
Easy-to-cultivate qualities	1	1,3
Same advantages as all vegetables	1	1,3
Loss for cultural/religion reasons	1	1,3
Don't know/no responses	7	8,9

Table 61. Reasons given by the initiatives to consider products as being NUCS

Appendix 6. Participatory Modelling Workshop

Participatory modelling

Participatory modelling was proposed as a means to test the validity of our typology. Emerging from natural resources management and complex systems, participatory modelling is the process of incorporating stakeholders into the modelling process (Voinov and Gaddis, 2008). A participatory workshop is organised whereby information is solicited from stakeholders, thus enabling the integration of scientific knowledge with local knowledge. The approach is goal driven, meaning that the purpose of the model and how it will be used is clearly defined. This approach levels the playing field among different types of experts. It produces co-learning, co-understanding and co-creation of models or typologies that are useful to stakeholders (Quimby and Beresford 2023).

The primary objective of the workshop was to **present, discuss in detail and validate the 1st version of the NUC value chain typology** with participants from the Living Labs of the project and external value chain experts. Based on their feedback, a 2nd version of the typology could be developed with the necessary modifications.

Workshop details

Date/Format: 27 March 2024, 10:00-13:00 CET / Online - Zoom

Participants: 14 Living Lab coordinators and other project participants from five countries (DK, FR, HU, IT, PT) and 13 external value chain experts from four countries (FR, HU, IT, PT)

Time	Agenda point
10:00-10:15	Welcome and introductions
10:15-10:30	Presentation of the DIVINFOOD project and work on the consumption value of agrobiodiversity by project coordinator, Yuna Chiffolleau
10:30-11:00	Presentation of DIVINFOOD's NUCs Value Chain Typology, Q&A
11:00-11:30	Coffee break
11:30-12:10	Breakout rooms in the following groups <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • France - DIVINFOOD Living Labs and experts • Hungary - DIVINFOOD Living Labs and experts • Sweden and Denmark - DIVINFOOD Living Labs and experts • Italy and Switzerland - DIVINFOOD Living Labs and experts • Portugal - DIVINFOOD Living Labs and experts
12:10-12:50	Plenary discussion, feedback from breakout rooms
12:50-13:00	Closing remarks, conclusions

Table 62. Agenda of the participatory modelling workshop

Presentation of typology

The typology was based broadly on a database of 1,272 short, medium and long value chain initiatives valuing NUCs (legumes and minor cereals) compiled across seven countries. Detailed information on the initiatives and the role of NUCs was collected through an online survey (n=72 at the time of the participatory modelling workshop). We relied directly on the characteristics of these 72 initiatives to develop the first version of the value chain typology.

In the first half of the workshop, the database of initiatives, the analysis methodology, the related descriptive statistics, and the approach used to define the value chain types were presented, followed by the first version of the typology.

In this first approach, the *attributes* found in the relevant literature of “value-based supply chains” to characterise value chains, were used as *variables* to distinguish between the different value-chain types. For each variable, we gave a definition, assigned a practical application in the typology, and a hypothesis that could be tested using the variable. See examples in the table below.

Variable	Definition	Operationalisation	Hypotheses
Maturity of the enterprise	The date of foundation ranges from 1819 to 2023	Traditional (founded before 2000), Mature (founded between 2000-2010), Young (founded between 2010-2020), Post-Covid (founded since 2021)	Food chains valuing NUCs are more likely to be young enterprises
Mission first	Number and type of missions	Four groups of mission: Health, Nature, Local economy, Nutrition Number of missions: 0-13	Food chains valuing NUCs have more than one mission

Table 63. Variable operationalisation

As a next step, the typology was presented in detail, supplemented with brief introductions of typical exemplary cases drawn from the database.

In the first version of the typology, four ideal types of value chains were defined, distinguished by the role of the key drivers/lead actors of the initiative and further described using the additional variables. See the brief description of the four value chain types below. The full version of the 1st typology can be found in the document “Additional material to Appendix 6” on the following Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/records/12826919>

- **Farm-Focused Value Chains:** These value chains are driven by producers who mainly sell their own locally sourced products, specialising in cereals, with little competition. The primary benefits of selling NUCs in these chains are environmental.
- **Market Quality Value Chains:** Driven by intermediaries, like online platforms, these chains focus on high-quality products and maintain long-term contracts with farmers, ensuring stable mid-tier supply chains. They deliver similar consumer prices and sales margins for NUCs as conventional products, with benefits extending to social and economic gains, alongside environmental ones.
- **Collective Market Value Chains:** These value chains are driven by hybrid intermediaries, such as processors, restaurants, and traders who also produce what they sell, characterised by collaborative efforts and long-term contracts. They promote a range of

benefits, including cultural and environmental, through their intermediary roles, though a clear social mission is not always articulated.

- **Diversified Value Chains:** Driven by shops with both physical and online presence, these value chains are highly diversified, relying on indirect supply and one-time sales to offer a wide variety of NUCs. These shops face little competition for NUCs, with higher consumer prices but maintaining the same profit margins as similar conventional products.

During the Q&A session, there were questions about the definition of NUCs used in the project and which types of value chains were included in the analysis, particularly whether medium and long value chains were considered. Participants also asked whether the benefits from NUCs might lead to coordinated campaigns among initiatives or remained individual efforts, and whether initiatives were self-sufficient or received incentives and support to promote NUCs. An initial interesting finding was that initiatives valuing NUCs were motivated by environmental concerns and missions, rather than economic benefits.

Breakout sessions and plenary discussion

In the breakout sessions, participants gave feedback on the typology and the description of the four value chain types along the following set of questions:

1. Conceptual linkages: Are the value chain dynamics captured?
2. Clarification of the categories: Are there some categories that are not clearly defined or could be better defined?
3. Distinctiveness: Are the presented value chains distinctive enough to be considered discrete types?
4. Empirical examples: Does the typology describe initiatives that you are familiar with?
5. What is missing?

The session moderators then presented the main feedback from each group in the plenary session.

Only summaries from the moderators are provided below; full transcripts of group discussions are available in the document “Additional material to Appendix 6” on the following link on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/12826919>

- **France:** The group primarily focused on Farm-Focused Value Chains, and suggestions and criticisms were made in this context. Participants acknowledged the diverse category of ‘farmers’, ranging from farmers’ cooperatives to individual and isolated farmers, making categorisation really challenging due to varying operational styles, levels of competition, etc. Factors other than the role of the leading actor, such as governance, contract types, etc., also influence the operation of initiatives and the role of NUCs, therefore the typology is somewhat biased and incomplete. Some of the variables are not compact enough: environmental concerns may also vary widely. Below-radar initiatives might be locally important, but they do not have drop out from the analysis. A recurring criticism was that certain categories of typology are difficult to distinguish, with a lot of overlap and classification is difficult.
- **Italy:** Experts found that the concept of the ‘leading actor role’ as a key criterion of differentiation did not align with their views. “Market quality” and “collective market” categories were hard for the participants to differentiate, especially because in several real-life cases, collective effort of players has a bigger role in the value chain than the

leading actor itself, finding a proper place for large players (e.g., supermarkets) difficult. Some real-life examples also struggled to fit within the typology. As an example, a farm that is partly selling NUCs on-farm, and partly to an urban shop, or as another example, the new and unusual retail spaces in cities, such as newspaper stores, where food is also sold.

- **Portugal & Denmark:** The presence of supermarkets selling local products raised questions about their classification. Some examples fit into more than one category, or some categories are overlapping. Finding a category for NGOs, non-profits, or those initiatives that do not sell, but promote NUCs, was rather challenging. New aspects/variables were suggested, such as sustainability and resilience, or the presence/absence of communication/promotion tools such as in-store nudging. Considerations for enterprise incentives and in-store nudging were proposed.
- **Hungary:** A fundamental question that arose was what exactly the purpose of the typology is. It was noted as one of the weaknesses of typology, that it does not consider the potential for initiatives to switch categories over time. Participants found it challenging to differentiate categories Market Quality and Collective Market. Some initiatives could not fit neatly into any category, including shopping communities, big online stores (without any mission), and below-radar trade did not align with existing categories. Additionally, for many, NUCs represented only a small portion of their business, making classification solely based on this aspect unjustified.

Outcomes

To effectively develop a typology, it is essential to clearly define our objectives. The initial approach, based on the available data was to understand how individual initiative value NUCs, examine their connections with other actors and identify the type of value chain they build up or belong to. In this approach, the structure and dynamics of value chains played a crucial role in how successfully NUCs are valued.

Based on the questions and feedback from participants, we need to take a different approach. It is increasingly clear that NUCs themselves will hardly make a difference in the value chains. Marketing of NUCs by leveraging their associated values and benefits, as well as consumer engagement (incl.: sharing recipes, organising tasting events, explanations of benefits, communication with restaurants, etc.) seems to be more critical for the success of NUCs than the value chain structure and dynamics itself.

It should also be recognised that NUCs and NUC-based products predominantly feature within value chains as components of wider concepts, representing and exemplifying concepts such as diversity, uniqueness, specificity, tradition, health or geographical indication. The concept of 'NUC-ness' does not inherently manifest as a singular value proposition, and/or is not recognised by the value chain actors either.

The current consideration is whether the most effective approach for enhancing the integration of NUCs into value chains is to introduce the concept of NUC independently and attribute and communicate its intrinsic value, or alternatively, to align NUC features with established concepts already acknowledged as valuable. This, of course, also leads back to rethinking the definition of NUCs.

Building upon the above, we concluded that the **selection of values**, coupled with **communication strategies and tools** and **contextual – explicit or implicit – mission statements**, could serve as effective means of determining different types of value chains that prioritise the valuation of NUCs.

Further guidelines/considerations for the adjustments of the typology

- **Address various conceptual issues:** Acknowledge, for example, the variation in how supermarkets value NUCs, and recognise that a single producer may utilise multiple types of value chains in different ways.
- **Comprehend the genuine benefit of NUCs in value chains:** Consider the role of communication in differentiating value chains in the next typology iteration.
- **Clear definitions:** Ensure a clear, shared definition to NUCs, value chain dynamics, etc. among stakeholders to avoid confusion in the typology.
- **Re-evaluate differentiating variables:** Explore alternative approaches where the leading actor is not the primary differentiating factor to gain a more nuanced understanding of value chains.
- **Inclusion of underrepresented value chains in typology:** Due to the relatively low response rate, certain types of value chains (e.g., school catering, farmers' markets) were not adequately represented in the analysed data. However, it is crucial to acknowledge their existence and incorporate them into typology development. Testing the typology on these underrepresented chains is essential for comprehensive evaluation and refinement.
- **Improve sample representation:** Strive for balanced participation across different types of initiatives, acknowledging limitations in project resources.
- **Incorporate additional variables:** Utilise available data to clarify linkages within value chains, while considering time and resource constraints.
- **Refine type definitions:** Enhance clarity in defining different value chain types to minimise confusion.
- **Consider vertical integration:** Recognise cases where farmers process and sell NUCs themselves, leading to vertically integrated value chains.

Based on these suggestions, we extended the date for collecting data from our questionnaire. We then went back to the literature and modelled a new set of clusters around these pivot points that better explained the differences in how ideal type value chains might value agrobiodiversity and NUCs in particular. The new typology is presented in the next section.

Validation workshop with DIVINFOOD partners

As discussed above, in March 2024 we organized an online participatory modelling workshop to validate our initial typology of short- and mid-tier chains valuing NUCs. After this workshop, we concluded that a different approach was needed on our part and the typology needs to be adjusted. The typology presented in this deliverable reflects the feedback received from the participants of this first workshop.

The new – and final – typology, which is presented here, was developed, but we still wished to validate this with the DIVINFOOD partners, to see whether they can be clearly understood and whether the initiatives they are familiar with in their countries or living lab regions could be categorized into these types with a relative ease. Therefore, a validation workshop was organized in the framework of the 2nd DIVINFOOD Annual Meeting in Copenhagen, on the 25th of June 2024.

This was an in-person workshop in which all attendees of the meeting (56 people in total) were present.

In the workshop, the key elements of the research and the typology were first presented by Allison Loconto: the presentation included the objectives of the task, the methodology behind developing the typology, the description of the various types, and one case study for each category to illustrate the key characteristics of the types.

After the presentation, we asked the participants to create groups according to their country: this resulted in 5 groups in total: one with the French, one with the Hungarian, one with the Portuguese, one with the Italian and Swiss, and one with the Danish and Swedish participants. Each group was given 25 minutes to discuss how the initiatives they are familiar with in their local contexts fit – or do not fit – into the categories suggested by our typology. They were asked to create a chart where the various initiatives were placed into the various categories.

The group exercise was followed by a plenary session where we gathered feedback on the exercise and what the thoughts within the group were about the typology. As it can be also seen from the charts that the groups created (Figures X-Z) , participants found it relatively easy to place different initiatives into the categories, even though the time in the workshop was limited to fully convey the characteristics of the types. Key feedbacks we received criticized the various overlaps between the categories and the question of creating a 5th category – with initiatives that answered that they do not deal with NUCs in the survey – was raised. Some confusion was present about the naming of the various categories, which resulted in us renaming two of them for this final version. Thus, “modest communicators” turned into “quality communicators” and “highly certified” was turned into “active promoters”.

Figure 22. Group work at the DIVINFOOD annual meeting - the Hungarian table

Figure 23. Group work at the DIVINFOOD annual meeting – the Italian-Swiss table

Figure 24. Group work results - Nordic countries

Figure 25. Group work results - France

Transcripts of breakout group discussions of the DIVINFOOD - NUCs Value Chain Expert Workshop in March 2024

France

Discussion topics	Feedback from Participants
Conceptual linkages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumers, citizens and local authorities sometimes play an important role in supporting (or even primary) functions. - The conceptual framework has been well captured, but I don't know if everyone has the same definition of NUCs. - Cooks (private and public restaurants) to be considered or processors (ready meals). - Could we have a definition of "Value Chain Dynamics" and other examples? - The Food Chains Valuing NUCs here are more focused on selling products to consumers and not on other NUC outlets (restaurants, eateries, etc.), so it's difficult to see how NUCs are used as a whole + there's no mention of how products are processed (e.g. chef, farmer-boulangerie, SMEs, etc.). - An experimental dimension that may be lacking in the dynamics (experimenting with the crop as a complement to a 'traditional' crop): not necessarily emphasised in the players' discourse. - Environmental objectives vary widely: is it a desire to adapt to climate change, to develop more resistant crops or a genuine biodiversity objective? - Differentiation between local and old seeds? With different dynamics and objectives - Very small experiments not developed on the Internet but locally (no communication) excluded from the analysis: perhaps develop a qualitative analysis with interviews/ethnography to complete the picture. - Introduction of NUCs through school catering (canteens)
Clarification of the categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The farm category has 2 sub-types: individual farmers and groups of farmers who structure a collective supply chain (and work with intermediaries). - "Vision of Nuc's value: categories a little vague (e.g. environmental) - Overlapping categories? Market that ultimately represents a "network" of producers - The "collective" category is more oriented towards economic benefits (differentiation from a mainstream industrial or agricultural cooperative). - The term "collective" is debatable: some manufacturers cooperate, others less so., - Where could health benefits be placed in a category?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The farm focused and collective markets categories can be quite similar. Rename the farm focused category for example (as some collective markets may also have farm sales...) - Last category: Processors may use NUCs for reasons of niche market opportunities, or 'food innovation', and no stable market.
Distinctiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of categories to specify the typologies (even if I understand that the surveys have already been carried out and that it is difficult to retrieve this information afterwards). - Make another presentation of the categories (and their interactions with each other) to see the interconnectivity between them (Venn diagram, etc.). - Need to discuss the interrelationships between dynamics (cooperation, etc.) - Specificity of sorting stages with sometimes very few operators (different value chains passing through the same link)
Empirical examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Release of the latest book from the BioValue sister project: "Value Chain Dynamics in a Biodiverse Environment" edited by Konstadinos Mattas, George Baourakis, Constantin Zopounidis, and Christos Staboulis?
What's missing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are 2 categories of chains missing: collective chains run by groups of farmers and chains run by a manufacturer/cooperative - Health benefits of NUCs and nutritional aspects - Innovations in meat substitutes (veggie steak) - Redefinition of NUCs with a more attractive semantics, but one that takes into account the positive aspects of species from field to plate

Hungary

Discussion topics	Feedback from Participants
Conceptual linkages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NUCs are extremely underrepresented in the Hungarian supply, so it is not clear what the purpose of the categories is?
Clarification of the categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market Quality and Collective Market Value are difficult to distinguish
Distinctiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiatives may change categories during their lifetime, - There are other values in Farm-Focused value chains than environmental.
Empirical examples	
What's missing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hard to find the proper category for shopping communities, CSAs

Italy and Switzerland

Discussion topics	Feedback from Participants
Conceptual linkages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competition between NUCs and conventional products (non-NUCs), - I would add the cooperative theme: common campaign - Online platform is more an instrument, than an actor – this category needs to be refined.

Clarification of the categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market quality value chains / Collective Market value chains - The name of these 2 categories should be better distinguished. - Supermarket chiana/mainstream channels, - Collective/collaborative dimension of the supply chain can be found in other types of supply chains, not only in Collective Market Value Chains) - Clarify how the price comparison is done
Distinctiveness	
Empirical examples	- Farm that sells partly on farm, in an urban coop, and to an SME
What's missing	

Portugal + Nordic countries

Discussion topics	Feedback from Participants
Conceptual linkages	
Clarification of the categories	<i>Market Quality</i> is perhaps also mission first in some cases. Duration of enterprises
Distinctiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are overlaps between the categories. - Examples are broader than the categories themselves, - Not clear distinction between Market Quality, and Diversified Value Chains
Empirical examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some examples fit into more than one category, - Supermarkets began to work with NUCs in Denmark and Portugal, with displays, selling legumes in bulks. Hard to categorize these. - Do non-profits/NGOs fit into the categories? - Cooking Lab promoting but not selling – where does it fit?
What's missing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentives of funding of the enterprises, - In-store nudging, - NGOs do not have a place in the typology, - Linkage with year of pulses, - Stability of market, resilience of enterprise, financial sustainability of enterprise as variables

As part of this appendix, see also the three attached PDF files with the boards from the breakout sessions from the participatory modelling workshop (“Appendix6_France”, “Appendix6_IT-Swiss”, “Appendix6_PT-Nordic”). See also the PDF file containing Version 1 of the typology that was proposed at the first workshop (“Appendix6_typology”).

Appendix 7. Case studies to illustrate the typology

7.1 Active promoters

7.1.1 Genfyld - Emballagefri købmand

Source: <https://genfyld.dk/>

Country: Denmark

Date of foundation: 2020

Actor type: Shop

Main activity: Selling food/retail

Sales points: Grocery; specialty shop; organic shop

NUC Varieties sold: Swedjer rye, emmer, einkorn, spelt (cereals), fuego beans, green peas and many others (legumes)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region; same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 1

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers only,

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales to consumers: 100%

Description written by the respondent:

Genfyld [Refill - Packaging-free grocery store] gives the customer the opportunity to pick up organic dry goods and liquid soaps in their own containers. The customer decides the quantity himself and pours the goods from food dispensers and other containers into his own container. The purpose is to give the customer the opportunity to reduce packaging and food waste, as well as support primarily Danish or European growers.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification, social control, and business-to-business (B2B) verification are all used in this value chain. The qualities that are guaranteed are: Taste, size, colour, place/origin, organic and vegan qualities. Consumer feedback is another means to guarantee quality and this is solicited through interaction on social media and through direct exchanges with the customer at the point of sale.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

Many of Genfyld's first-time customers do not know the different varieties and do not know how to process/prepare them or their nutritional benefits.

Communication

Genfyld uses a range of communication strategies: online tools (i.e., own website; facebook; instagram) are used for marketing/selling purposes, content sharing and maintaining a community. Word of mouth is main means of communication about the qualities of NUCs, but talks and speeches on social media, in their shop and as part of local events, are also common. The qualities that are communicated relate to health and nutrition, environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, the diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian and promoting local agriculture.

Social Mission

Genfyld has a very large number of social missions, which include: Gluten intolerance; overconsumption of meat; food insecurity; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; and unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are lower than comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are lower, and there are low levels of competition for NUCs in the market. It is within this economic context of selling NUCs that Genfyld claims that it gains cultural, social and environmental benefits from selling NUCs.

“We are talking about the fact that it is possible to grow well-known cereals or pulses in Denmark - for example beluga lentils or quinoa. We are talking about conversion from conventional agriculture to ecology and eco-labelling. I will explain how Swedjebrug works. We are talking about Danish growers who would like to switch to growing more pulses but find it difficult to set aside their harvest. In Denmark 200 years ago many legumes were grown, but as we eat more meat they had to give way to feed for animals and we started importing the fertilisers instead... And much else... :-)”

7.1.2 Odyssee d'engrain

Source: <https://odysseedengrain-patesbio.fr/>

Country: France

Date of foundation: 2013

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production/processing

Sales points: online sale; school canteens

NUC varieties sold: Lentils, coral lentils (locally produced); ancient wheats (Poulards)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 76 - 95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 2

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale; annual contract

Type of selling to consumers: Both directly and indirectly

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly); frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 45%

Description written by the respondent:

A collective of farmers and citizens organised in a collective interest cooperative society (SCIC) and committed to agricultural biodiversity, food autonomy of territories and fair remuneration of peasant work. We produce ancient wheat and small spelt, which we transform into pasta. We also produce lentil and buckwheat/chickpea pasta. Certified organic.

Typical elements:**Guaranteeing quality**

Third party certification and consumer feedback are the two ways through which Odyseesé d'engrain guarantees quality. They also have received the prestigious France Foundation Prize. The qualities that are guaranteed are: taste, place/origin, certified organic and nutrition benefits. Consumer feedback is solicited through direct exchanges with the customer at the point of sale.

Communication

Odyseesé d'engrain has an online platform that is mostly used for marketing. In terms of communication strategies for the cooperative, they use: Word of mouth; labels, brochures/flyers, posters, radio, TV, sales point displays and exchange visits with schools where their pasta is served. They communicate about the growing conditions of their products, specifically that no chemical inputs are used, that they cultivate living soils and are certified organic. Their general communication channels and tasting campaigns are used to communicate the qualities of NUC to their consumers. The qualities that are communicated relate to health and nutrition, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy, and promoting local agriculture. In terms of active promotion, Odyseesé d'engrain conducts cooking demonstrations, talks/speeches and engages in activism. These promotional activities take place on social media and in their processing plant. However, they have also organised local and regional events in public venues.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

For lentils, production is complex and lower than demand in France, because it is cheaper to buy in Turkey or elsewhere. Long live free trade! Ah ahAhah! For ancient cereals, some of which are little known, require different agronomic techniques, adaptation/selection over several years of the ancient wheat population on each farm to achieve satisfactory

Social Mission

Odyseesé d'engrain has a very large number of social missions, which include: Obesity; Malnutrition; Gluten intolerance; Overconsumption of meat; Food insecurity; Unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; Environmental degradation; Climate change; Biodiversity decline; Unfair global trade; Unfair remuneration of producers

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher than comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are lower, and there are sometimes low levels of competition for NUCs in the market. It is within this economic context of selling NUCs that Odyseesé d'engrain claims that it gains Cultural and Social benefits from selling NUCs. They claim that the cultural benefit is winning the “cultural battle over ecology”, while the social benefit is “popularizing healthy products.”

Challenges to production, processing and selling NUCs can be resolved “first by public markets voluntarily oriented towards NUCs, then by specific subsidies for the production and processing of NUCs and by agricultural protectionism favorable to the best environmental, social and local bidder.”

7.1.3 Farm2Fork Kft.

Source: [1https://www.farm2fork.hu](https://www.farm2fork.hu)

Country: Hungary

Date of foundation: 2019

Actor type: Intermediary (online platform)

Main activity: Wholesaling; transporting or delivery service; food storage/warehouse; selling food/retail

Sales points: Online platform selling local and/or organic food

NUC varieties sold: Chickpeas; spelt (tönkölybúza); stubble turnip (vegetable); quince (fruit)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: <5%

Origin of the NUCs: Same country

Type of supply from farmers: Directly from producers

Number of intermediaries: 1-2

Type of supply contract: Long-term contract (pluriannual)

Type of selling to consumers: Directly to restaurants and consumers

Type of consumers: Repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Farm2Fork is a business that specifically sells domestic, seasonal, partially organic vegetables, fruits and processed products to restaurants and residential customers.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Farm2Fork guarantees the quality of their products by soliciting consumer feedback via email and through their own, unique, business-to-business (B2B) verification systems. The qualities that are guaranteed are: Taste, size, colour, place/origin, organic, nutrition benefits.

Communication

Farm2Fork has their own website, a Facebook page and an Instagram account – all of which are used mostly for information and content sharing. Word of mouth is their main means of communication for the initiative.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

NUCs are usually difficult to obtain as few people grow them.

Farm2Fork promotes the consumption of NUCs by communicating: Environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy. They do this communication through their online platforms and via word of mouth.

Social mission

Farm2Fork maintains eight social missions, which include: Unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; unfair global trade; unfair remuneration of producers

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins are the same for NUCs as for similar non-NUCs products. There is competition for NUCs in the market, but it is considered low. It is within this context of selling NUCs that Farm2Fork claim that they have earned extra income (economic) and protect biodiversity (environmental) because of their sales of NUCs.

Farm2Fork aims to bridge the gap between consumers and top-quality Hungarian produce. We work with farmers on a daily basis to deliver fresh vegetables and fruits to your home or restaurant and put a great emphasis on building trustworthy relationships in the meantime.

7.1.4 UnSacco, pieni di grani antichi

Healthy

We use whole and semi-whole ancient grain flours, all stone ground. Therefore, they are full of fiber and with five wheat grains to fill up on nutrients (proteins, mineral salts, vitamins) and to support intestinal well-being.

A rediscovered flavour

Each variety of wheat has peculiar flavors and aromas. We want to awaken memories of genuine pleasure that lead directly to the countryside, where our grains are grown in balance with their own microclimate.

We safeguard the environment

We select ancient grains grown in organic and rotational agriculture. We care about the health of the land and the conscious use of water. Each piece of our project tries to make its contribution to the environment: from 4.0 machinery to delivery.

Ethical

The noble work of farmers must be respected and rewarded. The agreements with the farmers do not follow stock market logic but are signed recognizing fair compensation. We want to contribute to the growth of local economies.

Certified Organic

UNSACCO is authorized for the production and distribution of organic products. Many of our recipes are certified organic, like our flours. We want to safeguard an important heritage of agricultural biodiversity, such as ancient Italian grains.

We deliver with respect

We want the whole of Milan to rediscover the authentic flavors of ancient grains. For this reason we have created an e-commerce with delivery service with the possibility of having fresh breads, focaccias and desserts at home while respecting environmental sustainability.

Source: UnSacco, pieni di grani antichi

Country: Italy

Date of foundation: 2022

Actor type: Processor

Main activity: Processing; education; selling food/retail; research; advertising/marketing/promotion/valorisation

Sales points: Specialty shop; organic shop; online platform selling local and/or organic food

NUC varieties sold: local Italian varieties of red lentils, beans, chickpeas and peas; 25 out of the 100 ancient varieties of cereals that are present in Italy

NUCs as share of commercial activity: >95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region; same country

Type of supply from farmers: Directly from farmers

Number of intermediaries: 1

Type of supply contract: Annual contract; long-term contract (multiannual)

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers only

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); frequent consumers (once a week or more); members of a loyalty program

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

We are a bakery specialised in selling bread, cakes and baked products made with Italian organic ancient varieties of grains (“grani antichi”). Furthermore, we sell products made with legumes' flours, seeds and other healthy and sustainably cultivated products. We are also specialised in vegan cakes and recipes. We have an R&D department, headed by a nutritionist with PhD, to improve recipes. We sell through one point of sale and online via e-commerce. We would like, in the future, to expand ourselves with other points of sale. We are also a benefit company and social vocation start up with the social objectives of taking care of health, environment and spread around ancient grains.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification, business-to-business (B2B) verification and consumer feedback are all used to guarantee the quality of UnSacco’s NUCs. These guaranteed qualities include: Size; colour; place/origin; organic; vegan; nutrition benefits; and ecosystem services. They complement the official certifications (e.g., organic) that they use, with what the farmers declare in terms of production, and also with what official scientific studies or trusted sources, like doctors and nutritionists, say. They solicit consumer feedback through their own website, e-mail, direct messaging on social media, and through face-to-face exchanges with the customer.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

These varieties have been cultivated in Italy for centuries from Roman and Greek times and abandoned in the 60's/60th, substituted by higher productive modern varieties, with higher gluten strength. They all have a low gluten strength, which studies showed as more digestible. During centuries, they adapted to local climate, making their cultivation naturally organic and measured as more stable in stress situations.

Communication

UnSacco uses its website, Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp for marketing/selling purposes, for information/content sharing, for creating a community around the initiative and for activism. Their typical communication strategy includes word of mouth, posters, workshops and trainings. UnSacco actively promotes NUCs through their online platform and through their typical communication strategy. They also give public talks, trainings and run campaigns out of their own location, in public venues and on social media to promote NUCs. They promote the following qualities of NUCs: health and nutrition, environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy, medical properties, diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian and local agriculture support.

Social mission

Obesity; gluten intolerance; overconsumption of meat; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher than for comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are lower, and there is high demand competition for NUCs in the market. In this difficult economic context, UnSacco declares that there are important cultural, social, and environmental benefits. Culturally, people are understanding better the value of local food culture and history, as well as, the job of the farmer and bread-maker. Socially, people are becoming more concern about their health and eating a balanced diet, and having a higher sensitivity to biodiversity and the environment. The environmental benefits of selling NUCs are a higher attention to organic, high quality, seasonal and low emission agriculture.

We buy only old varieties of grains organically cultivated; the majority certified. They are all whole or half whole (“integrale”, “tipo 1” and “tipo 2”) grains and stone milled. They are all cultivated by Italian regional small farmers, with whom we have a direct relationship. Some of them are also cultivated using crop rotations. We communicate all the healthy and environmental properties of these grains confirmed by our nutritionist, official scientific studies and trusted sources, like doctors or other scientists. Transparency is our key value. Many customers become costumers because they have previously informed themselves about our products.

7.1.4 Quinta dos 7 Nomes CRL

A Cantina Social -Boca da Mata não é um restaurante. É uma **cozinha cooperativa**, onde cada pessoa que come connosco passa a fazer parte da família. A comida é sempre **vegan** e **biológica**, com uma maioria de **ingredientes locais, de época**, privilegiando os **produtos low waste** - sem embalagens, sem resíduos, os restos são transformados em composto - e a um **preço ético**. Dos 6€ que pagas por refeição - sopa, prato e chá -2,50€ são para o cozinheiro, 2,75€ para os ingredientes, e 0,75€ para a cooperativa cobrir despesas com o espaço.

Source: Quinta dos 7 Normes CRL

Country: Portugal

Date of foundation: 2007

Actor type: Shop

Main activity: Selling food/retail

Sales points: Grocery; organic shop; open-air market/farmers' market; on-farm selling point; collective farmers' shop (including drive pick-up services)

NUC varieties sold: Grão preto (chickpea); Corasano corn; purple stick carrot (vegetable); pearl pear (fruit)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; same region; same country

Type of supply from farmers: directly from farmers

Number of intermediaries: 0

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers

Type of consumers: Repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Biological grocery store, permaculture and regenerative agriculture laboratory, social canteen

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification, social control and consumer feedback are the three ways through which Quinta dos 7 Nomes guarantees quality. The qualities that are guaranteed are: taste, size, colour, place/origin, organic, tradition, and ecosystem services. Consumer feedback is solicited through their website, email and through direct exchanges with the customers in their shop.

Communication

Quinta dos 7 Nomes has a website that is used for marketing/selling purposes, information sharing and maintaining a community around the initiative, as well as for activism. Their core communication strategy is to use the word of mouth, but posters and a monthly newsletter are also developed.

Quinta dos 7 Nomes carries out active promotion of their NUCs through online platforms, word of mouth and by using labels. They give lectures and speak on social media and in their main location. They communicate the following qualities of NUCs: Health and nutrition, environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy and the promotion of local agriculture. Growing information is part of their communication about NUCs, where they claim that the NUCs are produced locally, on a small scale, by a certified producer, with high environmental awareness. They have this information as part of an in-store display.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

[Because they are] species that are increasingly less cultivated, with a high capacity for adaptation to the environment and resilience but low productivity

Social Mission

The social mission for Quinta dos 7 Nomes is composed of claims to the following values: Malnutrition; gluten intolerance; overconsumption of meat; food insecurity; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; unfair global trade; unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, profit margins are the same as for comparable non-NUC products, and there are sometimes low levels of competition for NUCs in the market. Quinta dos 7 Nomes claims that it gains cultural, social, economic, environmental and political benefits from selling NUCs. They claim that the cultural benefit is the preservation of traditional cultivation methods, while the social benefit is “supporting local producers by creating sustainable financial networks.” Creating financial sustainability is the economic benefit, while reducing the need to use pesticides and improving local ecosystems are environmental benefits from selling NUCs. Better political awareness is also seen as a benefit from their sale of NUCs.

Quinta dos 7 Nomes was founded in November 2007, by a nucleus of seven people, and an extended group of 50 founding partners, and today has more than 600 members. It was born from a dream and a need: to connect the local community of consumers with local producers. Our philosophy is based on practical principles that we intend to increasingly bring into practice: encourage the production of organic vegetables and fruit at a local level; consume in season, locally and in bulk; raise awareness of the importance of more sustainable consumption with the lowest possible impact on the environment; promote training actions in the area of sustainability, in an attempt to make the community increasingly resilient; support production for self-sufficiency, whether in the garden, with plots, or in the store, with the sale of homemade and artisanal products; work in favour of reducing prices for organic products, practicing political prices whenever possible; create sharing spaces where families can interact, integrating all members, from grandchildren to grandparents. And everyone is welcome!

7.1.5 Biohof Las Sorts+ Bergkartoffln aus dem Albulatal

Source: Biohof Las Sorts+ Bergkartoffln aus dem Albulatal

Country: Switzerland

Date of Foundation: 2001

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production; agro-tourism; processing; education; selling food/retail

Sales points: Grocery; organic shop; on-farm selling point; online platform selling local and/or organic food

NUC varieties sold: Mountain broad beans from the Albua Valley, barley, spelt, rye, 40 varieties of vegetables, 80 varieties of fruits, potatoes, grains, fruit trees, meat from Rhaetian grey cattle (other)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 76 - 95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; same region; same country; same continent

Type of supply from farmers: Producer of NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 0

Type of supply contract: n/a

Type of selling to consumers: Directly to consumers

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly); frequent consumers (once a week or more); members of a loyalty program

Share of direct sales: 100%

Description written by the respondent:

Organic regenerative mountain farming with potatoes, spelt, perennial rye, barley, and mountain broad beans. Meat specialties from our own animals, which are kept according to kag freiland animal welfare guidelines. Sales of mountain farm products throughout Switzerland - approx. 50% gastronomy. Awareness raising potato academy. Teaching business. Mountain fruit/agroforestry.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification, social control and consumer feedback are the three ways through which Biohof Las Sorts guarantees quality. The certifications used are Bio Inspecta certified Organic, kagfreiland livestock welfare certification and the Pro Specie Rara quality seal. In 2016, they were awarded the Bio Grischun Prize. The qualities that are guaranteed are: Taste; colour; place/origin; organic; tradition; known recipes; nutrition benefits; and ecosystem services. Consumer feedback is solicited via email and social media interactions. Direct exchanges with their customers are also very important. Their products are only available seasonally.

Communication

Biohof Las Sorts has their own website and uses social media for marketing purposes, information sharing and for maintaining their community. Their general communication strategy is to use labels and loyalty promotion displays in their shops, as well as brochures and posters. They also organise workshops and ensure that they talk with their customers about what they do. NUCs are actively promoted through their normal communication channels, but Radio and TV commercials are also used. Cooking demonstrations, public talks, teaching and campaigning about NUCs are carried out on social media, on their farm, and in public venues and special local, regional and national events. The qualities of NUCs that are promoted deal with their health and nutrition qualities, the environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy, the good value for money of NUCs and their role in promoting local agriculture. They also explain the regenerative organic farming methods in mountain areas that are used to grow their NUCs.

*Why are your varieties NUCs?
Cultivation of various old, forgotten varieties. Keeping PSR? animals*

Social mission

Biohof Las Sorts does not claim to have a social mission.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher than comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are higher, and there are sometimes medium levels of competition for NUCs in the market. Biohof Las Sorts claims that it gains cultural, social, economic, and environmental benefits from selling NUCs. These benefits are: Preservation of endangered culinary heritage (cultural); regional identification of residents with our farm (social); niche production with history (economic) and organic regenerative farming (environmental).

La Sort means lot or fate in Romansh. However, we do not simply leave the future of our farm to fate, but try to actively influence it. In 2005, we were able to rebuild the stable using wood from our own forest. It now complies with the animal husbandry regulations of Bio and kag freiland, the most animal-friendly organic label in Switzerland. The preservation of potatoes, beans, cows and fruit trees that are threatened with extinction is close to our hearts, which is why we have been a Pro Specie Rara quality seal company for years. In 2016, we were awarded the Bio Grischun Prize. This prize gave and gives us motivation for the future. We knew from the start that complaining is a waste of time

and energy. In order to remain as independent as possible, we create and produce various specialties, which we market as directly as possible in the niche. In recent years we have gained a lot of experience, had to pay the price again and again, but have also been able to celebrate countless successes. With perseverance, passion and a pinch of luck, we market crazy mountain potatoes, for example, which are now also in great demand in top-class restaurants. Many thanks to all our friends, helpers and customers, without you our pure farm would not exist as it does now!!!

7.2 Silent sellers

7.2.1 Kornsang

Source: <https://kornsang.dk/>

Country: Denmark

Date of foundation: 2004

Actor type: Processor

Main activity: Food production

Selling points: Organic shop in an organic village

NUC varieties sold: Spelt, emmer, fonio, cassava (cereals), cabbage (vegetables)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: > 95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality, same continent, outside Europe

Type of supply from Farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 4

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale

Type of selling to consumers: both directly and indirectly to consumers

Type of consumers: Frequent consumers (once a week or more); members of a loyalty program

Share of direct sales: 10%

Description written by the respondent:

Bread factory with sales to institutions, health food, cafes and private individuals. Organic, sustainable, local and social.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification is the main way of guaranteeing the organic and vegan qualities of their products. Their grains are in season all year round and cabbages are fermented when harvested. Consumer feedback is collected through direct exchanges with their customers on site.

Communication

Kornsang has its own website for marketing purposes and uses facebook and instagram for information sharing. Beyond this, word of mouth and labels are used in their communication. Their online platform and the labels that they use are the means used to promote the health and nutrition qualities of NUCs. Kornsang communicates the fact that their NUCs are grown and handled in the local area and that they are organic. The importance of NUCs in promoting local agriculture is another quality that is disseminated in their activism in local events.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

*Not many bake 100% spelt bread.
Cabbage as sauerkraut is a fantastic
healthy food, but is not used that much
in Denmark*

Social mission

Kornsang claims to work with a social mission. This mission aims to fight: Gluten intolerance lack of food alternatives; overconsumption of meat; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher than comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are higher, and there are sometimes high levels of competition for NUCs in the market. Kornsang claims environmental benefits from selling NUCs, they specifically benefit from diversity and plant health.

*“The basic idea for Kornsang is social-ecological sustainability. Here proximity and health are combined with sustainability and ecology. **Proximity** because the shareholders in Under Solen a/s - who own the buildings - are predominantly local, - because all employees live within a few hundred meters of the building - and because many different types of companies live in the same building. **Health** because everything that is produced, sold and served is made from super healthy organic ingredients. **Sustainability** because rainwater, heat recovery and locally grown grain are used here. **Organic** because Kornsang produces organic products - in an organic commercial building - in an organic village.”*

7.2.2 Les Champs de blé earl

Source: <https://www.local.bio/les-champs-de-ble>

Country: France

Date of foundation: 1999

Actor type: Farmer/ processor

Main activity: Food production

Selling points:

NUC varieties sold: Red Bordeaux wheat, Poulard wheat, einkorn, oberkulmer spelled wheat (Cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 26 - 50%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region, same country

Type of supply from farmers: Producer of the NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 1

Type of supply contract: n/a

Type of selling to consumers: both directly (on farm) and indirectly to consumers (via BioCoop)

Type of consumers: Frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 90%

Description written by the respondent:

We are peasant bakers. The 75% turnover comes from the sale of bread made from cereals produced in our fields.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification is used to promote the place of origin of their products as well as their organic quality. Consumer feedback is solicited through direct contact when consumers come to their on-farm store.

Communication

Les Champs de blé earl does not have its own website, instead uses facebook to maintain their community and the local.bio online platform to sell their products. The main form of communication is through the product labels. They do not actively promote NUCs, but they do provide information that the cereals are grown organically in the online platform and through the use of labels and sales point displays.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

These are cereals that do not find buyers on the markets outside of a microcosm of very motivated and

Social Mission

No social mission was declared.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher than comparable non-NUC products, profit margins are lower, and there is no competition for NUCs in the market. Cultural and environmental benefits from selling NUCs are claimed. The fact that there is another way to grow and eat, is the cultural benefit that their receive. The environmental benefit comes from the knowledge that soil fertility can also be improved by growing cereals that have not undergone selection over the last 100 years.

“We started baking on the farm in 2004. Le Fenouil immediately started selling our bread. Since then, we have kept pace with Le Fenouil's development as new shops have opened around Le Mans. Today we sell over 400kg of bread every week in the six Le Fenouil Biocoop shops. We are on the shelves on Wednesdays and Fridays. Thank you to the pioneers of fair trade, the creators of the Le Fenouil consumer co-operative, for having pioneered a new way of distributing organic produce over 30 years ago, where farmers, processors and consumers are respected. Thank you to Le Fenouil-Biocoop and thank you, our customers and co-operators, for placing your trust in us over the past 17 years.”

7.2.3 Jóllét Műhely Egyesület

Our activities ▾ About us ▾ Things to read Archive ▾ Contact

Szolnok Basket Community

Our active activities

- ▶ Szolnok Basket Community
- ▶ You are what you eat
- ▶ Blooming Szolnok
- ▶ Common good

Recent posts

The current situation forges a community between producer and consumer

Archive

Realized projects
Gallery

Contact

5000 Szolnok, Ady E. út 5. 8/6.
+36304424197
jolletmuhelyegyesulet@gmail.com

Source: <https://jolletmuhelyegyesulet.hu/szolnoki-kosar-kozosseg/>

Country: Hungary

Date of foundation: 2021

Actor type: Intermediary – online platform

Main activity: Transporting or delivery service, selling food/retail

Selling points: Online platform selling local and/or organic food

NUC varieties sold: Spelt (tönkölybúza) (cereals), chicory, purple carrot, purple potato (vegetables)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 76 - 95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 1

Type of supply contract: Long-term contract (multiannual)

Type of selling to consumers: n/a

Type of consumers: n/a

Share of direct sales: <5%

Description written by the respondent:

The main activity of our community is to deliver the high nutritional content and chemical-free products of local small and primary producers, at subsidised prices to the widest possible audience of customers. In this way, support the survival and growth of producers, as well as the access to quality food for our conscious customers. The organisation acts as a transfer point between the producer and the end user.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Jóllét Múhely Egyesület relies upon Third party certification, Self-declaration and consumer feedback as ways to guarantee the nutrition benefits of their NUCs. Their organisation deals with local products, including seasonality from local features. Therefore, they cannot ensure the availability of seasonal products all year round.

Communication

Jóllét Múhely Egyesület maintains a website and uses social media (i.e., Facebook, Instagram, TikTok) to market, share content, maintain their community and conduct activism. The association organises workshops and their customers hear about them via word of mouth. They do not actively promote NUCs.

Why are your varieties NUCs?
Little known products. Many times, customers do not even know their usage options.

Social mission

Jóllét Múhely Egyesület is an association that works with a social mission that aims to fight against unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices, biodiversity decline and unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are comparable to non-NUCs products. There is a medium level of competition for NUCs in the market. Jóllét Múhely Egyesület claims that it provides environmental benefits, specifically biodiversity support, from selling NUCS.

“The Szolnok Basket Association coordinates the supply of local producers with the demand. They organise their work based on the small producers' decree, so they contact farmers within a forty-kilometre radius of the county seat and the city in order to ensure that really fresh goods can be put on the tables of families. Many people are looking for alternative ways of shopping, a good example of which is the basket community (...). The Szolnok Basket Community not only provides an interface but also help our customers with a basket system as a community transfer point. The producer prepares the orders in boxes, which the volunteers transform into the customers' personal baskets.”

7.2.4 Azienda agricola Zordan Tiziano

LA FILIERA | I NOSTRI SOCI | VARIETÀ DI CEREALI ANTICHI | EVENTI | CONTATTI

Country: Italy

Date of foundation: 1875

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production

Selling points: None

NUC varieties sold: Autonomy, Villa Glory, Frassineto, Inallettabile, Canove, Piave, Gentil Rosso, Cobra Q population, Cobra A population, Mixture 180, Li Rosi durum wheat mixture, einkorn variety Haermanni (cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 26 - 50%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region, same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly, producer of the NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 1 supply intermediary, at least 1 selling intermediary (but actual number not known)

Type of supply contract: Annual contract

Type of selling to consumers: indirectly to consumers

Type of consumers: consumers not known

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

With my small 4-hectare agricultural property located in Villa Estense (Padova), I collaborate with another 14-hectare organic farm, adjacent to mine, owned by Montecchio Luigino. With this collaboration, we are able to carry out longer rotations for cereals. In recent years, we have joined the "Let's cultivate diversity" and "consemi" projects, coordinated by Rete Semi Rurali. These projects aim to promote the development of innovative, local and sustainable supply chains and the preservation of genetic diversity and conservation/ dissemination of local and traditional peasant seeds, suitable for organic farming and the different soil and climate conditions of the territories. Within these initiatives, starting from a small quantity of seeds that were made available to us, we reproduced a quantity of seed sufficient for sowing and open-field harvesting. In here we multiplied a certain number of species, varieties and populations of grains local and traditional so-called ancient ones, including: Autonomia, Villa Glory, Frassineto, Inallettibile, Canove, Piave, Gentil Rosso, Senatore Cappelli, Cobra Q population, Cobra A population, mixture 180, Li Rosi duri mixture, and the einkorn variety Haermanni.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Azienda agricola Zordan Tiziano uses Organic Third-party certification to guarantee the quality of his NUCs. Sometimes grains are stored before sale, so he is able to extend his season.

Communication

There is no website, but there is a Facebook page and the farm can be found on the website of Crescent Short Organic Chain for Ancient Grains.

Social Mission

Azienda agricola Zordan Tiziano does not work with a social mission.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are higher than for non-NUCs products and they do not know what the market competition is like for their NUCs. Economic and environmental benefits from selling NUCs are recognized by Tiziano Zordan. He claims that economic benefits are generated from the fact that they require fewer technical means to grow them, so the benefit comes when you manage to find a buyer who values them with the right price. In terms of environmental benefits, NUCs do not require fertilisation but only rotations with intercropped green manures. NUCs have good competition against wild plants.

"We are well aware that none of the seeds we grow are or can be ours. Ours is rather the ability to empathise with them, understand their needs, their ability to adapt, understand their characteristics and peculiarities. Our commitment is the ability to guarantee healthy and fertile soil where these can grow, furthermore, ours may also be the ability to select new populations of plants that blend well with the pedo-climatic peculiarities of our territory. (Crescent)"

Why are your varieties NUCs?

Because they were selected and reproduced within the "Let's grow diversity" and "semi-seed" projects, coordinated by Rete Semi Rurali, with the aim of promoting the development of innovative, local and sustainable supply chains and promoting the preservation of genetic diversity

7.2.5 Terra bio Lda

Source: <https://www.facebook.com/terrabiocb/about>

Country: Portugal

Date of Foundation: 2018

Actor type: Shop

Main activity: Selling food/retail

Selling points: Grocery; organic shop

NUC varieties sold: Khorasan wheat (cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Outside Europe

Type of supply from farmers: indirectly

Number of intermediaries: >1, the number of supply intermediaries are not known

Type of supply contract: n/a

Type of selling to consumers: Directly to consumers

Type of consumers: Repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Certified store specializing in organic products, with sections for gluten-free, vegan and vegetarian products, cosmetics and animal feed. It aims to make organic products available to the entire community, as well as, raise awareness and promote the importance of this form of production and encourage local producers to opt for this method of production. We value local and national production and strive to have the greatest possible representation of national products.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification is used to certify the organic quality of the NUCs. The Khorasan wheat is imported and they have it on the shelf throughout the year.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

They were used ancestrally, but difficult to obtain nowadays

Communication

Terra bio Lda maintains a Facebook page used to support the community around their initiative. Their main means of communication is word of mouth, but they do not actively promote NUCs.

Social mission

Terra bio Lda does not declare to be working with a social mission.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are higher compared to non-NUCs products and there is no competition for NUCs in their market. Terra bio Lda claims that the sales of NUCs provide no additional benefits.

Yesterday was the day, on the way home, to stop at this new store. It would just be to get to know you, but who can resist? Large and with room to grow; with light and full of colour; meat/fish, milk, but also vegan products for those who, like me, want it; friendliness without exaggeration on the part of the owner; openness to look for other products that the grocery store doesn't yet have, and a variety of products that range from essential to delicious: I'm obviously a customer! I wish "Terra Bio" a long and healthy life.

7.2.6 Boställets vedugnsbageri

Ring Oss På 076 127 30 22

Följ oss på

...och på

Bread Both About Boställets Our Bread Packed lunch The residence's café Here You Find Us News Contact Us

The residence's wood-fired bakery is us

We have lived in Maspelösa Boställe for almost 18 years and we feel very comfortable here. Me (Karin), Ulf and our three children Algot, Ebba and Ester. Since 2011, I have run Boställets wood oven bakery and café in the old barn.

Since we moved here, I have thought about whether it would be possible to start something of my own to be able to work from home. I don't really know how the idea of baking bread popped into my head. In and of itself, I have always baked and when I started experimenting with sourdough and reading everything possible about sourdough baking, a seed was planted. We had a large empty barn here on the farm and it could be used as a bakery. Now Boställets wood oven bakery is a cozy excursion destination where several generations meet in the countryside for a good coffee in a lovely setting.

Since October 2011, Boställets wood oven bakery and café has been completed.

OPENING HOURS

Thursday - Friday 10-17
Saturday 10-16
Sunday 11-16

BLOG

We have Christmas holidays until January 11
Closed for rest and repair of our furnace.
This is Bostället - my picture
Weed soup
We are still open

HERE YOU FIND US!

On Facebook

Source: <https://bostallets.se/om-oss/>

Country: Sweden

Date of foundation: 2011

Actor type: Processor

Main activity: Agro-tourism; bakery café

Selling points:

NUC varieties sold: Emmer, spelt, Öland wheat and old local varieties (cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality, same region, same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 2 supply intermediaries

Type of supply contract: Verbal contracts with neighbour

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly); frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Bakery and café in the countryside. I mainly use locally produced products.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Quality control is conducted by their suppliers – either the mills or the farmers themselves. The guaranteed qualities are taste; colour, protein levels, and lot number. Their wheat is stored and milled throughout the year.

Communication

Boställets vedugnsbageri maintains their own webpage as well as a Facebook page and an Instagram account. All of these online platforms are used for selling their products. The general communication strategy is to talk about their initiative and hold workshops. They do not actively promote NUCs, however, in the store consumers are informed about the local variety grown in the local area and the good baking properties (e.g., gluten-free).

Why are your varieties NUCs?

I use the NUC varieties because they give good bread and are useful. They also preserve biodiversity compared to large corporate varieties. Some can withstand drought better.

Social Mission

Boställets vedugnsbageri does not work with a social mission.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are higher when compared to non-NUCs products and there is no competition for NUCs in their market. Boställets vedugnsbageri claims receiving environmental benefits, specifically diversity preservation, from selling NUCs. A culinary benefit is also claimed by this store, which is that it tastes good and makes beautiful bread.

“Flour, water and salt, that's all you need to bake good bread. We bake with sourdough that is left to rest for a long time to develop flavours. The long fermentation time also means that nutrients in the flour become more readily available to our body. In the bakery, we mainly use organic grain grown in Östergötland and ground into flour at Orga mill. From Warbro mill in Södermanland, we buy whole grain flour from einkorn and other older types of grain. Since recently, we also have a small stone mill and can grind wholemeal flour ourselves for some breads. We are happy that we can bake Öland wheat and emmer, etc produced by a farmer in Grannbyn. We bake different kinds of bread, mainly with rye and wheat, but also, more and more, whole grain bread with older varieties.”

7.2.7 Verein Erlebniswelt Roggen Erschmatt

Source: <https://www.erschmatt.ch/en/botanic-reserve/>

Country: Switzerland

Date of Foundation: 2003

Actor type: Other – Botanic reserve

Main activity: Advertising/marketing/promotion/valorisation; research

Selling points: n/a

NUC varieties sold: *Vicia faba*: 15 varieties (legumes), rye, wheat, barley, maize: many varieties (cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 76 - 95%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region, same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 1 supply intermediary

Type of supply contract: A variety of contracts are used depending on the project

Type of selling to consumers: Not selling to consumers

Type of consumers: n/a

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Since its foundation in 2003, the non-profit association Erlebniswelt Roggen has been committed to the preservation, enhancement and further development of the natural and cultural heritage related to rye. It promotes efforts and projects for the preservation of the cultural landscape and biological diversity. In addition, the association is committed to promoting a diverse cultural life in and around Erschmatt through public events (concerts, readings, communal events, thematic village tours, etc.). The botanical garden offers a home to ancient Valais cultivated plants. These traditional crops are nowadays rarely planted but they are part of the biodiversity and cultural heritage of the people of Valais. The diversity of these old varieties is important as a reservoir for future new varieties. The field flora to be found in the reserve include rare beautiful plant species that are also part of the region's biological diversity. Activities: - preservation of old varieties and rare field flora of our region Valais - research: how can those varieties be used/cultivated on a bigger scale? - guided visits, group visits - small

production of seeds - transmit the knowledge around the varieties, the tradition of rye production and processing - consulting to farmers, gardeners.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

No qualities are guaranteed for NUCs in this initiative.

Communication

Verein Erlebniswelt Roggen Erschmatt maintains their own website and a Facebook page, both focused on information sharing and maintaining their community. Their general communication strategy focuses on providing brochures and flyers about their seeds and spreading the word through verbal communication and in workshops. They do not actively promote NUCs. However, they give indications on how to grow the seeds. They do not sell NUC-based products beyond the seeds.

*Why are your varieties NUCs?
These varieties are not cultivated by farmers anymore, even though they originate from this region.*

Social mission

This association is dedicated to curbing biodiversity decline and more specifically to the preservation, enhancement and further development of the natural and cultural heritage related to rye.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are higher when compared to non-NUCs products and it is not known what the market competition is like for the NUCs. Verein Erlebniswelt Roggen Erschmatt does not receive any additional benefits from selling NUCs.

The Erschmatt Botanic Reserve (Sortengarten) was created in 1985 when traditional Valais rye was still cultivated in the village. Fields of wheat, barley and oats were also to be seen. You could see several rare field flowers such as corn cockle (Agrostemma githago) or prickly poppy (Papaver argemone) in the fields. So, this was an ideal place to set up a Botanic Reserve to cultivate and display Valais cultivated plants in all their diversity.

7.3 Quality Communicators

7.3.1 Torup Spisehus

Torup Spisehus is buying produce from

Meat, milk & vegetables from Engmosegaard 1,5km

Vegetables from Andelsgaarde 3,3km

Game from Grønnessegaard 4km

Flour from Fællesmølleriet 4km

Vegetables from Sølager 5,8km

Beer from Det Våde Får 23,4km

Fish from Fiskeri kajen 60km

Icecream and cheese from Tothaven 4,4km

Artworks

Mains, sandcast iron, 2019, Asta Lyngé

Source: <https://torupspisehus.dk/en>

Country: Denmark

Date of foundation: 2020

Actor type: Processor, restaurant

Main activity: Food service

Selling points: Restaurant

NUC varieties sold: Chickpeas, horse beans, beluga lentils, puy lentils (legumes), red wheat, purple wheat (cereals), skorzone roots (vegetables)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 2 supply intermediaries

Type of supply contract: Long-term contract (multiannual)

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales:

Description written by the respondent:

Restaurant with a focus on local and organic ingredients. We make all the food from scratch, make our own cheeses, hams and bread according to old principles. For our evening menus, we only use ingredients sourced within a 7 km radius of the restaurant, except for oil, vinegar and salt. Our menu is predominantly vegetarian, with small amounts of meat, if at all.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

The restaurant relies upon self-declaration to guarantee the qualities of taste, place/origin and organic to their consumers. They also solicit consumer feedback through direct exchanges in the restaurant. They use both fresh and dried legumes, in and out of the season. They use grains primarily in dried form for bread.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

I am not an expert, and it may well be that the varieties I mention are not NUCs. However, I found the range of pulses, grains and vegetables to be very limited to very few varieties.

Communication

Torup Spisehus has a website and an Instagram account that is used for marketing purposes. Their general communication strategy is via word of mouth and brochures. They use these means to promote NUCs. They promote the following qualities of their NUCs: Environmental/landscape preservation; (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration; culture and gastronomy (preserving identity and heritage); and diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian. The restaurant engages in teaching and speaking about NUCs in their other locations. They also explain to their customers that their NUCs are locally grown or grown in Denmark.

Social mission

Torup Spisehus does not articulate a specific social mission.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are lower and profit margins are lower when compared to non-NUCs products, and there is no competition for NUCs in their market. Torup Spisehus claims that it gains cultural and environmental benefits from selling NUCs because they show that they are keeping up with the times and the transition to a more plant-based diet.

Torup Spisehus is located in Dyssekilde ecovillage, Torup. Torup Spisehus focuses on organic and local produce, and works closely with the producers and suppliers on the surrounding farms, mill and brewery. At Torup Spisehus everything is made from scratch: meat is cured in the backroom, fresh cheese made from local milk, vegetables fermented, kombucha brewed, and sourdough bread baked.”

7.3.2 Earl la Ferme du Bois du Treuil

Country: France

Date of foundation: 1990

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production; processing; selling food/retail

Selling points: Organic shop; on-farm selling point; community-Supported Agriculture

NUC varieties sold: Red of Bordeaux, Red of Lot, Red of Morvan, Red of Roc, Carré de Crête, Touzelle (wheat and einkorn - cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 26 - 50%

Origin of the NUCs: Same country

Type of supply from farmers: Producer of NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 1 selling intermediary

Type of supply contract: None

Type of selling to consumers: both directly and indirectly to consumers

Type of consumers: Frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 75%

Description written by the respondent:

We are an organic farm with large crops of 110 hectares. We transform the cereals produced on our land into flour and then into bread. We have cereal storage and sorting tools. We also have an Astrié type mill (stone millstone) for grinding cereals as well as a wood-fired oven for making bread. We sell flour and bread directly (farm store, market, AMAP) as well as in organic stores. We use population (old) varieties of soft wheat and einkorn.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

The farm and bakery use third party certification to guarantee the origin, taste and organic quality of their NUCs.

TARIFS ET PRODUITS

TARIFS 2024

FARINES			PAINS AU LEVAIN		
Type	Taille sac	Prix	Type	500 g	1 kg
Blés Anciens	1 kg	2,30 €	Pain de campagne	2,90 €	4,80 €
	5 kg	10,50 €	Pain complet	2,90 €	4,80 €
	10 kg	20 €	Pain aux graines	3,40 €	5,70 €
	25 kg	45 €	Pain aux noix	3,80 €	6,30 €
Épeautre	1 kg	3,70 €	Pain d'épeautre	3,70 €	6,10 €
	5 kg	17,50 €	Pain d'engrain	4,40 €	7,50 €
	10 kg	34 €	Pain au sarrasin	4 €	---
Engrain	1 kg	4,90 €	Pain Spécial	4,90 €	---
	5 kg	23,50 €	Brioche 400g	4,70 €	---
	10 kg	46 €			
Sarrasin	1 kg	3,70 €			
	5 kg	17 €			
	10 kg	32 €			
Seigle ou Maïs	1 kg	2,90 €			
	5 kg	13,50 €			
	10 kg	26 €			

LÉGUMES SECS (1KG)

Lentilles Vertes 4,60 €

Source: <https://www.farinepainbio.com/home>

They actively solicit consumer feedback through direct exchanges with the customer on the farm or in their bakery.

Communication

Earl la Ferme du Bois du Treuil has a website, a Facebook page and an Instagram account that are all used for information sharing. They use word of mouth and labels to communicate about their initiative. Active NUCs promotion is conducted online, through their normal communication channels and through public talks in their main location. The qualities that they promote include: Health and nutrition; environmental/landscape preservation; (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration; and the promotion of local agriculture.

Social mission

No social mission declared

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, and profit margins are higher when compared to non-NUCs products, and there are sometimes low levels of competition for NUCs in the market. Earl la Ferme du Bois du Treuil claims that it gains cultural and economic benefits from selling NUCs. They claim that the cultural benefit is safeguarding genetic heritage, while the economic benefit is a more attractive selling price.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

These are landrace varieties gradually abandoned during the 20th century in favor of lineal or hybrid varieties.

“Peasant Bakers since 2006, we have been growing cereals which we transform into flour on site with a stone mill. Then, we make organic sourdough bread cooked in a wood-fired oven. From the land to the plate, we cover the entire sector.”

7.3.3 Toscanatura Bio

Source: <https://www.toscanaturabio.it/> 2

Country: Italy

Date of foundation: 2016

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Inputs production; food production; agro-tourism; wholesaling; blogging; other

Selling points: n/a

NUC varieties sold: Lupine (legumes), quinoa, amaranth, chia (seeds)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; outside Europe

Type of supply from farmers: Producer of NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 1 selling intermediary

Type of supply contract: n/a

Type of selling to consumers: both directly and indirectly to consumers

Type of consumers: One-off consumers (single purchase); repeat consumers (once monthly)

Share of direct sales: 30%

Description written by the respondent:

Our company is located in Tuscany. In our farm, we produce and sell under the brand Toscanatura Bio quinoa, teff, amaranth, flaxseed and flaxseed oil. In the same farm, we have a country house. Furthermore, under the brand tuttoquinoa (www.tuttoquinoa.com), we produce and sell seeds for sowing to farmers and we have developed a supply chain of quinoa in Italy (from seed to table) in collaboration with our partner specialised in processing. On our website, we have a blog about pseudo cereals and minor crops farming. We have a project about lupins and we are trying to maintain a local accession. This year we will try a new lupine supply agreement from South America to evaluate their alkaloids content.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Toscanatura Bio does not guarantee the quality of their NUCs. However, they do solicit consumer feedback via email.

Communication

Toscanatura Bio uses Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, LinkedIn and Mangia Locale online platforms to share information and maintain a community around the initiative. They communicate more generally via word of mouth, brochures and in trade fairs. They actively promote their NUCs through their normal communication channels and through online and in person seminars in off-farm locations. They communicate the following qualities of their NUCs: Health and nutrition; environmental/landscape preservation; (agro-)biodiversity conservation/restoration; and medical properties. Farm visits are organised and they provide information in the online platforms in order to share the growing information with their consumers.

Social mission

No social mission

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are lower and profit margins are higher compared to non-NUCs products, and there are sometimes medium levels of competition for NUCs in the market. Toscanatura Bio claims that they gain no additional benefits from selling NUCs.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

All these crops have been abandoned, for different reasons, during so much time. Some of them have probably been abandoned for the trouble in processing (LupineLupin or quinoa), some others for cultural or religious reasons.

*“The small size allows family management and scrupulous and constant control over our crops. All processes are carried out using non-invasive techniques, reducing mechanical interventions to a minimum. **We believe that food must be produced with respect for nature, and we try to express this concept not only in the field, but also in packaging. In fact, from 2024 we have decided to only sell the product "by weight", in paper packages, reducing costs waste and energy consumption.** All our products are grown without resorting to irrigation, relying only on the water that nature offers us from the sky, and completely eliminating the consumption of this important and increasingly scarce resource.”*

7.3.4 Artisan Bread AB

Opening hours

Newsletter

A modern artisan bakery that offers bread, pastry and coffee in a beautiful setting.

info@artisanbread.se
054-15 32 00
Kasernhöjden 4, Karlstad

INSTAGRAM FACEBOOK

MON - FRI
08.00 - 18.00

SATURDAY
08.00 - 16.00

SUNDAY
09.00 - 16.00

MAY 1st WE CELEBRATE 10 YEARS! 09.00-16.00.

Source: <https://artisanbread.se/>

Country: Sweden

Date of foundation: 2014

Actor type: Processor

Main activity: Selling food/retail

Selling points: Specialty shop (e.g. bakery, butchery, fruit and vegetable shop...)

NUC varieties sold: old country varieties, such as gray pea, Gotland lentil, vreta yellow (legumes), country wheat varieties, Dala country wheat, Värmland wheat, Västgöta wheat, emmer, einkorn (cereals)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 51 - 75%

Origin of the NUCs: Same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 1 supply intermediary

Type of supply contract: No written contracts

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers

Type of consumers: Frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 100%

Description written by the respondent:

Bakery/Café

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Artisan Bread does not guarantee the qualities of its NUCs.

Communication

Artisan Bread uses Instagram for marketing and information sharing. They also promote NUCs through this online platform. They highlight the following qualities of NUCs: Health and nutrition; environmental/landscape preservation; (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration; culture and gastronomy (preserving identity and heritage); and promoting local agriculture. They speak to their customers over the counter to explain that artificial fertilisers are not used in the growing of their NUCs.

*Artisan bakery/patisserie/café in
Karlstad, Sweden. Everything from
scratch. Organic.*

Social mission

There is no social mission for Artisan Bread AB.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, and profit margins are lower when compared to non-NUCs products, and there is no competition for NUCs in their market. Artisan Bread claims that it does gain economic and environmental benefits from selling NUCs. Their NUCs help them to create local economies and avoid input funds.

"A modern artisan bakery that offers bread, pastry and coffee in a beautiful setting. Open every day. Welcome to us!"

7.4 Mission first

7.4.1 La Cagette de Montpellier

La Cagette de Montpellier

The first cooperative and participatory non-profit supermarket in Montpellier, whose members participate for three hours every four weeks and are the only owners, the only decision-makers and the only customers.

Source: <https://lacagette-coop.fr/?PagePrincipale>

Country: France

Date of foundation: 2017

Actor type: Shop

Main activity: Selling food/retail

Selling points: Supermarket/hypermarket (including delivery, pick-up services); frozen food shop; organic shop

NUC varieties sold: all varieties of legumes; spelt, buckwheat (cereals); kohlrabi, parsnips, Jerusalem artichokes

NUCs as share of commercial activity: <5%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; same region; same country; same continent; outside Europe

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: >2, the exact number of intermediaries in their long supply chains are not known

Type of supply contract: They work with producers over the long term, some with annual volume planning. On the other hand, nothing is contractual.

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers only

Type of consumers: Repeat consumers (once monthly); frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 100%

Description written by the respondent:

Offer an alternative to mass distribution accessible to all. A complete range of products: food, hygiene, maintenance, etc. A non-profit supermarket: no dividend paid! Everything is reinvested in the Cooperative. Total transparency on the margin made. A place for exchange, sharing and debate on food.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

La Cagette does not guarantee the NUCs quality, but seek consumer feedback through email and surveys with members via online forms. They try to make seasonal NUCs identifiable on the shelves.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

It seems to me that all varieties of vegetables can be useful to achieve a less processed, healthy and ecological diet.

Communication

La Cagette has its own website and use Facebook, Instagram and peertube for marketing, for information sharing, for creating a community and for activism. They have a communication strategy that is organised around the use of word of mouth, brochures/flyers, posters, workshops/trainings, radio, TV, and sales point displays. There is active promotion of NUCs using the core communication strategy, but La Cagette also indicates the local origin of the producer. They produce a newsletter that includes their promotion of NUCs and organise events, cooking demonstrations, give talks and conduct activism around NUCs in their store and in other locations and local events. The qualities of NUCs that they promote are focused on their socio-economic aspects and include: culture and gastronomy; affordable price; good value for money; and their role promoting local agriculture.

Social mission

La Cagette is a mission first participatory consumer cooperative whose members work in the store 3-4 hours per month. They are the only decision-makers and customers in the cooperative. Their mission is to fight against: Obesity; malnutrition; gluten intolerance lack of alternative food products; overconsumption of meat; food insecurity; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; unfair global trade; and the unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, and profit margins are the same when compared to non-NUCs products, and there are high levels of competition for NUCs in the market. La Cagette claims that it gains cultural, social, economic, environmental and political benefits from selling NUCs. Learning to cook recipes and their producer-consumer meetings have created a better understanding of each other’s issues (cultural benefits). Social connection, mutual aid, neighbourhood atmosphere are social benefits. The economic benefits come from their business model whereby the cooperative sells more to its members and buys more from its suppliers. Consumers benefit from their unique low margin system and the non-profit purpose of the structure. Environmental benefits are gains from producers whose environmental methods are virtuous and can find new outlets and increase their production. The political benefit comes from the dissemination of environmental, economic, social and therefore political issues among all stakeholders.

“We sell products from long supply chains of which we only know the mandatory legal notices (origin, allergens). We therefore do not provide any further information on these products. We also sell products from direct channels on which we can provide more precise information (production methods, problems encountered by producers, taste

qualities, preparation methods, labels, etc.). On these products, we try to provide complex information: for example, surveys carried out by our committee to better understand our supply chains, allowing us to send articles to all our members via our newsletter. That said, it's very time-consuming and we don't do it enough... it's frustrating and we'd like to do it more and better."

7.4.2 MagosVölgy Ökológiai Gazdaság

Source: <https://magosvolgy.hu/>

Country: Hungary

Date of foundation: 2014

Actor type: Intermediary – community supported agriculture

Main activity: Food production

Sales point: On farm distribution

NUC varieties sold: Fava bean

NUCs as share of commercial activity: <5%

Origin of the NUCs: Same region; same continent

Type of supply from farmers: Indirectly only

Number of intermediaries: 2 supply intermediaries

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale; Annual contract

Type of selling to consumers: Directly to consumers only

Type of consumers: Members of a loyalty program

Share of direct sales: 100%

Description written by the respondent:

Mixed organic vegetable cultivation, in an agricultural system supported by the community, with annual commitment, unit share, advance payment, with 150 vegetable community members.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

MagosVölgy does not guarantee quality to their consumers beyond gaining consumer feedback through interaction on social media and through direct exchanges with the customers on their farm. They sell their NUCs only in season when they are fresh.

Communication

MagosVölgy maintains a website and a Facebook page that have multiple uses. These are: marketing purposes, information sharing, maintain a community around the initiative and for activism. The main communication strategy for the initiative is to use labels, word of mouth and workshops or trainings. They actively promote NUCs in their online platforms and through their verbal communication. The qualities of NUCs that they promote include: Health and nutrition, their role in the diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian and what they can do to promote local agriculture. They do explain the growing conditions and the difficulties that they face to their consumers.

Social mission

MagosVölgy Ökológiai Gazdaság has a very large number of social missions, which include: unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices, environmental degradation, biodiversity decline, and unfair remuneration of producers.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

Their fresh consumption in Hungary and their production as a fresh product are not known or barely known.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, and profit margins are higher when compared to non-NUCs products, and there is no competition for NUCs in their market.

MagosVölgy has declared to gain environmental benefits from selling NUCs because legumes are favourable in the crop rotation and there is also a culinary benefit which is that the vegetable palette is wider for members of the vegetable community.

"We carry out controlled organic farming in MagosVölgy. This means that we comply with the conditions of organic farming, we farm according to the EU and Hungarian legal framework. We have a contract with a certification organisation, which in our case is Bio Garancia Kft. However, what is really important to us is not the "official" paper, but rather that we can operate and produce food in harmony with nature as much as possible. The members of the vegetable community, our children and we eat the same."

7.4.3 Tularù Società agricola

Source: <https://www.tularu.it/>

Country: Italy

Date of foundation: 2016

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production; agro-tourism; processing; transporting or delivery service; advertising/marketing/promotion/valorisation; education

Selling points: On farm

NUC varieties sold: Rieti wheat

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 26 - 50%

Origin of the NUCs: Same municipality; same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly, producer of NUCs

Number of intermediaries: 1 supply intermediary, 1 selling intermediary

Type of supply contract: Long-term contract (multiannual)

Type of selling to consumers: Both directly and indirectly to consumers

Type of consumers: Frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: 65%

Description written by the respondent:

We cultivate local traditional wheat, in rotation with rational pasture raised cows and we cultivate a regenerative garden. We transform the wheat in bread, we sell the meat directly to the consumers and we transform the vegetables for the kitchen in the agro-tourism. We organise several meetings and parties related to the agricultural process.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification and consumer feedback are the two ways through which Tularù guarantees quality. The qualities that are guaranteed are: Organic. Consumer feedback is solicited through direct exchanges with the customers on their farm and through interaction on social media. Their wheat can be easily stored during the year and they mill it when necessary.

Communication

Tularù maintains their own website as well as a Facebook page, an Instagram account and WhatsApp groups. These are used for marketing, information sharing, and maintaining the community around their initiative. For general communication, they use the word of mouth, brochures and workshops.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

It is the local wheat variety used as starter by Nazareno Strampelli for the first wheat crossing in early 1900's/1900s.

They are actively promoting NUCs online and through their general communication. They promote the following qualities of NUCs: their health and nutrition characteristics, their role in environmental and landscape preservation and (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration. They explain their role in culture and gastronomy and in promoting local agriculture. They provide information through their general forms of communication about the regenerative agriculture and rotation with cows, which are part of the growing practices. At their agro-tourism centre, they also teach this information about NUCs.

Social mission

Tularù is mission first. They are fighting against: unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity decline; unfair global trade; and unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher and profit margins are lower when compared to non-NUCs products, and there are sometimes low levels of competition for NUCs in the market.

Tularù claims cultural, social, economic, environmental and political benefits from selling NUCs. They claim that the cultural benefit is sharing the responsibility for a better environment. The economic benefit is increasing the value of the wheat, while the environmental benefit is increasing the organic matter in the soil. The political benefit is creating a local community aware of the importance of the protection of the landscape.

“Tularù is a concrete response (firstly by 2 people but progressively by a group of people) to satisfy the need to escape the extractive paradigm on which contemporary society is based. Having had the opportunity to use a fundamental means of production such as land, the intention was to take back the responsibility of caring for and regenerating it and to share this responsibility with the territory.”

7.4.4 Quinta do Arneiro

Source: <https://quintadoarneiro.pt/>

Country: Portugal

Date of Foundation: 2007

Actor type: Farmer

Main activity: Food production; processing; transporting or delivery service; selling food/retail; organic production

Sales points: Organic shop; open-air market/farmers' market; on-farm selling point; online sale of organic baskets with home delivery

NUC varieties sold: all indigenous varieties of legumes or legume varieties normally consumed in the country; ancient varieties of cereals such as Barbela wheat among others

NUCs as share of commercial activity: <5%

Origin of the NUCs: Same country; same continent

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: 1-2

Type of supply contract: 1 time sale

Type of selling to consumers: directly to consumers

Type of consumers: Repeat consumers (once monthly); frequent consumers (once a week or more)

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

Organic vegetable and fruit production farm. Transformation of surplus and Bread production. We purchase products to add to those produced by us. Direct sale to the end consumer through online sale of baskets, with home delivery. Sale at street markets on Saturdays, and sale at the grocery store existing on the farm. All products sold are certified organic and there is a restaurant on the farm. They say that knowledge does not take up any space, but we believe it does. Knowledge can take up space, soul and heart. Learning or remembering can help us change.

Change habits, change the way we see things, change our way of being. And that is why we think it is essential to teach and to help remember. At the farm academy we have workshops and more in-depth courses on a myriad of subjects, but all have in common a real concern for sustainability and the preservation of this planet of ours. What we do, what we eat, what we consume, how we consume...

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

Third party certification and consumer feedback are the two ways through which Quinta do Arneiro guarantees quality. The qualities that are guaranteed are: place/origin, organic and nutrition benefits. Consumer feedback is solicited through their website, via a contact form, via email and through direct messaging on social media.

Why do you consider your products to be NUCs?

Because they are products of high nutritional quality that are no longer produced due to lack of profitability, due to intensive production and genetic manipulation

Communication

Quinta do Arneiro maintains a website that is used for marketing and maintaining a community around their initiative. The general communication strategy is to rely up on labels, flyers and posters, but also by word of mouth. Quinta do Arneiro does carry out active promotion of their NUCs through online platforms, word of mouth and by using labels. They hold workshops in their Academy and run promotional campaigns on social media and in their main location, but they are also active in local and regional events. They communicate the following qualities of NUCs: environmental/landscape preservation, (agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration, culture and gastronomy and the promotion of local agriculture. They provide growing information to their consumers through their normal communication strategy by explaining that the NUCs products are produced organically and in Portugal.

Social mission

Quinta do Arneiro is strongly mission driven whereby their company claims to fight: Malnutrition; overconsumption of meat; food fraud; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; environmental degradation; biodiversity decline; unfair global trade; unfair remuneration of producers.

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices for NUCs are higher, and profit margins are higher compared to non-NUCs products, and they face high levels of competition for their NUCs in the market. It is within this economic context of selling NUCs that Quinta do Arneiro claims that it gains economic and environmental benefits from selling NUCs. The economic benefit is the revitalisation and sale of national products, while NUC cultivation helps to improve soil quality, thus bringing an environmental benefit from their sale.

As a result of hard work, dedication, will and stubbornness, we have managed to overcome many obstacles and grow a company that makes us proud every day. Has it been easy? No. Do we feel like it has been worth it? Yes. And it is a great joy to know that we have led so many families to change their eating habits, to start consuming organic products, to become more aware and concerned about the environment. It is a family project that would not be possible without the help of all those who work here. We are proud of what was done. And we still have much to do. We work so that the day never comes when we can say: "Mission accomplished."

7.4.5 AGRIDEA

Your centre for Agricultural Advisory and Extension Services

As an independent knowledge centre, AGRIDEA has been proactively promoting sustainable and practice-oriented solutions in the Swiss agricultural and food industry since 1958. With around 120 employees in Lindau, Lausanne and Cadenazzo, the association networks various stakeholders with agronomic and methodological know-how and offers courses, projects, publications and software in the framework of strong partnerships.

Source: <https://www.agridea.ch/en/>

Country: Switzerland

Date of foundation: 1958

Actor type: Education

Main activity: Food production/processing

Selling points: On farm

NUC varieties sold: Lentils, broad beans, chickpeas (legumes)

NUCs as share of commercial activity: 5 - 25%

Origin of the NUCs: Same country

Type of supply from farmers: Both directly and indirectly

Number of intermediaries: Unknown

Type of supply contract: Unknown

Type of selling to consumers: Not concerned with the sale of food

Type of consumers: n/a

Share of direct sales: n/a

Description written by the respondent:

As an independent knowledge hub, AGRIDEA has been proactively committed to sustainable, down-to-earth solutions in the Swiss agriculture and food industry since 1958.

Typical elements:

Guaranteeing quality

AGRIDEA does not guarantee quality. However, they are conducting research and farmer advice on organic farming.

Communication

AGRIDEA has an online platform that is mostly used for information sharing. They are actively promoting NUCs using their online platforms and conducting workshops, training, and cooking demonstrations on farm, in schools and in national events. They promote the health and nutrition, environmental/landscape preservation and promotion of local agriculture qualities of their NUCs.

Why are your varieties NUCs?

They are not very cultivated, but are very good for the environment and health

Social mission

AGRIDEA works with a social mission, which is dedicated to fighting: food insecurity; unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices; climate change; biodiversity decline and unfair remuneration of producers. They are heavily involved with legumes in various projects

Benefits from selling NUCs

Consumer prices and profit margins for NUCs are the same as for similar, non-NUC products. AGRIDEA claims that they gain economic, environmental and political benefits from selling with NUCs. The economic benefit is delivered through diversification. The environmental benefit comes from the biodiversity conservation through NUCs, while the political benefits come from promoting less meat in the food system.

AGRIDEA fulfils an essential role as a link between research, popularisation, training and practice. Our mission is to provide important background documents such as data collections and practical tools. At the same time, we encourage innovation through projects. Our varied course offering aims to meet the individual needs of our customers and give them new impetus to move forward.

